

Chapter 5. Businesses as key actors in transformative change: options for action¹

Coordinating Lead Authors: Amrei von Hase (South Africa), Laura Jane Sonter (Australia)

Lead Authors: Jacolette Adam (South Africa), Steven Dickinson (France), Marie-Hélène Enrici (France), Thao Fabregas (France), Felicia Permata Sari Lasmana (Indonesia), Divya Narain (India, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Philippa Howard (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Natalia Lutti Hummel Wicher (Brazil), Hishmi Jamil Husain (India).

Fellows: Tuan Nguyen (Vietnam / Belgium)

Contributing Authors: Isabel Ashman (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland / United States of America), Pradeep Kumar Dubey (India), Nadine McCormick (Switzerland / United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Quentin Meekers (Belgium).

Review Editor: Olga Barbosa (Chile)

Co-chairs of the assessment: Matt Jones (United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland), Steve Polasky (United States of America), Ximena Rueda (Colombia).

Technical support unit: Alina Vera Paz, Olena Tarasova-Krasiieva, Orlando Vargas Rayo, Érika Peñuela Vega.

This chapter should be cited as: von Hase A., Sonter L.J., Nguyen T., Adam J., Dickinson S., Enrici M-H., Fabregas T., Howard P., Hummel Wicher N.L., Husain H.J., Lasmana F.P., Narain D., Vera Paz A., Tarasova-Krasiieva, O., Vargas-Ray O. (2026). **Chapter 5: Businesses as key actors in transformative change: options for action.** In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependence of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074573>

The designations employed and the presentation of material on the maps used in the assessment do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. These maps have been prepared or used for the sole purpose of facilitating the assessment of the broad biogeographical areas represented therein.

¹ Authors are listed with, in parentheses, their country or countries of citizenship, separated by a comma when they have more than one; and, following a slash, their country of affiliation, if different from that or those of their citizenship, or their organization if they belong to an international organization. The countries and organizations having nominated the experts are listed on the IPBES website (except for contributing authors who were not nominated).

Contents

Executive summary	1
Knowledge gaps	5
5.1. Introduction	7
5.2. Businesses as key actors	9
5.2.1. Roles for businesses in transformative change.....	9
5.2.2. The responsibility of businesses to act	12
5.3. Motivations and barriers	13
5.3.1. Internal and external factors driving business action	14
5.3.2. Barriers to business action.....	15
5.4. Business-led initiatives guiding business action	17
5.5. Options for business action: a typology	18
5.6. Private actions to address a business’s own impacts and dependencies	22
5.6.1. Corporate: actions to transform the business.....	22
5.6.2. Operations: actions to achieve outcomes at the site level	28
5.6.3. Value chain: actions to influence suppliers and customers.....	34
5.6.4. Additional private actions for financial institutions	41
5.6.5. Greening Finance.....	41
5.6.6. Financing Green	45
5.7. Actions to change the system and influence others	46
5.7.1. Delivering outcomes beyond impact mitigation goals	47
5.7.2. Directly supporting the enabling environment	47
5.7.3. Collaboration, partnerships and collective action.....	49
5.7.4. Social signalling actions to inspire action by others.....	52
5.8. References	54

List of boxes

Box 5.1. Greenwashing: challenges for business action on biodiversity.....	10
Box 5.2. Risks for businesses and financial institutions related to biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people	15
Box 5.3. Regulatory Barriers for Indigenous Peoples and local community-Led Businesses – The Tendu Leaf Trade, India	17
Box 5.4. Use and misuse of biodiversity credits in addressing business impacts on biodiversity...	33
Box 5.5. Voluntary sustainability standards	38
Box 5.6. Chain of custody initiatives to share knowledge and align practices: the case of the Aluminium Stewardship Initiative	40
Box 5.7. Place based initiatives to enable coordinated landscape action on biodiversity	51
Box 5.8. Partnerships and initiatives support benefit sharing and fair access to biodiversity: the case of South Africa’s rooibos tea industry.	52

List of figures

Figure 5.1. Roles for businesses: include private actions by businesses to address their own impacts and dependencies, system changing actions to create the enabling conditions for transformative change, and social signalling to influence and encourage actions by other actors.	10
---	-----------

Figure 5.2. The role that businesses can play in transformative change depends on their control over global biodiversity outcomes through private actions, and their influence over the actions taken by others through system changing actions and social signalling.....	12
Figure 5.3. Decision-making levels included in Chapter 5 private action typology (represented as boxes), the goals of actions taken at each level (described in text) and links in actions among levels (shown with arrows)..	19
Figure 5.4. The mitigation hierarchy, including actions to avoid, minimise, restore and offset. Note that conservation outcomes that contribute to renewing and regenerating biodiversity over and above a business' mitigation measures aimed at achieving no net loss outcomes would contribute to reversing biodiversity losses. Adapted from Maron et al., (2025).....	32
Figure 5.5. Typical agricultural commodity value chain (e.g., olives, olive oil) with six interconnected stages from production to end-use..	34

List of tables

Table 5.1. Business actions organized by their roles in transformative change, the decision-making levels at which they occur, and where impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are measured.....	20
Table 5.2. Factors favouring engagement with or disinvestment from a business	44

Executive summary

1. Businesses have a key role to play in scaling-up action to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity (*well established*) {5.1, 5.2, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7}. All businesses, including financial institutions, impact and depend on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. While an increasing number of businesses now assess their own biodiversity-related risks and opportunities, the groundswell of concerted and systemic action needed for transformative change is lacking and the projected outcome of continued business-as-usual is a net global drawdown in biodiversity. Many more businesses need to take more effective actions, including actions to recover biodiversity in areas of conservation priority. Businesses with significant control and influence over global biodiversity outcomes have a particularly large role to play. This includes primary industries with significant resources (e.g., land ownership), large private financial institutions and transnational corporations with substantial influence through their portfolios and value chains, and actors whose actions can shape regulatory frameworks and market conditions. Small and medium-sized businesses also play an important role, particularly supported through partnerships and collaborative initiatives, to implement actions and drive positive outcomes.

2. While some factors motivate business action on biodiversity, and business-led initiatives offer guidance for planning, implementation and reporting, significant barriers to transformative change remain (*well established*) {5.2, 5.3, 5.4}. Motivations for business action can be both intrinsic and instrumental, driven by internal values or external pressures, such as access to finance, opportunities to maximise profits through environmental markets or consumer demand for sustainable products. However, systemic barriers, such as existing business models and economic systems that externalise the costs of biodiversity loss, government policies that incentivise harmful practices and fail to regulate poorly performing actors, widespread gaps in data capacity and gaps in context-specific knowledge, continue to constrain action. These barriers are particularly acute for small and medium-sized enterprises, despite many of the strongest examples of action in favour of biodiversity coming from this group. Business-led initiatives have helped address some barriers, but their focus remains skewed toward large businesses in high-income countries, often prioritising disclosure and risk management over requirements to deliver tangible biodiversity outcomes. Some have also advanced faster than the scientific evidence underpinning their theories of change. Critically, businesses face a lack of clear expectations from consumers, investors and governments on what constitutes an appropriate and credible contribution to global biodiversity goals.

3. Businesses can act at four decision-making levels (corporate, operations, value chain and portfolio) to address their own biodiversity impacts and contribute to system-level changes that create enabling conditions for transformative change and inspire actions by others (*well established*) {5.2.1, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7}. Actions taken at one decision-making level drive actions at others. For example, at the corporate level, actions aim to transform the business by embedding biodiversity and nature's contributions to people into corporate goals and strategy, policies, governance, systems and culture. These actions must be supported by sufficient resources, stakeholder engagement, capacity-building, innovation and a consideration of alternative business models. Together, they enable businesses to address their own impacts and dependencies and deliver outcomes on the ground within their operations and across value chains. System-changing actions include responsibly advocating for the conservation and recovery of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and against incentives that cause damage and loss, either individually or through collaborative initiatives. This can include addressing government policies at different levels (from local to national, and international) and positions by industry and trade associations. Social signalling, aimed at influencing other actors' impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, is possible at all decision-making levels for both private and system changing actions; although this

relies on businesses first taking these actions themselves and needs to be supported by robust and transparent disclosures.

4. While measurement can guide and improve outcomes, many corporate-level actions can be implemented immediately, despite incomplete biodiversity data, especially when carried out through engagement with internal and external stakeholders (*established but incomplete*) {5.5, 5.6.1}. Corporate-level actions include establishing ambitious biodiversity commitments, targets and strategy, integrating these into broader business strategy, creating and revising policies and standards (including procurement, incentives, investment, product and service design and use, marketing, stakeholder engagement and grievance mechanisms) and developing associated management systems (including for measurement, monitoring and reporting), transitioning the business to support implementation (together with capacity and resourcing), and exploring alternative business models, where appropriate. Corporate actions are essential to set the direction and enable action at other decision-making levels and for driving measurement and use of knowledge and data in decision-making for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Opportunities exist to integrate biodiversity targets with other sustainability goals, including those related to climate and other components of nature, to improve uptake, implementation and outcomes. Meaningful engagement is key for knowledge acquisition, more democratic environmental governance, and improved corporate legitimacy in biodiversity conservation initiatives. This includes working with internal and external stakeholders to build capacity of staff, promote environmental leadership at the board level, gather diverse perspectives on biodiversity values and actions, receive input on biodiversity strategy and assessment of impacts and dependencies and target setting, establish alliances to audit, and to monitor and assess performance.

5. Delivering meaningful and lasting biodiversity outcomes on the ground requires business operations to conduct robust impact assessments, rigorously apply the mitigation hierarchy, and implement credible monitoring, adaptive management, and stakeholder engagement (*well established*) {5.6.2}. This includes undertaking environmental and social impact assessments at ecologically appropriate scales; applying the mitigation hierarchy in sequence to avoid, minimise, restore, and, as a last resort, offset negative impacts; monitoring biodiversity outcomes as well as actions; and engaging with rights-holders and stakeholders prior to, throughout and after the life of business operations. Although the mitigation hierarchy is recognised as leading practice, adoption remains partial, since many business activities and impacts fall outside regulatory requirements; even when applied, demonstrating sufficient impact avoidance is often difficult for businesses. Later-stage measures such as restoration and offsetting are typically more costly, uncertain, and less effective at returning biodiversity to baseline conditions, reinforcing the need to prioritise early-stage avoidance and minimisation. Very few business operations have achieved or demonstrated no net loss of biodiversity. Monitoring outcomes requires appropriate, sector-specific metrics that link actions to biodiversity targets, yet reporting often lacks sufficient data for independent verification. Early and ongoing engagement with affected communities, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities is essential to build trust, align actions with local priorities, and enable collaboration.

6. Numerous opportunities exist for action at the value chain level, particularly for businesses beyond primary and extractive sectors. Approaches that emphasise value chain integration, collaboration and innovation hold the greatest potential to lever transformative change (*well established*) {5.6.3, 5.7.3}. Biodiversity has received limited attention in the literature on sustainable value chain management, but examples of relevant actions and a growing body of guidance have emerged. Value chain mapping provides the transparency needed to link products and materials to specific suppliers, locations and impacts, helping businesses to identify risks and prioritise actions. Improving traceability is especially important for businesses with global or complex value chains, although mapping beyond tier-one suppliers often remains a challenge. Once value chains are mapped, businesses can set and communicate clear expectations for suppliers, monitor performance,

and address non-compliance, including, where appropriate, through suspension or exclusion of poor performers. Approaches that incentivise performance and build long-term relationships and supplier capacity through training, knowledge exchange, and innovation are essential and can be more effective. This is particularly critical for small businesses in enabling their adherence to biodiversity standards, supported by incentives and penalties. Voluntary sustainability standards can complement these efforts as part of due diligence systems, and consumer-facing strategies such as product labelling, education, incentives and post-purchase engagement provide opportunities to shape behaviour and improve transparency. Yet, their effectiveness is often constrained by consumer scepticism, the costs of certification, and business models reliant on unsustainable consumption.

7. Any effort to deliver transformative change depends on reversing harmful finance flows and allocating funds to achieve biodiversity outcomes aligned with global targets (*well established*) {5.6.1, 5.6.4}. Financial institutions can drive this shift through two complementary strategies: *greening finance*, which directs financial services away from activities that harm biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, and *financing green*, which channels funds toward biodiversity-enhancing activities. At the corporate and portfolio levels, lenders, investors and insurers can adopt a range of greening finance actions, including setting financing and investment criteria (e.g., biodiversity impact assessments, mitigation and no net loss/net gain requirements, and traceability and sourcing standards – applied at the level of the clients' projects or value chains), implementing stewardship by engaging with clients to align practices with biodiversity targets exercising voting rights, and excluding or divesting from harmful activities. At the same time, corporate-level financing mechanisms, such as blended finance, impact investing and green or sustainability-linked bonds, can mobilise capital for enterprises that protect, restore or sustainably manage biodiversity. This also extends to bilateral or multilateral contributions to initiatives such as the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund or the Cali Fund. The actions and their influence on biodiversity outcomes vary across financial institutions – for example, between lenders and investors – but all have a role in redirecting finance flows to support biodiversity outcomes.

8. Significant opportunities exist for businesses to help halt and reverse global biodiversity loss by going beyond impact mitigation to invest in landscape conservation, restoration and sustainable management and system-changing actions that create the enabling conditions for transformative change (*established by incomplete*) {5.5, 5.7.1, 5.7.2}. Achieving global goals requires businesses to extend accountability beyond impact mitigation actions at their operations and value chains, by supporting additional conservation efforts. Businesses with strong dependencies on biodiversity or historical contributions to loss are particularly well placed to contribute. Actions that focus on ecological recovery (e.g., restoring species habitat) should be prioritised over those that simply avert potential future loss (e.g., creating new protected areas). Nature-based solutions are also a key pathway, delivering biodiversity benefits while supporting other sustainable development goals, such as climate adaptation, water security, and social outcomes. Businesses further play a critical role in advocating for ambitious biodiversity policy, rejecting harmful lobbying, and ensuring that industry associations align with global goals. Leadership includes making progressive policies public, addressing grievances transparently, and signalling the importance of biodiversity and sustainable lifestyles to consumers and society, for example, by tackling food consumption and waste. While large corporations and sector-wide initiatives may influence national or multilateral regulatory processes, smaller businesses can also contribute by, for instance, engaging local authorities and chambers of commerce.

9. Collaboration, partnerships, and collective action with other businesses, governments and Indigenous Peoples and local communities can amplify biodiversity outcomes of business actions across all decision-making levels (*established by incomplete*) {5.3, 5.4, 5.6, 5.7.3}. Partnerships are essential for scaling implementation, enabling knowledge exchange, and ensuring more inclusive and legitimate governance. Trade associations and commodity roundtables can

complement regulation by developing shared standards and raising expectations of good practice, while public–private partnerships can unlock resources, technology, and governance capacity. Multi-stakeholder platforms and coalitions can align business strategies with global biodiversity targets, and sector-wide initiatives, including voluntary sustainability standards, create a level playing field and extend commitments across value chains. Partnerships that include Indigenous Peoples and local communities are important for ensuring equitable and durable outcomes. Transboundary initiatives and global collaborations can address biodiversity challenges no single actor can resolve alone. Through participation in financial associations and adoption of voluntary standards, such as the Green Bond Principles, businesses can also help align capital flows with biodiversity outcomes and embed accountability across internal systems. Collaboration and partnerships represent a critical pathway for scaling impact, aligning diverse interests, and embedding biodiversity into the core of business and financial systems.

10. Businesses could act more effectively with a clearer understanding of which actions, implemented where and by whom, drive positive biodiversity outcomes; which disclosures and reporting practices create meaningful change; and which tools best measure and manage impacts and dependencies at different decision-making levels (*established but incomplete*) {5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.6, 5.7}. Some evidence exists for operational-level actions with directly attributable outcomes, but most studies suggest these actions – including those aimed at achieving no net loss of biodiversity – have been largely ineffective to date. There is limited understanding of which actions at the broader landscape and system levels are most effective, how responsibilities should be shared among businesses depending on their dependencies and contributions to biodiversity loss, and what additional measures are needed to improve their effectiveness. Better, fit-for-purpose tools are required to systematically integrate innovation into business decision-making. Addressing these gaps will require a cultural shift, with businesses disclosing not only their impacts and dependencies, but also their actions, outcomes, and progress in closing shortfalls against biodiversity targets. While some voluntary standards already require disclosure to enable third-party verification, greater knowledge is needed to strengthen the theory of change linking transparency, visibility of failures, and incentives for improvement in performance.

Knowledge gaps

Category	Section	Knowledge gap
Studies relevant to business	5.1	Lack of evidence on whether businesses with the greatest responsibility to act are implementing the most impactful actions.
Data and knowledge	5.2	Lack of clarity from consumers, investors, and governments on what constitutes an appropriate and credible business contribution to global biodiversity goals.
Methods	5.2.2, 5.3.2	Insufficient methods to translate and disaggregate global biodiversity goals into business-level targets at scales meaningful for decision-making.
Methods	5.3.2, 5.6, 5.7	Lack of robust methods to independently assure business claims about contributions to net biodiversity outcomes.
Data and knowledge	5.3.2	Limited knowledge within businesses about biodiversity, including their own impacts and dependencies and how biodiversity loss translates into business risk and informs action.
Data and knowledge	5.3, 5.7	Limited knowledge and guidance on how small and medium-sized enterprises can overcome acute capacity and resource barriers.
Studies relevant to business	5.4	Need for stronger scientific evidence to underpin the guidance and inherent theories of change developed by business-led initiatives.
Data and knowledge	5.4, 5.6, 5.7	Limited illustrative examples of businesses taking actions, including their motivations and barriers, impacts and outcomes, and explanatory factors unpinning success and failure.
Studies relevant to business	5.4, 5.6, 5.7	Lack of empirical studies to test and validate a theory of change linking actions related to risk disclosure to biodiversity outcomes.
Data and knowledge	5.6, 5.7	Limited evidence on the effectiveness of different types of business actions – what works, in which contexts, and why.
Data and knowledge	5.6, 5.7	Limited availability of metrics and methods that capture multiple biodiversity values and perspectives to ensure actions deliver effective outcomes.
Data and knowledge	5.6	Lack of baseline biodiversity data to inform business actions at all decision-making levels.
Data and knowledge	5.6.1	Limited evaluation of how corporate governance tools (e.g., targets, policies, incentives, procurement, product design) translate into measurable biodiversity outcomes across scales.
Data and knowledge	5.6.2	Lack of rigour, consistency and clarity in environmental and social impact assessments, limiting their effectiveness in delivering biodiversity outcomes globally.

Data and knowledge	5.6.2	Inconsistent application of the mitigation hierarchy, with no agreed thresholds for avoidance, minimisation or offsetting, and weak evidence for restoration and offsets.
Methods	5.6.2, 5.7.1	Insufficient monitoring of site- and landscape-level outcomes, with inadequate metrics and no frameworks to assess whether cumulative actions contribute to global biodiversity goals.
Data and knowledge	5.6.3	Insufficient data on business value chains, including the location of operations and flows of globally impactful products, to enable biodiversity impact and dependency analysis.
Data and knowledge	5.6.3	Uncertainty about which consumer-facing strategies (labelling, education, incentives, post-purchase engagement) effectively change behaviour and deliver biodiversity outcomes.
Methods	5.6.4.2	Limited tools and scarce real-world applications for assessing biodiversity impacts and dependencies at the portfolio level.
Data and knowledge	5.6.4	Need for stronger evidence on how actions related to financial instruments and stewardship translate into biodiversity outcomes, and how lenders versus investors can best exert influence.
Data and knowledge	5.6.4	Insufficient biodiversity-related impact and dependency data collected by financial institutions (investors, lenders, insurers) on their investments and clients.
Methods	5.7	Lack of approaches to inform and monitor collective and system-changing actions, particularly for small and medium enterprises that depend on such initiatives.
Methods	5.7	Need for approaches to better integrate business action on biodiversity with other societal goals (e.g., on climate), to minimise trade-offs and avoid budget fragmentation.
Methods	5.6, 5.7	Insufficient methods to support effective capacity-building on biodiversity, across businesses and their value chains.
Data and knowledge	5.6, 5.7	Gaps in knowledge about mechanisms linking transparency (including visibility of failures) to improved biodiversity performance.
Data and knowledge	5.7.1, 5.6.2	Limited understanding of how to attribute biodiversity outcomes at landscape or system scales to specific business actions, to support credible claims.
Data and knowledge	5.7.2	Lack of evidence on effective and responsible business advocacy for biodiversity, including how to influence government policy and trade associations.

5.1. Introduction

Businesses, including private financial institutions, have a critical role to play in achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity, as part of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (O'Brien et al., 2024). Many businesses are large, powerful actors that significantly shape global consumption and production systems and thus have great potential to contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss. Approximately 500 businesses control over 70 per cent of key global commodity markets (OECD, 2015), many of which directly or indirectly impact on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (Carvalho et al., 2023). Some businesses have begun to act, often to meet regulatory obligations, respond to stakeholder pressure, or satisfy investor requirements. Others act to mitigate material risks to their operations and value chains that arise from declining biodiversity (G. S. Smith et al., 2021). As of July 2024, more than 420 organizations across 50 countries have committed to begin aligning with the guidance of the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures, including 25 per cent of the world's most important banks. However, the extent to which actions are being taken by those businesses with the greatest responsibility of – or whether they reflect interventions with the greatest benefit for – biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, remains unclear.

To date, the aggregate effect of business activity on biodiversity has been overwhelmingly negative (**Chapter 3**). Businesses have contributed to all five main direct drivers of biodiversity loss identified in the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (2019a): land- and sea-use change, direct exploitation, climate change, pollution and invasive species (IPBES, 2019a). For example, rapid expansion of oil palm plantations in Southeast Asia, driven by demand for vegetable oil, income growth and biofuel policies, has led to extensive deforestation and biodiversity decline (Carlson et al., 2012; Vijay et al., 2016; Wilcove & Koh, 2010). Large scale agricultural production for beef, palm oil, soy and wood caused 40 per cent of tropical deforestation between 2000 and 2011 (Henders et al., 2015). Most businesses still rely heavily on fossil fuels, contributing to both regional air pollution and climate change. Despite progress in some sectors, fossil fuels continue to account for ~80 per cent of global energy use (IEA, 2023) and some business models, such as aviation, still lack viable alternatives. Water withdrawals for irrigated agriculture, energy and manufacturing degrade freshwater ecosystems (Dudgeon et al., 2006; Reid et al., 2019), while global shipping facilitates the spread of invasive species (Hulme, 2009). Beyond the primary and extractive sectors, the value chain impacts of other businesses remain significant, yet often hidden in assessments of biodiversity loss and nature's contributions to people (Wieland, 2021), making it difficult to assign clear accountability for mitigating these impacts.

Business-as-usual trajectories, both in terms of the scale and effectiveness of current actions on biodiversity, are misaligned with global biodiversity goals and targets (Leclère et al., 2020). While there is growing recognition of nature-related risks, action remains slow and commitments often lack ambition (UNEP, 2024). Recent assessments found that most large and transnational businesses still fail to identify, assess or disclose their biodiversity impacts and dependencies (WBA, 2024) and financial institutions largely overlook or undervalue biodiversity, due to a poor understanding of how its loss creates portfolio risks (McElwee et al., 2020). However, even among those that do commit to action and disclosure, evidence of implementation and effectiveness remains limited, and there is a lack of accountability mechanisms to ensure that claimed positive actions lead to meaningful biodiversity outcomes (zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022). Some businesses have also been found to deliberately mask unsustainable practices under the guise of 'nature-positive' strategies, using aspirational framings to deflect their accountability (Buckley et al., 2025).

Transformative change will require additional action, especially by the businesses that have been most responsible for impacts to date and which have the greatest potential to influence future

conservation and regeneration outcomes. But this will also require fundamental reforms to internal business models and the external conditions (policy and legal frameworks, economic and financial systems, social values, norms and culture, technology and data, and capacity) within which businesses operate (IPBES, 2019, **Chapter 6**). In many cases, the absence of sufficient business incentives to act reflects a deeper framing problem: the economy is still treated as separate from, rather than embedded within, the biosphere (Dasgupta, 2021; Folke et al., 2021). As a result, the depletion of biodiversity is not adequately internalised in business decision-making, making it difficult for businesses to justify action under traditional interpretations of fiduciary duty, which typically prioritise short-term shareholder returns. Addressing this challenge will require complementary action by non-business actors, including governments, the financial system, civil society and Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs), to reshape incentive structures and prevent continued economic growth from undermining ecological foundations (White et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, given the urgency of the biodiversity crisis, there is a need for business to act in the absence of perfect enabling conditions, even if those actions are seemingly piecemeal (IPBES, 2024a). This includes scaling up actions at all levels of decision-making – from operations to value chains, and across portfolios – to address their own impacts and dependencies and to contribute towards broader systems change. In some cases, this will require businesses to go beyond short-term profitability, embracing new business models that prioritise long-term societal value. In other cases, it will require proactive engagement in advocacy and policy reform. Indeed, precedent exists. For example, in 2024, more than 130 businesses publicly endorsed policy recommendations for implementation of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and called for stronger biodiversity legislation (Business for Nature, 2024). Ultimately, these actions and their impact on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people will vary depending on the specific actor, sector, product and geography. Identifying priorities on where to act first, alongside the safeguards needed to manage remaining uncertainty and risks of greenwash, is essential to ensure business contributions collectively support global biodiversity goals.

Chapter 5 reviews options for business action to contribute to the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. **Section 5.2** conceptualises the roles businesses can play in transformative change and outlines methods available to determine their individual responsibility to act. **Section 5.3** examines the factors currently driving business action and remaining barriers, highlighting key differences across business types and geographic contexts. **Section 5.4** summarises the strengths and limitations of emerging risk disclosure frameworks and performance standards co-developed by businesses to guide action. **Section 5.5** presents a typology of business actions, organized by the decision-making levels at which biodiversity impacts and dependencies are measured, as described in **Chapter 4**. **Section 5.6** details options for private actions by businesses, including financial institutions, to address their own impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. **Section 5.7** outlines additional actions for businesses to drive the system-level change necessary for transformative change and influence the actions taken by others, including through partnerships and collective action. Examples of business action are provided throughout the Chapter and expanded in **Annex 5.1**. The evidence base for these examples remains limited, however, and inclusion does not imply endorsement or verification of performance.²

² Data management report referring to the literature reviews conducted for Chapter 5
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12789799>

5.2. Businesses as key actors

5.2.1. Roles for businesses in transformative change

Businesses and private financial institutions can play three interconnected roles in transformative change (Naito et al., 2022, Booth et al., 2024, **Figure 5.1**). (1) Private actions can be taken by businesses to address their own impacts and dependencies occurring from their operations, value chains and portfolios. Actions include assessing and mitigating biodiversity impacts, engaging with their suppliers and consumers to implement sustainable supply chain practices, and ensuring that corporate policies, processes and capacity drive and support these actions to deliver outcomes on the ground; (2) businesses can also take action to contribute beyond their own impact to reversing biodiversity loss and changing the system within which they operate by intentionally contributing to macro-level conditions enabling transformative change. For example, lobbying governments to strengthen laws and regulations to conserve biodiversity, shifting social norms and access to capital, and innovation in science and technology; (3) finally, businesses can publicly share and signal information about their actions and outcomes to inspire and influence the behaviour of other businesses and non-business actors. This could include marketing to showcase public commitments or certification of their products and services, provided that these actions are backed by credible strategies, commitments and tangible actions to avoid being perceived as greenwash (**Box 5.1**).

Figure 5.1. Roles for businesses. These roles include private actions by businesses to address their own impacts and dependencies, system changing actions to create the enabling conditions for transformative change, and social signalling to influence and encourage actions by other actors. All three roles can be taken individually or collectively through partnerships and collaborations. Figure adapted from Naito et al., (2022).

Box 5.1. Greenwashing: challenges for business action on biodiversity

Greenwashing occurs when businesses mislead stakeholders about the environmental benefits of their products, services or operations (Delmas & Burbano, 2011; Krause et al., 2021; zu Ermgassen, et al., 2022). It takes multiple forms, including the use of vague and undefined terms – such as ‘eco-friendly’ or ‘nature-positive’ – that lack measurable targets, clear and consistent definitions, or transparent reporting. These allow businesses to appear environmentally responsible without undertaking substantive action, undermining accountability and raising questions about the authenticity of their sustainability claims (Krause et al., 2021; zu Ermgassen, et al., 2022).

Selective disclosure is another form of greenwashing, in which businesses highlight positive environmental actions while concealing negative impacts (Lyon & Montgomery, 2015; Marquis et al., 2016). This erodes trust, diminishes the credibility of corporate sustainability efforts, and creates scepticism among stakeholders, including consumers, regulators and investors. It also creates reputational spillover, making it

harder for genuinely committed businesses to gain recognition or build support for legitimate biodiversity actions.

The fear of being accused of greenwashing can deter businesses from engaging in biodiversity initiatives altogether, particularly when reputational or legal risks are high and sustainability efforts are vulnerable to public scrutiny. These risks are amplified by inconsistent regulations, weak enforcement, and low institutional capacity, especially in developing countries and emerging markets (Krause et al., 2021; Treepongkaruna, 2024; zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022).

Addressing greenwashing risks requires a commitment to transparency and accountability. This includes setting clear, time-bound and measurable biodiversity targets aligned with global goals; using standardised frameworks for disclosing risks, impacts and dependencies, and participating in credible third-party verification schemes. Genuine collaboration with trusted partners and independent reviewers can further enhance credibility and reduce risks of unsubstantiated claims (Andréasson, 2023).

The impact that private actions, system change and signalling actions have on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, and their relative contribution towards global goals, will differ among businesses, dependent on their control and influence over biodiversity outcomes (**Figure 5.2**). Larger businesses, including transnational businesses, with greater resource use by their operations, can play a larger role than smaller businesses because they have greater impacts to address within their direct control (Folke et al., 2019). The World Benchmarking Association identified 2,000 of the most influential keystone businesses, highlighting their crucial role as economic actors in contributing to transformative change (WBA, 2024). Large businesses have influence through their direct control of large operations, but also through their influence on suppliers and customers in their value chains, and through their influence on other entities (other businesses, non-governmental organizations, IPLCs, and governments) (Ahen, 2019). Such businesses also have the potential to contribute to sustainable development and economic growth in low-income regions (Lawrence, 2023), as well as to shaping the economic landscapes of regions worldwide (Folke et al., 2019; Yeung, 2009).

Figure 5.2. The role of businesses in transformative change. The role that businesses can play in transformative change depends on their control over global biodiversity outcomes through private actions, and their influence over the actions taken by others through system changing actions and social signalling. Collective action can help to boost both the control and influence that any one individual actor has on biodiversity globally.

5.2.2. The responsibility of businesses to act

The degree to which businesses are responsible for achieving global goals for biodiversity – or to be held liable for any inaction – is a societal decision. **Chapter 6** discusses the roles of non-business actors, including consumers, governments and IPLCs, in creating the enabling environment for transformative change. To drive business action, this environment must include clear expectations on which sectors in which locations are required to act and what outcome for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people needs to be achieved by these actions (Booth et al. 2024; White et al. 2024). Laws and policies, from local to national scales, governing business operations and their value chains, including fiduciary duties of businesses to address material risks and uphold voluntary commitments, are also essential (Mair et al., 2024; Maron et al., 2018; Pascual et al., 2022). Some policy frameworks, including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, commit nations to take such action, including through National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (CBD, 2022)

and suggest responsibility is not evenly shared among business actors. Target 15, for example, emphasises a disproportionate responsibility for large and transnational businesses and financial institutions (CBD, 2022). Some business-led initiatives also provide tools to guide decisions on which impacts and dependencies are material and thus require action (SBTN, 2024). However, expectations for small and medium-sized businesses to contribute towards biodiversity targets are less clear (Panwar, 2023). While their individual influence is small, collective mechanisms to address sector-wide impacts can be powerful. For example, The Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil has successfully traced impacts for over 48,990 farmers in 13 countries since 2013 (RSPO, 2024).

Uncertainty remains on whether societal responsibilities of businesses to act will 'add up' to achieve global goals for biodiversity (White et al., 2024). Missing are clear methods for businesses to disaggregate global biodiversity goals, at a resolution that is sufficient to support effective decision-making to enable businesses to act. Some progress has been made in defining planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023; Simmonds et al., 2022) and developing metrics and methods to enable related downscaling of business action (Clift et al., 2017; Crona et al., 2024). This approach is now being implemented for some global goals, such as mitigating climate change and achieving land, freshwater and oceans targets (SBTi, 2024, 2025; SBTN, 2020). The concept of planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023) has not yet led to defining specific limits for the full breath of biodiversity components, nor are rules for fair shares of resources clearly defined, making this concept difficult to understand by business actors (Clift et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2025), although used in the Science-Based Target Network (SBTN, 2020) and researched to identify rules by which 'fair shares' could be allocated to actors (Bai et al., 2024). Some biodiversity goals and targets, including those of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and others (UNEP, n.d.), are not framed as ecological limits or outcomes-based targets (Maron et al., 2018), with clear actionable and time bound objectives (Hawkins et al., 2023). Without this, a disconnect remains between global goals, national policies, and project requirements to mitigate impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

Finally, regardless of how much each business acts, they can also make efforts to ensure that any action they take has fair and equitable outcomes that align with the principles of the Convention on Biological Diversity, including benefit sharing and sustainable use of natural resources. When taking actions to improve biodiversity on lands and seas, including freshwater ecosystems, under the custodianship of IPLCs, whose livelihoods and cultural heritage are often deeply connected to their natural environments. This includes recognising, respecting and upholding the rights, knowledge systems, leadership structures and multifaceted ways in which communities conserve and manage biodiversity, and integrating Indigenous and local knowledge and perspectives into decision-making, including those related to building local resilience against future risks to biodiversity loss (Dawson et al., 2021, Kennedy et al., 2023). To integrate responsibility measures, businesses can also uphold Free Prior and Informed Consent and the rights granted to Indigenous Peoples, as recognized in the United Nation's Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (United Nations, 2008).

5.3. Motivations and barriers

Motivations and barriers to business action depend on the context in which businesses operate. While an action may be possible for one company in one country, it may be impossible in others. For example, small and medium enterprises operating in developing countries might be particularly constrained by access to capital, internal capacity and regulatory uncertainties (Durrani et al., 2024). Regardless of the context, businesses are driven to act by a mix of internal and external motivations (Graafland & Van De Ven, 2006). Internal motivations can be both intrinsic, stemming from moral norms, values and ethics, and instrumental, based on perceived business benefits. Chapter 5 organizes barriers according to the enabling conditions for transformative change, described in **Chapter 6**: legal

and regulatory; economic and financial, norms and values; technology and data; and capacity and knowledge. This section includes examples of how motivations and barriers differ among business types, sectors and geographies. **Sections 5.4 and 5.7** include options for businesses to address barriers, through individual and collective action.

5.3.1. Internal and external factors driving business action

Intrinsic motivations stem from the moral norms, personal experiences, and environmental values of individual staff, as well as broader corporate culture. They often reflect a collective sense of social responsibility to address biodiversity loss (Jia et al., 2018; Krause et al., 2021). For example, individuals' views on conservation have informed and shaped decision-making within the Chilean wine industry (Márquez-García et al., 2018).

Instrumental motivations are linked to the expected organizational benefit of acting on biodiversity. These include improved company attractiveness, higher productivity and stronger employee retention (Bauer & Aiman-Smith, 1996; Bhattacharya et al., 2008; Greening & Turban, 2000; Gully et al., 2013; Hedblom et al., 2019). Action can deliver financial returns in several ways. They can enable businesses to enter new markets with innovative products and services, as demonstrated by examples from the cosmetics sector in Europe and South America (Kolenova et al., 2025; Turconi et al., 2021). Businesses may also improve their market share by greening existing offerings and positioning themselves ahead of less sustainable competitors (Lambooy & Levashova, 2011). Operational efficiencies can also be enhanced; regenerative agriculture in California's almond industry, for example, has reduced costs while improving productivity (Fenster et al., 2021). Further, pro-environmental practices can lead to lower payroll costs for equivalent work and contribute to stronger employee engagement and retention (Burbano, 2016; Cassar, 2019; Cassar & Meier, 2018; Krueger et al., 2020; Lozano, 2015; Non et al., 2022; Nyborg & Zhang, 2013). Some businesses also see talent attraction as a benefit (Aladağ, 2023; Krause et al., 2021); 77 per cent of sustainability leaders cite this as a driver for sustainable strategy development (SpencerStuart, 2023). Additional incentives include preferential access to finance and markets (Flammer et al., 2025) and, in some cases, biodiversity disclosure itself can improve financial performance (Elsayed, 2023). For businesses that directly depend on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, acting can serve to mitigate material financial risks associated with biodiversity loss (**Box 5.2**).

Many of these motivations are shaped by factors external to the business. Regulatory obligations are a major driver. Biodiversity-related laws and policies in e.g., the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (UK Government, 2023), the European Union and Latin America (Villarroya et al., 2014) require businesses to address their impacts on biodiversity. Non-compliance can result in significant penalties, including fines, restricted market access, operational delays and refusal of permits (Smith et al., 2019) (J. W. Bull & Strange, 2018). Businesses may also be motivated by the conditions placed on access to finance, supplier agreements or procurement contracts. Meeting the safeguard requirements of financial institutions and the sustainability criteria of consumers and investors has become increasingly important (Adler et al., 2017; Jia et al., 2018). Adoption of voluntary frameworks for biodiversity risk disclosure and target setting can help reduce legal and reputational risks (Aladağ, 2023) and maintain a social licence to operate (Vanclay, 2017), particularly as businesses expand their view of stakeholders to include communities, civil society and the general public (Freeman et al., 2007). Businesses that are trusted by local communities and have established partnerships often experience fewer operational disruptions, while protecting the livelihood options of those affected by their activities (Gehman et al., 2017). Businesses with consumer-facing brands are also motivated to introduce sustainability policies to enhance their brand value and obtain a green premium for marketed products (Coqueret et al., 2025; Gomez-Trujillo et al., 2020; Mayer & Gereffi, 2010). These businesses are particularly attuned to shifts in public expectations and the risks of perceived inaction on environmental issues.

Box 5.2. Risks for businesses and financial institutions related to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

Biodiversity loss presents a range of material risks for businesses. These include physical risks, such as disruptions to value chains caused by ecosystem degradation, and transition risks, such as increased compliance costs due to stricter environmental regulations. These risks can, in turn, translate into risks for financial institutions that lend to, invest or insure businesses, manifesting as loan defaults, asset devaluation, or insurance losses (NGFS, 2024).

Many of these risks are endogenous, meaning that they originate from the businesses' own activities. Others are exogenous, arising from broader socio-political, climatic or macroeconomic shocks (Danielsson & Shin, 2003). Under the principle of double materiality, which considers both the impact of financial activities on biodiversity and the implications of biodiversity loss for a business's financial performance, managing endogenous risks becomes a strategic imperative.

Addressing these risks requires robust assessment, measurement and disclosure. While an increasing number of voluntary frameworks offer guidance (**Section 5.4**), the current landscape remains fragmented. There is an urgent need to harmonize frameworks and move toward mandatory requirements to measuring, managing and disclosing biodiversity-related impacts, dependencies, risks and opportunities.

5.3.2. Barriers to business action

Existing business models remain one of the most significant barriers to transformative change. The prevailing emphasis on short-term profit maximisation, reinforced by the fiduciary duty of executives to deliver financial returns to shareholders, has historically impeded action on biodiversity (Krause et al., 2021; Panwar, 2023; Schaltegger et al., 2023). Publicly listed businesses are less likely to act than private businesses, likely due to shareholder pressures and short-term reporting cycles (Gartenberg & Serafeim, 2023; Li & Wu, 2020). This is particularly true for actions requiring significant upfront investment with limited immediate return (Chen et al., 2025). Quarterly and annual financial reporting can discourage planning over periods that are compatible with ecological timeframes and, while there is some movement toward incorporating broader societal value into corporate mandates, fiduciary duty rarely extends to environmental or social impacts in practice (Treepongkaruna, 2024).

Short-termism, however, is not the only obstacle to taking action to halt and reverse biodiversity loss and enable its sustainable use and fair benefit sharing. Businesses also face complex and interrelated financial, regulatory, technological and organizational barriers, many of which are particularly acute for small enterprises and businesses operating in developing economies. Access to capital for biodiversity-related investment remains limited and, even when financing is available, biodiversity actions often compete with other sustainability priorities (Mammen, 2024; WEF, 2025). While nature-based solutions offer strong economic and ecological returns, current global investment (around \$220 billion in 2023, with just 10 per cent from the private sector) falls far short of the \$571 billion needed per year by 2030 (UNEP, 2026). Meanwhile, approximately \$7.3 trillion was directed in 2023 towards activities that have negative impacts on nature (UNEP, 2026). Of this total, public finance flows through environmentally harmful subsidies accounted for approximately \$2.4 trillion, directed primarily towards fossil fuels (\$1.13 trillion), agriculture (\$0.41 trillion), water (\$0.40 trillion), transport (\$0.18 trillion), construction (\$0.15 trillion) and fisheries (\$0.06 trillion) (UNEP, 2026). The private sector was responsible for the majority of the nature-negative finance flows in 2023, estimated at \$4.9 trillion and concentrated on utilities (\$1.6 trillion), industrials (\$1.4 trillion), energy (\$0.7 trillion) and basic materials, including fertilizers and agricultural inputs (\$0.7 trillion) (UNEP, 2026).

Financial barriers are even greater for smaller businesses and those operating in emerging markets (World Bank, 2019). As of 2020, the credit gap for formal micro, small, and medium sized enterprises in these regions was approximately \$5.7 trillion (19 per cent of Gross Domestic Product), limiting

their growth and resilience to economic shocks (Carvajal & Didier, 2024; World Bank, 2019). Businesses without a proven track record find it especially difficult to secure funding and high transaction costs –linked to due diligence, legal title issues or community engagement – can deter investors (Lambooy & Levashova, 2011; McQuaid et al., 2021). Externally, market pressures and consumer behaviour can also limit action (Makepa & Chihobo, 2024). While stakeholder expectations, such as green consumerism, can drive action, their influence on outcomes depends heavily on stakeholder values (Krause et al., 2021). In many cases, consumer preferences for affordability and convenience outweigh environmental concerns, particularly in sectors such as food and transport (OECD, 2023).

Regulatory and policy barriers constrain business action. National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) often lack the ambition and specificity needed to guide or incentivise private sector contributions to global goals (Bell-James & Watson, 2025). Although some countries directly reference business action – for instance, Malaysia's National Policy on Biological Diversity (Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, 2016) – policies vary widely across jurisdictions. This creates legal uncertainty and complexity, particularly for multinational businesses (Clift et al., 2017; Heinrich et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2021). Weak enforcement, particularly in jurisdictions with limited governance capacity, further undermines policy effectiveness (Jia et al., 2018; Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen et al., 2018; Krause et al., 2021). In some cases, government incentives or subsidies can also drive business behaviour that contradicts biodiversity goals and targets, promoting unsustainable practices or excluding opportunities for Indigenous and informal sector businesses (Myers, n.d.) (**Box 5.3**). Even when regulations exist, high compliance costs may lead businesses to treat them as procedural requirements rather than taking meaningful biodiversity action.

Data and technology gaps pose challenges. Businesses require data on biodiversity impacts, dependencies, risks and opportunities to set targets, prioritise actions and track performance (Panwar, 2023; Schaltegger et al., 2023). However, data needs and availability vary by decision-making levels and business context (see **Chapter 4**). Financial institutions often need standardised metrics for portfolio-wide assessment (Clément & Grenon, 2025) while site-specific data – sometimes down to species-level information – is essential for planning at the level of operations (zu Ermgassen, et al., 2022). While in some cases these data do not exist, in others they are simply not obtainable from a company's internal tracking and data management systems. Lack of data transparency can particularly constrain businesses with value chains across multiple countries (Salmi et al., 2023) and the proliferation of biodiversity metrics can create confusion, inconsistent reporting and inefficiencies in external monitoring (Zhu et al., 2024). In many cases, essential biodiversity data is not accessible because of paywalls or weak data-sharing practices, both resulting from insufficient funding (McKenzie et al., 2025; White et al., 2023). Acknowledging and interweaving Indigenous and local knowledge is also essential yet often overlooked (Heinrich et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2021). Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and remote sensing, can improve precision and scalability, but immature or inaccessible tools may also introduce ethical risks and widen capacity gaps, especially for resource-constrained businesses (Chang & Slaubaugh, 2017; Purwandani & Michaud, 2021; Ullah et al., 2024).

Capacity constraints also create barriers. Many businesses lack the internal knowledge and skills to understand or act on biodiversity impacts, particularly at the executive level (Boiral et al., 2019; Krause et al., 2021; zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022; Lambooy & Levashova, 2011; Panwar, 2023; White et al., 2023). Externally, investors and financial institutions often lack awareness of biodiversity-related risks and opportunities (Lambooy & Levashova, 2011). While some pension funds have begun to acknowledge the long-term value of environmental, social and governance issues (Clark & Hebb, 2004; Tilba & McNulty, 2013), their reliance on external service providers and limited in-house expertise remain barriers (Tilba & McNulty, 2013; Yamahaki & Marchewitz, 2024). Tools such as natural capital accounting could help bridge these gaps by linking biodiversity condition

and ecosystem service flows to business and financial risk (Ingram et al., 2024), but uptake and integration remain limited across sectors (Parkhurst et al., 2025).

Within businesses, organizational structures and cultures present additional barriers. Biodiversity-related responsibilities are frequently siloed within sustainability or compliance teams, limiting coordination with core business functions, such as procurement, operations and strategy design (Schaltegger et al., 2023). Although guidance to build internal capacity is increasing, many businesses (especially small to medium-sized enterprises) receive little support. Smaller businesses typically lack personnel, access to relevant data and tools, and tailored sustainability reporting guidance (Van Tulder & Da Rosa, 2014). Capacity constraints also vary by sector; for example, industries with fragmented value chains may struggle to coordinate action between upstream extraction and downstream processing. Organizational culture can also limit action. Traditional leadership styles and a preference for the status quo can entrench existing business models, especially in the absence of strong external pressures (Krause et al., 2021). Path dependencies and legacy systems may discourage innovation or delay necessary changes (Chesbrough, 2002). Many businesses continue to view biodiversity as immaterial to their operations (Addison et al., 2019; zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022).

Box 5.3. Regulatory barriers for Indigenous Peoples and local community-led businesses – The Tendu Leaf Trade, India

Tendu leaves (*Diospyros melanoxylon* L.), known as 'green gold', are a valuable non-timber forest product in India, primarily used to roll *bidis* – a traditional Indian cigarette. India produces between 300 billion and 1 trillion *bidi* sticks annually, with 61,000 tonnes of bidi tobacco exported globally (Jain et al., 2024). The leaves are harvested across several Indian states, including Madhya Pradesh (the largest producer (Lele et al., 2015)), Maharashtra, Bihar, Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu. For many Indigenous communities in these regions, tendu leaves represent a major source of income – contributing 20 – 40 per cent of annual earnings among tribal households (Guleria & Gautam, 2021).

Millions of tribal workers, particularly women, are engaged in tendu leaf collection in Central India. The process is labour-intensive, requiring careful plucking, bundling and drying. Historically, the trade has been unorganized and largely tax-exempt, resulting in significant volumes of unaccounted *bidi* production (Jain et al., 2024). Collection was previously controlled by the Forest Department, with tribal workers forced to negotiate with private contractors who frequently exploited them through low wages, delayed payments and poor record-keeping (Sharma, 2003). Collectors often received as little as INR 5,000 per 1,000 bundles, with payments and bonuses delayed for up to two years (Yadav & Prajapati, 2023).

The enactment of India's Forest Rights Act (FRA) in 2006 marked a turning point, granting tribal communities Community Forest Resource (CFR) rights over minor forest products, including tendu leaves. In Maharashtra's Korchi block (Gadchiroli district), more than 90 *gram sabhas* (village assemblies) united to form the Mahagramsabha federation, securing direct ownership of the tendu leaf trade (Srivastava, 2024). This governance model has empowered local communities to negotiate higher prices – raising earnings from INR 4,500 in 2013 to INR 11,000 in 2022 per standard bag (Yadav & Prajapati, 2023).

Recognising and supporting tribal rights over forest resources has not only improved livelihoods but also enhanced environmental outcomes. By eliminating the role of exploitative contractors, community-led governance has reduced forest degradation and promoted more sustainable harvesting practices. The result is greater biodiversity protection, improved carbon sequestration and enhanced ecosystem resilience (Lele et al., 2015). This model potentially secures sustainable livelihoods for over 32 million hectares of forest-dependent communities in India (Yadav & Prajapati, 2023).

5.4. Business-led initiatives guiding business action

A diverse and rapidly growing set of business-led initiatives has emerged to support corporate action on biodiversity, offering performance standards, disclosure frameworks and guidance on assessing impacts and dependencies, setting targets and planning actions. These initiatives aim to address

barriers to action (**Section 5.3.2**) and provide guidance to help businesses identify impacts (SBTN, 2020), define roadmaps and prioritise actions (TNFD, 2023b) including for different sectors (Business for Nature, n.d.-b; WBCSD, 2023b) and apply good practice (Baggaley et al., 2023; Locke et al., 2021). However, requirements vary considerably, most remain weighted toward risk disclosure and reporting, and uptake across the wider business sector is insufficient to deliver the necessary scale and speed of action. Some initiatives apply universally, while others are sector- or region-specific. Voluntary disclosure frameworks show the greatest alignment, yet important differences remain on concepts such as materiality and “nature positive” (Milner-Gulland, 2022; UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI, 2024). Greater harmonisation of standards, metrics and methods across sectors and countries could enable more systematic tracking of business actions and biodiversity outcomes. The needs of small and medium-sized enterprises, particularly in the global South, are also often overlooked (Mukherjee et al., 2024), despite some targeted efforts (Business and Biodiversity, 2022; EFRAG, 2022). Many initiatives have also outpaced the science needed to support them (White et al. 2024) and poorly standardised or voluntary approaches risk delivering limited or counterproductive outcomes (Mair et al., 2024). While IPBES provides science-based recommendations for all stakeholder groups, including business, these have not yet been consistently framed or communicated to define a clear, cohesive role for business and finance in enabling transformative change (IPBES, 2024a; Pörtner et al., 2021).

5.5. Options for business action: a typology

A broad range of options for business action exists, which can be organized into the three roles businesses play in driving transformative change: (1) private actions to address a business's own impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people; (2) directly changing and creating the enabling conditions for transformative change; and (3) signalling these actions and their outcomes to influence and inspire actions taken by other businesses and non-business actors (**Section 5.2.1, Chapter 6**). These actions can be implemented at the four business decision-making levels at which biodiversity impacts and dependencies are measured – corporate, operations, value chains and portfolio (**Table 5.1**) – using the tools for measurement described in **Chapter 4**.

Chapter 5 highlights options for business actions from the perspective of an individual business, first focusing on private actions taken at each decision-making level (**Section 5.6**) and then expanding to include system-changing actions and social signalling (**Section 5.7**). A range of illustrative options for action are provided, rather than a comprehensive suite tailored to specific business types, sectors or geographic contexts, and the types of actions that can be taken at different decision-making levels are summarised in **Table 5.1**. Actions are needed at all decision-making levels and by all businesses, including financial institutions, although priorities on where and how to act first will differ depending on their size, sector, value chain role and impact distribution, where outcomes can be achieved most effectively, and their degree of control and influence over stakeholders. For example, a mining company may prioritise action first at the operational level, while a retailer selling forestry or food products may need to focus first on value chain-related actions. Example actions taken or reported in practice are provided in **Annex 5.1**. However, the evidence base for these examples is limited, and inclusion does not imply endorsement or verification of performance.

Close links exist between actions implemented across decision-making levels (**Figure 5.3**). For instance, targets set at the corporate level drive actions and outcomes at the operational and value chain levels. These levels also reflect a flow of information: from the operational, where impacts and dependencies occur and outcomes are delivered, to the corporate and portfolio levels, where strategic decisions can reshape business models. Many actions also have multiple effects – for example, changes to corporate strategy can influence procurement practices and advocacy positions, which in turn can drive broader system change. Similarly, enabling conditions influenced by pro-biodiversity

advocacy may create the need for revised strategies or changes to operational or value chain decisions (T. Smith et al., 2020). A key intended outcome of value chain actions is for suppliers to implement their own on-the-ground activities to deliver outcomes (Maron et al., 2023).

All actions need to form part of a due diligence process (Lumme et al., 2023). Many actions can be taken immediately, even before detailed assessments are completed, particularly those related to strategy, policy, resourcing or product design (Addison et al., 2019). However, all should be informed by appropriate measurement, which is also essential for tracking performance and outcomes (**Chapter 4**) (Smith et al., 2020). Important is also to note the overwhelming lack of verified evidence on the scale of implementation of actions by businesses and on the outcomes of these actions for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

Figure 5.3. Decision-making levels included in Chapter 5 private action typology (represented as boxes), the goals of actions taken at each level (described in text) and links in actions among levels (shown with arrows). For example, action to transform the business can enable actions by operations to achieve outcomes at sites.

Table 5.1. Business actions organized by their roles in transformative change, the decision-making levels at which they occur, and where impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people are measured.

	Corporate (Section 5.6.1)	Operations (Section 5.6.2)	Value chain (Section 5.6.3)	Portfolio (financial institutions: greening finance) (Section 5.6.4.2–4)
Private actions to address impacts and dependencies (Section 5.6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set ambition and integrate biodiversity in corporate strategy • Create policies, develop management systems and clarify requirements for engagement, measurement, monitoring, reporting, disclosures and assurance • Transition the business, build capacity and ensure adequate resourcing to implement policies and achieve targets • Innovate in processes, products and services • Explore and adopt alternative business models <p><i>Additional actions for financial institutions:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Greening finance (Section 5.6.4.1) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set requirements for clients to take private actions – Financing green (Section 5.6.4.5–7) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blended Finance • Green or sustainability-linked bonds • Impact investing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct environmental and social impact assessments • Apply the mitigation hierarchy to achieve no net loss of biodiversity or better • Measure and monitor biodiversity impacts and outcomes of actions • Identify and meaningfully engage with stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map value chain actors and ensure traceability to prioritise and inform action • Use supplier management systems to set expectations, monitor performance and address non-compliance • Build relationships and partnerships to build capacity and drive improved performance • Engage, educate and incentivise downstream customers, clients and consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess biodiversity impacts and dependencies • Manage biodiversity risk and impacts through stewardship, divestment and/or exclusion

Actions to change the system and influence others (Section 5.7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Deliver conservation outcomes beyond impact mitigation• System changing actions:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Engage responsibly in policy and advocacy○ Contribute to standard-setting and guidance across and within sectors, and collaborate on chain-of-custody initiatives○ Innovate and share data, technology, and research openly to improve biodiversity outcomes○ Build capacity and exchange knowledge, including through industry associations○ Advocate for and collaborate on coordinated biodiversity disclosure for consumer products○ Educate consumers on biodiversity impacts and sustainable choices• Collaborate and form partnerships to drive collective action• Signal leadership to inspire action by others:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Report externally on biodiversity impacts, dependencies, risks and opportunities○ Publicise participation in biodiversity-related initiatives and industry associations○ Promote the use of credible voluntary standards and certification schemes○ Disclose actions and outcomes to demonstrate biodiversity performance
--	--

5.6. Private actions to address a business's own impacts and dependencies

5.6.1. Corporate: actions to transform the business

Corporate-level actions involve strategic decisions that shape a company's overall direction and long-term performance. These decisions are needed to implement private actions at the operations and value chain levels (**Section 5.6.2 and 5.6.3**) and enable system changing actions (**Section 5.7**), they also drive the need for measurement and monitoring of biodiversity to further inform decisions and action. Corporate actions include: (1) setting ambition and integrating biodiversity in corporate strategy; (2) creating policies and standards to implement those strategies, including systems for measurement, monitoring and reporting; (3) transitioning the business in line with those policies, including shifts in governance and organizational structures, capacity-building and management, and incentives; (4) innovating in processes, products and services; and (5) exploring alternative business models and adopting these when appropriate.

5.6.1.1. Setting ambition and integrating biodiversity in corporate strategy

Biodiversity strategies reflect business motivations, ethos and ambitions, while addressing dependencies and impacts, regulatory requirements and stakeholder expectations (Macellari et al., 2018). Such strategies define: i) the organization's objective with respect to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and its scope; ii) the organizational structures needed to achieve it; iii) the necessary allocation of financial, human and technical resources; and iv) the role of business-unit management in coordinating activities to deliver desired outcomes. Objectives are commonly expressed as targets, which include environmental and social outcomes alongside financial performance targets. To track progress, key performance indicators are formulated. In some cases, these follow the 'SMART framework' – specific, measurable, accepted, realistic and time-bound targets – although many businesses adopt only some of these principles (Addison et al., 2019; 2024). Targets and indicators can be set independently (e.g., committing to protect a defined number of hectares in the headwaters of a business's key water supply) or aligned with collective initiatives and international goals (Haffar & Searcy, 2018).

While the number of businesses setting biodiversity targets is increasing, substantial variation exists among them and evidence of effectiveness in delivering outcomes for biodiversity is limited (Hawkins et al., 2023; Mair et al., 2024; zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022). Targets can encompass specific net outcomes, such as no net loss, net positive impact, net gain of biodiversity, or zero deforestation (PBAF, 2022, Global Canopy & UNEP FI, 2020). For instance, mining company Anglo American has a corporate-level net positive impact target to leave biodiversity within their operational area in a better condition than before the business arrived (**Annex 5.1**). Such commitments can be framed explicitly to align with overarching global or national goals (e.g., Hermes, a French luxury apparel and fashion business, states alignment of its biodiversity targets with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and France's National Biodiversity Strategy for 2030; **Annex 5.1**), although doing this is uncommon and rarely done in a quantitative way (Haffar & Searcy, 2018) and with a limited scope. Evidence from Fortune 100 businesses shows that by 2021, 46 had some biodiversity commitments, skewed towards sectors with significant operational impacts such as energy, compared with service-based sectors, and that only nine had defined SMART targets – a small increase from 2016 (zu Ermgassen, Drewniok, et al., 2022). Further, many service-based businesses appear to consider biodiversity of limited materiality to their core operations (Addison et al., 2019), although significant biodiversity impacts remain in their value chains (J. W. Bull et al., 2022).

Identification and assessment of a business's impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people is an important early step to take. Findings can help inform and refine targets, strategies and action (Schaltegger et al., 2022), with much emerging guidance focused on corporate biodiversity measurement (see **Chapter 4**). High-level work on this can correct misconceptions by managers and others that a business does not interface with biodiversity and nature's contributions to people at all (Schaltegger et al., 2022).

For financial institutions, biodiversity strategies can include plans to shift private capital towards outcomes consistent with halting and reversing biodiversity loss. This reflects the growing recognition that the finance sector needs to commit resources to restoration and conservation to close the global biodiversity financing gap (see **Sections 5.6.4.5–5.6.4.7**). One example is the AGRI3 Fund, established by Rabobank and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), which uses blended finance instruments – including de-risking mechanisms, such as first-loss guarantees – to enable commercial banks to invest in deforestation-free agriculture, forest conservation and rural development (**Annex 5.1**). Target-setting for biodiversity within financial institutions typically begins with identifying sectors and industries with significant biodiversity exposure, as these represent potential sources of financially material risks. Target-setting can also be guided by alignment with sustainable finance frameworks, such as the Equator Principles, the Principles for Responsible Banking, the Principles for Sustainable Insurance, or the UN-supported Principles for Responsible Investment, to which institutions may be signatories (Global Canopy & UNEP FI, 2020).

Biodiversity strategies, including targets, can be informed and strengthened through internal and external stakeholder engagement, including employees, investors, policymakers, suppliers and consumers, academia, other businesses operating within the same landscapes and IPLCs (Schaltegger et al., 2023; TNFD, 2023a; UN Global Compact and IUCN, 2012). Each business will have a unique set of stakeholders, with specific needs, interests and expectations, and with whom a dialogue is needed to manage relations. Approaches exist to identify and appropriately engage with these groups (Human Rights and Biodiversity Working Group, 2024; IFC, 2007; Kvam, 2019; Vanclay & Esteves, 2024; World Bank, 2017). Engagement also provides opportunity to recognise diverse values of biodiversity in strategies and target setting (IPBES, 2022). Strategies based on employee involvement, for example, are more effective and can be implemented without comprehensive measurement, drawing on tacit knowledge on biodiversity issues held among employees (Boiral et al. 2019). Engagement and communication with internal stakeholders can also help build stronger relationships, aligning on goals, working more efficiently, sharing resources, exchanging ideas, and improving support for proposed strategies, policies and action on biodiversity (Dzhengiz & Niesten, 2020a; Singh et al., 2019).

When a business's biodiversity strategy is integrated with other sustainability goals and into the broader corporate strategy, it becomes more prominent to managers and employees which can lead to better outcomes. For example, businesses with greater climate-risk awareness tend to have higher quality biodiversity reporting (Bassen et al., 2025); however, this awareness may not translate to improved material risk management for businesses and their investors. Four key elements have been proposed for integrated biodiversity into broader corporate strategy (zu Ermgassen, et al., 2022). These include: defining the scope to demonstrate biodiversity outcomes across the organizations full value chain; mainstreaming biodiversity throughout corporate strategies, including through securing organization-wide buy-in; recognising and amplifying interlinkages between biodiversity and other sustainability ambitions, including climate change; and ensuring that measurable outcomes are made against a fixed baseline and aligned with broader societal goals.

Once strategies are defined, businesses can undertake a series of actions to implement these. Strategy and implementation will evolve and be refined over time, as assumptions are tested, ambition grows, and external factors come into play.

5.6.1.2. Creating policies, developing management systems and clarifying requirements for engagement, measurement, monitoring, reporting, disclosures and assurance

The first step in implementing a biodiversity strategy is to establish policies that guide actions across operations and value chains. Policies, standards, and protocols clarify expectations for internal and external actors, and may draw on international standards (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), n.d., 2025), voluntary sustainability standards developed by industry associations or third parties (e.g., by the Global Reporting Initiative) or bespoke company approaches.

Effective integration requires both top-down measures (corporate strategy, policy, governance) and bottom-up engagement (employees, value chains), supported by indicators and regular reporting (**Section 5.6.1.1**). While businesses often prioritise operational interventions, systemic solutions are critical to avoid negative biodiversity impacts and promote lasting change (Addison et al., 2020; Panwar, 2023; T. Smith et al., 2019). Embedding biodiversity across all business functions – procurement, operations, finance, marketing, human resources, governance, and strategy – can shift companies from piecemeal actions to coordinated approaches that address root causes of biodiversity loss.

Corporate policies and management systems help align commitments with ambition and targets. They typically cover resource efficiency, waste, water and energy use (including climate action), governance and risk management, performance incentives, procurement and sourcing, due diligence, stakeholder engagement and grievance mechanisms, marketing and auditing. To be effective, policies must be actionable across operations and value chains and adaptable to diverse contexts (WBCSD, 2023; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022).

Corporate commitments such as avoiding ecosystem conversion or respecting Indigenous Peoples and local community rights cascade into procurement and product policies. These commitments shape acceptable practices, including redesigning products to increase recycled content, excluding harmful materials, applying geographic sourcing strategies for traceability, embedding supplier codes of conduct into contracts, and extending product lifespans through repair, repurchase and recycling (**Section 5.6.4**). For example, food retailers can reinforce zero-deforestation commitments by excluding products linked to ecosystem conversion or endangered species (Beck-O'Brien & Bringezu, 2021). Similarly, financial institutions also apply exclusion policies to direct capital away from harmful activities (**Section 5.6.4**).

Disclosure of biodiversity strategies, policies, and outcomes can be made internally and externally through annual reports and public statements, covering impacts, dependencies, risks and opportunities (CSRD, 2024; EFRAG, 2022 & TNFD recommendations, 2023). Independent third-party audits enhance credibility and accountability compared to self-reporting (OECD, 2024). However, biodiversity-related reporting remains limited and fragmented. Only 19 per cent of businesses sampled in the United States of America reported on biodiversity (Treepongkaruna, 2024). In megadiverse countries, reporting is highly variable across sectors, with stronger disclosure in materials, energy, and industrials, and weaker in healthcare and information technology. Many statements remain vague and lack quantitative data (Skouloudis et al., 2019). A review of over 2,000 environmental, social and governance reports from 43 countries (2010–2019) found biodiversity reporting has declined since 2015, coinciding with increased focus on climate following the adoption of the Paris Agreement (Bassen et al., 2025). Perceptions can also differ: investors may see detailed disclosure as indicating higher risk, while other stakeholders reward transparency, with quantitative reporting strengthening credibility (Bassen et al., 2025).

Although disclosure frameworks are welcomed by the business community, concerns remain that reporting and quantitative risk assessments alone cannot manage nature-related financial risks.

Complementary approaches are needed, including precautionary policies and qualitative methods to redirect capital away from unsustainable activities (Irvine-Broque & Dempsey, 2023), as well as outcomes-based frameworks and regulation to drive systemic change (Kedward et al., 2020; Mair et al., 2024). Reporting alone rarely delivers substantive outcomes: meaningful change requires integrating stakeholder perspectives and local contexts (Smith et al., 2019), elevating biodiversity to the same level as climate in corporate practice, and stronger external pressure from governments and civil society (Bassen et al., 2025). Improved frameworks should address both impacts and dependencies, supported by leadership, capacity-building, and integration into wider sustainability strategies. Investors also need deeper understanding of biodiversity risks to allocate capital responsibly. While credible reporting can enhance reputation and support global goals, including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, it must be combined with stronger regulatory, policy and outcomes-focused measures to align business practice with biodiversity objectives (Bassen et al., 2025).

5.6.1.3. Transitioning the business, building capacity and ensuring adequate resourcing to implement policies and achieve targets

The successful execution of biodiversity strategies, transition plans and policies require businesses to build up adequate, and often new, internal capacities and allocate sufficient resources, including financial investment and time. Governance reform may also be needed. Yet many businesses face constraints on their ability for effective action on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, such as expertise gaps, siloed responsibilities and resource shortages (**Section 5.3.2**). These challenges mirror broader findings on corporate sustainability transitions, which emphasise the need for organizational learning, leadership commitment and allocation of sufficient resources to enable contributions towards transformative change (Schaltegger et al., 2022; Wicki & Hansen, 2019).

Governance structures play a key role in embedding biodiversity and nature's contributions to people into core decision-making. Despite 66 per cent of Fortune 500 businesses placing sustainability within the Board's remit, only 2 per cent have directors with sufficient biodiversity expertise to provide meaningful oversight (World Benchmarking Alliance, 2023). Strengthening awareness and competencies at senior leadership level, including Board (where relevant) and top management, can ensure leadership is better positioned to understand and manage biodiversity related risks, impacts and opportunities. Board diversity and expertise can be positively associated with the quality of sustainability governance and the consideration of biodiversity in business strategy (Mutua et al., 2025; Nguyen & Kanbach, 2024; Whelan, 2024). Integrating biodiversity into corporate governance frameworks can further ensure it becomes a strategic priority rather than an adjunct consideration (Ludwig & Sassen, 2022). Within organizations, responsibility for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people is often fragmented across departments or confined to specific functions. Creating synergies and points of integration across sustainability, operations, risk management and stakeholder engagement functions is critical to overcoming silos and aligning efforts towards shared biodiversity goals.

Recruiting and training employees with biodiversity-related expertise is also important, as environmental competencies are directly related to businesses' environmental performance (Dzhengiz & Niesten, 2020b). Some businesses, such as Natura, require biodiversity training for all associates, including senior leadership and new employees, to ensure familiarity with the business's Global Code of Conduct (**Annex 5.1**). A business's investment in training and capacity-building also needs to extend to operations and value chain actors, for example to support suppliers' capacity to understand and align practices with corporate commitments and requirements (**Section 5.6.3.3**). Developing the necessary internal capacity that can enable a business to support transformative change requires multiple skill sets and may range from technical biodiversity knowledge and information management to engagement with a wide variety of rights-holders and stakeholders, including IPLCs.

Employee knowledge and initiatives can be harnessed to transform voluntary pro-environmental behaviours into formalised responsibilities that directly support biodiversity outcomes tasks (Boiral et al., 2019). Structured training on biodiversity and internal reporting on implemented, successful actions can also help embed a biodiversity-conscious culture, encouraging employees to take further initiatives action (Boiral et al., 2019; Chaudhary & Klug, 2023; The Confederation of Swedes Enterprises, 2023). Encouraging experiential approaches, such as workplace exposure, field visits, or collaborations with local conservation actors, can further strengthen biodiversity-friendly norms across the workforce (Panwar, 2023).

Resource constraints remain a central barrier for businesses, particularly for small and medium enterprises (Torelli & Balluchi, 2023). The clear link between financial capacity and biodiversity action underscores the need for dedicated investment and financial planning to ensure that strategies can be effectively implemented (Mutua et al., 2025; Nguyen & Kanbach, 2024). Incentive structures are vital, as both monetary and non-monetary rewards can drive behavioural change (Ludwig & Sassen, 2022). Aligning sustainability objectives with financial goals and performance metrics can strengthen employee engagement and sustain organizational transformation (Merriman et al., 2016).

5.6.1.4. Innovating in processes, products and services

Businesses can (re-)design products, services and processes to limit negative impacts, promote positive impacts and sustainably manage dependencies on biodiversity. Circular economy approaches, moving away from linear “take-make-waste” models, are gaining traction in business and policy spheres (Bocken et al., 2022; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, n.d.-b). They emphasise reuse, repair, recycling, sharing of assets, and regeneration of natural ecosystems to minimise resource extraction, landfill and pollution (Bocken & Short, 2016; Konietzko et al., 2020).

One focus is on durability and extending product lifespans. Businesses are redesigning products and packaging to be more durable, easier to repair or produced from recyclable or biodegradable materials such as cornstarch or seaweed (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2021). In electronics, modular devices that allow for repair and upgrades reduce e-waste and reliance on rare earth elements sourced from biodiversity-rich areas (Fairphone, 2024). In the fashion industry, durable and reusable items made with sustainably sourced materials reduce the frequency of resource-intensive production cycles. For example, Patagonia, a retailer specialized in outdoor clothing and equipment has a ‘Worn Wear’ program that encourages consumers to trade or buy its products second-hand, extending product lifecycle (see **Annex 5.1**). Online resale platforms such as Vinted have grown rapidly, now accounting for around 11 per cent of clothing sales in France, with the global second-hand apparel market projected to grow by more than 30 per cent between 2025 and 2029 (Innovation Forum, 2025; Statista, 2025). Vaude also offers rental services as an alternative to ownership of outdoor gear (Vaude, n.d.).

A second area is resource efficiency and recycling. More resource-efficient manufacturing and operational processes can reduce consumption and waste. In agriculture, precision farming technologies such as drones and artificial intelligence-powered monitoring systems optimise water use and reduce pesticide applications, limiting runoff harmful to nearby ecosystems (Getahun et al., 2024). Businesses are also adopting take-back and recycling schemes to keep materials in circulation. Interface, for instance, collects and recycles used carpet tiles (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, n.d.-b), while Pandora has shifted to 100 per cent recycled silver and gold since 2024, sourced from suppliers audited against Responsible Jewellery Council Chain of Custody standards (Pandora Group, n.d.; The Responsible Jewellery Council, 2024). Mining companies have piloted innovative by-product use, such as producing sand from mined ore (Franks et al., 2025), which can reduce pressure on natural ecosystems from sand extraction (UN Environment Programme, 2022). Holcim has been among those trialling ore-sand technologies (**Annex 5.1**), which could scale significantly with enabling conditions such as industry buy-in, policy support, and market acceptance (Franks et al., 2025).

A third priority is sustainable sourcing and alternative materials. The use of alternative materials can significantly reduce biodiversity impacts by eliminating reliance on harmful or unsustainable resources (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, n.d.-a). For example, INVERSA sources leather from harmful non-native species, benefitting ecosystems by removing invasive populations (Harrell, 2025; Inversa, n.d.). Replacing palm oil with sustainably sourced or alternative oils, such as algae-based products, can reduce deforestation and protect habitats of species such as orangutans. Similarly, sourcing certified or recycled materials (e.g., certified timber) reduces the need for raw extraction, though businesses also require working with suppliers to shift practices rather than simply switch suppliers (**Section 5.6.3.3**).

Finally, businesses are exploring models that influence consumption patterns. These circular economy-focused approaches not only make business sense and create innovation opportunities but also help address dependencies on biodiversity. However, limitations have been noted: recycling is not viable for all products, and circularity alone does not resolve continually rising demand for materials driven by resource-intensive lifestyles and population growth (Bocken et al., 2022). Experts highlight the importance of sufficiency – ‘making do with less’ – and prioritising *refuse, reduce and rethink* over recycling (Alexander, 2012; Gossen et al., 2019; Niessen & Bocken, 2021). However, a minority of businesses are already pursuing models explicitly aligned with moderating consumer demand, integrating sufficiency into their offerings, customer engagement, and marketing (Bocken et al., 2022; Niessen & Bocken, 2021). Common features of these businesses include stated purposes aligned with environmental and social objectives, B-Corp certification (see **Section 5.6.1.5**), governance structures that enable autonomy and flexibility, alternative financing (e.g., “slow finance”), and partnerships with NGOs that provide credibility and biodiversity expertise (Bocken et al., 2022).

5.6.1.5. Exploring alternative business models and adopting these, where appropriate

New business models are needed to enable progress on global biodiversity goals (Feger & Mermet, 2020; Hahn & Tampe, 2021). Available options emphasise systems thinking, include a shift towards the restoration, preservation and enhancement of ecosystems, and alignment with organizational, cultural and institutional values. Businesses themselves, in sectors as diverse as agriculture, tourism or the manufacturing and sales of appliances, are attempting to transform their internal business models (i.e., the way in which businesses create, distribute and appropriate value) towards regeneration (Das & Bocken, 2024), though mostly small and medium enterprises. For example, over 9,000 corporations are certified by the non-for-profit network B Lab with the B-Corp certification for demonstrating high social and environmental performance, making a legal commitment to be accountable to all stakeholders, and publicly sharing their performance measured against B Lab's standards (B Lab, n.d.).

One way in which business models can be transformed is shown by alternative ownership enterprises (AOEs). These are ‘firms that significantly shift economic value and decision-making power toward the non-investor stakeholders they impact, such as workers, producers, consumers, community members, or even a non-financial purpose’ (Armeni et al., 2023). They differ from conventional enterprise models mainly by changing economic and governance rights linked with business ownership and who can access this ownership. This can be done in various ways, for example through shifting ownership to non-investor stakeholders (e.g., producers, community members, workers, or consumers, or a non-financial purpose), splitting economic and governance rights into different share classes held by different groups, thereby enabling these to influence governance; through granting decision-making power irrespective of ownership; or choosing legal forms that limit the rights typically granted to outside investors and thereby establishing legal accountability to stakeholders (Armeni et al., 2023).

For example, Tony's Chocolonely, a chocolate manufacturer, has awarded a 'golden share' to an independent legal entity in perpetuity to protect its sustainability-focused mission (Hou Jones et al., 2024) (**Annex 5.1**). Cafédirect, a coffee distributor working with 25 coffee cooperatives in Latin America and Tanzania and reaching over 100,000 small-scale farmers, includes farmers in its governance and business decision-making processes: since 2004 farmers have been represented on the Board of Directors to facilitate small-scale producers' leadership role in the business. The business reinvests 50 per cent of its profits in a farmer-led charity set up by Cafédirect that implements producer support and development programmes (Hou Jones et al., 2024). In 2022, Patagonia, a large outdoor apparel business, shifted to an alternative ownership model, transferring all its voting stock to a trust that safeguards the business's values and all its non-voting stock to a nonprofit entity, with annual profits (after reinvestment) distributed as dividends to support environmental protection (Patagonia, 2021) (**Annex 5.1**).

5.6.2. Operations: actions to achieve outcomes at the site level

Businesses have direct control over their operations where actions can be taken to address their own impacts and dependencies to deliver outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people at the site level. These actions include: (1) conducting environmental and social impact assessments; (2) applying the mitigation hierarchy to address negative impacts on biodiversity; (3) monitoring biodiversity impacts and outcomes for biodiversity; and (4) meaningful stakeholder engagement. Actions at this level must be supported by measures at the corporate level (**Section 5.6.1**), such as establishing environmental and social management systems, and ensuring sufficient capacity, systems, and processes are in place at the operational level to support implementation and compliance with auditing and assurance requirements. While the operationalisation of these corporate systems is not detailed here – such as how staff and contractor capacity is built and performance assessed, or how systems are embedded in day-to-day operations – their importance for effective delivery of outcomes is underscored. Further, **Section 5.7** describes additional actions that can be taken at the level of operations, including collaborative efforts with other businesses and non-business actors. These fall outside the scope of private actions and are instead aimed at influencing wider system conditions and achieving positive outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

5.6.2.1. Conducting environmental and social impact assessments

Environmental and social impact assessments aim to identify and evaluate the occurrence and significance of potential environmental and social impacts of proposed actions (Jay et al., 2007). The environmental and social impact assessment process involves screening to determine the need for assessment, followed by scoping to identify key issues, stakeholders and baseline information. An examination of alternatives is then undertaken to establish options. Finally, impact assessment evaluates the significance of predicted effects and informs the design of mitigation and monitoring measures. Findings are compiled in an environmental and social impact assessment report, which undergoes review and decision-making by a competent authority, leading to project approval (often with conditions) or rejection (IAIA IEA, 1999). Principles have been developed to help ensure environmental and social impact assessments contribute to sustainable development outcomes, aligning decision-making and conditions of approval with broader sustainability goals (Brownlie & Treweek, 2018; IAIA IEA, 1999). Leading practice includes applying an ecosystem perspective to screening and scoping assessments and conducting analyses at ecologically appropriate spatial and temporal scales – for example, by using the 'ecologically appropriate area of analysis' concept (IFC, 2019). Best practice also involves assessing not only nature-related impacts but also dependencies and trade-offs (Morrison-Saunders & Pope, 2013; Sousa et al., 2020), conducting meaningful stakeholder engagement throughout the entire process (Hundloe, 2021) (see **Section 5.6.2.4**), identifying mitigation measures that support local and national biodiversity and ecosystem service

goals (Tallis et al., 2015), and planning for ongoing monitoring, evaluation and adaptation over the life of the project (Morrison-Saunders et al., 2024).

Most environmental and social impact assessments for operations are carried out in accordance with regulatory frameworks (Morgan, 2012). Hundreds of national, regional and international governing bodies now require environmental and social impact assessments (Hundloe, 2021), including in regions with significant infrastructure development expected in future (zu Ermgassen et al., 2019). However, requirements vary widely in scope, rigour and ecological relevance, which can limit their ultimate contribution to broader biodiversity goals (Retief et al., 2016). Issues with environmental and social impact assessments include limited scope of activities, omission of ecologically significant yet under protected components of biodiversity (e.g., common species of least concern) (Simmonds et al., 2020), unclear definition of and thresholds for what constitutes a 'significant' impact (e.g., whether small or cumulative impacts, or impacts on already degraded systems, are captured (Reside et al., 2019; Simmonds & Watson, 2019), inadequate alternatives analysis, inadequate treatment of uncertainty and assumptions (Cardenas & Halman, 2016; Johnston et al., 2015), insufficient clarity about the distinction between mitigation and offset actions (Bigard et al., 2017) (see also **Section 5.6.2.2**), and no clarity on the desired outcome (such as no net loss or net gain) from applying all steps in the mitigation hierarchy.

While environmental and social impact assessments typically assess direct and indirect impacts of a project, including landscape-level effects such as habitat fragmentation (Gontier et al., 2006), there is growing recognition of the need to evaluate cumulative impacts. This includes, for instance, the combined effects of multiple projects across migratory corridors or biodiversity hotspots (Piet et al., 2021; Reside et al., 2019). Although individual projects can include cumulative impact assessments within their environmental and social impact assessment processes, cumulative impact assessments are generally more effective when coordinated through strategic environmental assessments (Declerck et al., 2023). Actions by individual businesses at the operational level can still contribute to or catalyse these broader assessments, although this typically requires collaboration with other stakeholders across the landscape, beyond the site boundary (**Section 5.7**). Some methods and biodiversity metrics are now available to support businesses in conducting or contributing to cumulative impact assessments (Bennun et al., 2024) and some business-led initiatives, such as the Nature Positive Initiative (Nature Positive Initiative, 2025) and the World Business Council on Sustainable Development (WBCSD, 2025), are working to harmonise data inputs and methodological approaches to support consistent reporting and tracking of biodiversity outcomes across sectors and geographies.

In contexts where regulatory frameworks are weak or misaligned with best practice, businesses can voluntarily align their environmental and social impact assessment processes with internationally recognised standards. Two essential elements of such alignment are: (1) ensuring that environmental and social impact assessments capture a broad range of business sectors and activities that cause impacts and biodiversity features that are impacted, including those not explicitly required by law; and (2) designing environmental and social impact assessment processes to inform application of the mitigation hierarchy and deliver specific biodiversity outcomes, such as no net loss or net gain in biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Ultimately, the scope of projects, the features assessed and the quality of baseline data collected, determine the extent to which planning, implementation and long-term performance can be aligned with biodiversity targets.

5.6.2.2. Applying the mitigation hierarchy to achieve no net loss of biodiversity or better

The mitigation hierarchy is a framework that outlines a sequential approach for managing biodiversity and nature-related impacts. It begins with avoiding negative impacts, followed by minimising and reducing impacts through controls, restoring affected biodiversity, and finally, where appropriate and

feasible, offsetting any residual impacts through biodiversity offsets (**Figure 5.4**). The intended outcome of applying this hierarchy is to achieve no net loss, and ideally a net gain in biodiversity (BBOP, 2012; J. Bull et al., 2018). For this to be achieved, any biodiversity gains resulting from mitigation measures should be of the same type and magnitude as those lost to business activities and sustained for at least the duration of project impacts (BBOP, 2018; IFC, 2019; Milner-Gulland et al., 2021).

While the mitigation hierarchy is widely recognised and referenced across many business sectors, particularly those subject to environmental and social impact assessment requirements (IPIECA, 2015; Rainey et al., 2015), its rigorous implementation remains limited and inconsistent. There are several contributing factors at play. First, environmental and social impact assessments and mitigation requirements are only legally required for a subset of business activities (see **Section 5.6.2.1**), meaning many businesses fall outside these regulatory frameworks and only apply the mitigation hierarchy voluntarily, if at all. Second, even where the mitigation hierarchy is required, there is limited guidance on how much of any given action is enough. For example, how much impact avoidance is required before moving on to minimisation. In many risk assessment frameworks, management requirements are often interpreted using the principle of “as low as reasonably practicable”, which is inherently subjective (Kletz, 2005). Because there is no agreed threshold or performance standard for what constitutes sufficient avoidance, minimisation or offsetting, its implementation cannot be enforced or assured in a credible way (Phalan et al., 2018). As a result, very few projects successfully achieve their stated or implied net outcome targets, and the continued global decline in biodiversity suggests that current application of the mitigation hierarchy is falling short (Thomas et al., 2025). Stronger regulatory frameworks with clearer expectations, measurable thresholds, and consequences for non-delivery would help drive more consistent and effective application, particularly by encouraging greater emphasis on impact avoidance as the first and most critical step.

The early stages of the mitigation hierarchy – avoidance and minimisation – are considered the most reliable for achieving positive biodiversity outcomes (Phalan et al., 2018). A broad range of avoidance measures exists, from cancelling or reconfiguring projects entirely to alternative siting, routing and scheduling of operations. Some tools and methods are available to support the identification, prioritisation and measurement of avoidance actions (Cook et al., 2018). However, demonstrating that impacts have been credibly avoided, and justifying that enough avoidance has been achieved, remains a major challenge (J. W. Bull et al., 2022). As mentioned above, businesses would benefit from clarity on a minimum set of biodiversity features that should be avoided (i.e., no-go zones) where societal demand for impact avoidance is clear. Minimisation measures, in contrast, are typically easier to document, as they involve applying physical, operational or abatement controls to reduce the duration, intensity or significance of residual impacts. For example, “shutdown on demand” protocols have been used to reduce bird mortality from collision and trauma in wind energy operations (Marques et al., 2014). However, best practice minimisation is not a one-time effort. It requires continuous review and integration of improved technologies and practices over the life of a project, rather than locking in controls during initial planning phases, which in turn demands ongoing, adaptive environmental impact assessment (IPIECA, 2015). Notably, while documentation of minimisation actions is relatively common, demonstrating the effectiveness of those actions in terms of actual outcomes for biodiversity is far less routine and presents an ongoing gap in both assurance and accountability.

Later stages of the mitigation hierarchy – restoration and offsetting – are typically more expensive, often more uncertain, and pose greater risks to achieving impact mitigation goals, compared to earlier steps such as avoidance and minimisation (IPIECA, 2015). These stages can include a range of actions including remediation, rehabilitation, restoration and offsetting. Remediation refers to actions that address pollution or other environmental hazards to make a site safe for use. Rehabilitation focuses on stabilising and revegetating a disturbed site, often for a different land use (e.g., post-mining

landscapes), whereas restoration aims to return an ecosystem to its pre-disturbance condition or trajectory. Biodiversity offsets are measurable conservation outcomes designed to compensate for residual impacts after all other mitigation measures have been applied, with the goal of achieving no net loss or a net gain in biodiversity (Gann et al., 2019; Poulton & Maron, 2025). While rehabilitation may be feasible in some contexts, particularly in sectors like mining where land disturbance is concentrated, its effectiveness is limited. Despite significant progress in the development of best practice principles (Young et al., 2022) and technical innovations in ecological restoration (Dixon et al.,) rehabilitated areas rarely return to pre-development (baseline) biodiversity conditions within a reasonable and defined timeframe (Campbell et al., 2024). Moreover, outcomes are often shaped by broader, uncontrollable pressures such as climate change, altered fire regimes, and invasive species, which can undermine even well-designed rehabilitation and restoration efforts.

Biodiversity offsetting is the final step in the mitigation hierarchy, reserved to addressing truly residual impacts that remain after all efforts to avoid, minimise and restore have been exhausted. As the riskiest and most uncertain mitigation measure, offsetting should be initiated as early as possible to allow adequate time for monitoring, stakeholder engagement, and adaptive management (BBOP, 2012; IPIECA, 2015). To support transparency and accountability, offset design, including the type and amount of expected biodiversity gains, feasibility assessments, and long-term management plans, should be clearly documented (BBOP, 2012). Effective offsetting measures are accompanied by regular audits, public disclosure of performance, and contingency plans to address shortfalls, as required under standards such as those of the International Finance Corporation (IFC, 2012a). Some operations, such as Ambatovy, use biodiversity management plans to include measures consistent with applying the mitigation hierarchy, with the aim of achieving at least no net loss outcomes, and commitments to restoration (**Annex 5.1**). In principle, offsets should deliver biodiversity gains that are equivalent in type, amount and duration to the biodiversity lost through business activity (Gardner et al., 2013). Offset planning should also address potential trade-offs between biodiversity, nature's contributions to people, and the wellbeing of people affected by offset activities (Griffiths et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2023; Sonter et al., 2020). Although there is substantial knowledge, experience and guidance on offsetting (see **Section 5.6.2.3**), evidence of successful, outcome-based implementation remains limited. (Maron et al., 2025) highlight common pitfalls, including weak governance, poor enforcement, and insufficient long-term commitment.

For businesses, early and sustained planning to achieve no net loss or net gain outcomes at the level of operations is critical. Success depends on establishing strong governance arrangements, engaging relevant rights- and stakeholders from the outset, ensuring public disclosure of intended and actual outcomes, and applying an adaptive management approach. Notably, while these practices are essential to biodiversity offsetting, they are also critical for other mitigation measures yet are often underperformed or overlooked. Strengthening these foundational elements could improve the effectiveness and credibility of mitigation actions across the entire mitigation hierarchy (Ghijselinck et al., 2026).

Figure 5.4. The mitigation hierarchy, including actions to avoid, minimise, restore and offset. Note that conservation outcomes that contribute to renewing and regenerating biodiversity over and above a business' mitigation measures aimed at achieving no net loss outcomes would contribute to reversing biodiversity losses. Adapted from Maron et al., (2025).

5.6.2.3. Measuring and monitoring biodiversity impacts and outcomes of actions

Many methods are available to support businesses in measuring biodiversity at the site level (see **Chapter 4**), including specific approaches tailored to environmental and social impact assessments and application of the mitigation hierarchy (Burgess et al., 2024). For example, critical habitat assessments are widely used in infrastructure projects to identify species and ecosystems requiring special assessment and mitigation (IFC, 2019) while similar approaches – such as the High Conservation Value (HCV) framework – are used in agriculture and forestry (High Conservation Value (HCV) Network, n.d.). Guidance also exists for using biodiversity metrics to estimate and account for losses and gains over time (Mayfield et al., 2022; SEEA, n.d.). Numerous tools also exist to support the design and implementation of mitigation projects. These include tools for aligning site-level actions with broader biodiversity targets (e.g., jurisdictional goals (Simmonds et al., 2020)), selecting suitable delivery mechanisms (e.g., biodiversity credit systems; see **Box 5.4**), ensuring robust safeguards (Narain et al., 2022), and designing interventions to maximise additional benefits to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (Bull et al., 2018; Tallis et al., 2015). Policy- and sector-specific tools are also available to support tracking progress toward no net loss targets throughout the project life cycle (Gibbons et al., 2016).

A growing body of research has focused on evaluating the effectiveness of environmental and social impact assessments and mitigation measures in achieving biodiversity outcomes. Effective evaluation requires clearly stated net outcome targets, appropriate metrics, and a counterfactual comparison – i.e., measuring biodiversity changes attributable to the project against what would have occurred in its absence (Maron et al., 2018). In some cases, businesses are required to conduct and publish this information. For example, the International Finance Corporation and several other lenders require regular audits on Biodiversity Action Plan implementation from clients receiving project financing. For example, Compagnie des Bauxites de Guinée (CBG) has developed biodiversity action plans as part of its mining operations in Guinea (**Annex 5.1**). However, such reporting often focuses on barriers to action rather than outcomes, and the data made public is frequently insufficient for third-party evaluation. For instance, while one-third of biodiversity offset projects reported success, most used inadequate metrics or evaluation methods to support their no net loss claims (zu Ermgassen et

al., 2019). This is beginning to shift. Some frameworks now require the publication of essential project information, such as location, size and methodologies used, which would enable independent evaluation (GRI, 2024). To date, most evaluations highlight the underperformance of biodiversity offsetting projects, although isolated cases suggest that well-designed mitigation measures can achieve no net loss (Devenish et al., 2022). However, a major gap remains there are currently no tools or frameworks to assess whether the cumulative outcomes of individual project-level mitigation actions are sufficiently large or strategic to support claims that a business is contributing meaningfully to global biodiversity goals.

Box 5.4. Use and misuse of biodiversity credits in addressing business impacts on biodiversity

While businesses can take direct actions to manage their biodiversity-related impacts, market-based mechanisms, such as the purchase of biodiversity credits, have also been proposed. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework highlights biodiversity credits as one of several innovative finance mechanisms to mobilise private sector investment in biodiversity recovery (CBD, 2022). A biodiversity credit is defined as “a certificate that represents a measured and evidence-based unit of positive biodiversity outcome that is durable and additional to what would have otherwise occurred” (Biodiversity Credit Alliance, 2024). Several initiatives, including the International Advisory Panel on Biodiversity Credits, the Biodiversity Credit Alliance, and the World Economic Forum Biodiversity Credits Initiative, are working to explore the development, scaling, and appropriate use cases for such credits.

However, significant challenges remain. There is currently no standardised methodology for assessing, verifying, or reporting biodiversity outcomes, nor a consensus on how to define or trade units of biodiversity gain or loss. The creation of a high-integrity supply of credits at sufficient scale, and demand from buyers with credible biodiversity claims, is still in early stages. The relationship between biodiversity credits and biodiversity offsets remains contested. A key concern is whether credits could be misused as a substitute for real, site-level mitigation. Many stakeholders advocate for a clear distinction between credits used for voluntary biodiversity contributions and units used to compensate for biodiversity losses elsewhere (Pollination & Taskforce on Nature Markets, 2023; Wunder et al., 2024). Ideally, credits should only be purchased after a business has demonstrated it has achieved no net loss across its operations and value chains (Maron et al., 2023).

Progress has been made through the International Panel on Biodiversity Credits (IAPB), which developed a Framework for High Integrity Biodiversity Credit Markets. This framework builds on the Biodiversity Credit Alliance definition, outlines three use cases for biodiversity credits, proposes 21 high-level principles for credit quality, and does not endorse international offsetting, instead emphasising the need for local-to-local, like-for-like compensation. As the concept and implementation of biodiversity credit markets continue to evolve, it will be critical to draw from lessons learned in other conservation incentive schemes (Shrikanth et al., 2025; Swinfield et al., 2024; Wunder et al., 2024), to ensure biodiversity credits complement, rather than undermine, core principles of the mitigation hierarchy.

5.6.2.4. Identifying and meaningfully engaging with stakeholders

Effective engagement with local communities, rights- and stakeholders is essential to building trust, understanding and assessing site-specific impacts and their significance, and prioritising and achieving mitigation actions to deliver meaningful and lasting biodiversity outcomes (TNFD, 2023a).

When operations require acquisition or modification of land or resource rights, the undertaking of environmental and social impact assessments and other related studies is key to understand the context and uphold Indigenous rights, and other applicable rights of local communities related to property, governance, culture, livelihoods and food security. These studies entail assessing social baselines, land tenure and land use to identify formal or customary rights and potential impacts. Where rights or livelihoods may be affected, business engagement with rightsholders and stakeholders is necessary to obtain free, prior and informed consent in culturally appropriate ways, clarifying access rights, compensation and benefit-sharing. If free, prior and informed consent is not secured, best practice is for the business not to pursue its plans. These requirements reflect

international law and standards, such as the Accountability Framework, Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil, International Finance Corporation's Performance Standards, High Conservation Value and High Carbon Stock Approaches (Accountability Framework initiative (AFi), 2019; Brown et al., 2013; Hoyle et al., 2018; IFC, 2012b; Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO), 2022). Using study insights, businesses can define, implement, monitor and verify measures to protect Indigenous rights, and other applicable rights of local communities, with grievance mechanisms in place to address risks and impacts.

Broader engagement supports transparent and accountable decision-making, helps balance diverse expectations and can increase the efficiency and legitimacy of mitigation actions (IFC, 2007). This is particularly true when business operations contribute to cumulative impacts, as engagement enables coordination with other land users and institutions to support landscape-scale planning and mitigation (Fauna and Flora International, 2021). Collaborative efforts can improve the information base for impact assessments and help broker partnerships that align conservation and development goals (see Section 5.7.3).

5.6.3. Value chain: actions to influence suppliers and customers

Tracing materials and products is a crucial step to measuring and addressing biodiversity impacts that occur upstream (through suppliers) and downstream (through clients and consumers) of a business's operations. Value chains – and the most suitable actions to address their biodiversity loss and secure their affected nature's contributions to people – differ from business to business and from sector to sector. Different businesses can also occupy different positions within the same value chain (i.e., be suppliers for some businesses and clients for others), meaning that actions taken by a company upstream to address downstream impacts will have implications for the actions required by downstream businesses. **Figure 5.5** provides an example, illustrating different parts and activities in a typical value chain for an agricultural commodity.

Figure 5.5. Typical agricultural commodity value chain (e.g., olives, olive oil) with six interconnected stages from production to end-use. It includes: 1) provision of essential agricultural inputs (e.g., seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and machinery for cultivation); 2) production, involving farmers cultivating olive trees; 3) post-harvest

aggregation and storage of olives in facilities to maintain quality before processing; 4) processing and manufacturing of products (e.g., olives, olive oil, ingredients for food products); 5) distribution and retail of processed products for consumers; and 6) the consumption by end-users, including consumers and industries. Each stage has distinct environmental impacts and dependencies, particularly concerning land use, biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. The diagram illustrates agricultural production as the primary land-use stage with other stages shown as upstream and downstream activities (adapted from WBCSD, 2023b).

Value-chain actions are shaped by commitments made at the corporate level, which are embedded in associated policies and strategies. These commitments cascade into procurement practices and into protocols for product and service use and disposal (see **Section 5.6.1**). In doing so, they influence what businesses consider acceptable practice in areas such as product design and marketing and affect multiple actors both upstream and downstream. Examples include redesigning products to increase recycled content, substituting inputs to exclude environmentally harmful materials, and applying geographic sourcing strategies to improve traceability. They may involve integrating due diligence and supplier codes of conduct into contractual negotiations or extending product lifespan through post-sale services such as repair, repurchase or the collection of end-of-life goods for recycling and remanufacturing. Other instruments, beyond direct responses to corporate biodiversity actions, also drive supply chain actions. For example, internal codes of conduct and discretionary investments in supplier support aim to improve conditions on site and encourage gradual supplier compliance, but do not exclude providers from entering the value chain (Zadek, 2007). Third-party certifications (e.g., Fair Trade, Rainforest Alliance) and bans or moratoria (Gibbs et al., 2015) are also designed to ensure that only compliant suppliers participate in value chains (Rueda et al., 2017).

Regardless of the driver, implementation requires businesses to assign responsibility within teams, allocate resources, and develop robust systems to assess supplier and customer impacts and dependencies, verify compliance, and report progress (see **Section 5.6.1**). Collaborative initiatives involving multiple businesses and non-governmental organizations can further scale sustainable practices across value chains and sectors, promoting system-level change (Pagell & Wu, 2009) (**Section 5.7**). Businesses may also disclose value chain actions to their clients and consumers through marketing campaigns or other communication tools; however, decisions to do so relate to assessments of reputational risks and brand equity (Mayer & Gereffi, 2010; Rueda et al., 2017).

Biodiversity loss has received limited attention in the supply chain management literature (Quarshie et al., 2016; Salmi et al., 2023). Addressing biodiversity loss beyond tier one suppliers remains difficult due to limited traceability, greater geographical separation, and reduced influence over drivers of biodiversity loss at these broader scales (Marttinen & Kähkönen, 2022; Villena & Gioia, 2018). Several major disclosure frameworks and standards now provide guidance to businesses to inform value chain actions to address these barriers. They include the Science Based Targets Network (SBTN, n.d.-a); the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), n.d.) and the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, n.d.), alongside sector-specific principles and operational guidance, such as those published by the Accountability Framework Initiative (Accountability Framework Initiative, n.d.-a) for agriculture and forestry supply chains. Key business actions identified in such guidance, can be grouped into cooperative and coercive practices (Hoejmose et al., 2014) and are organised below as: (1) mapping the value chain to prioritise and inform action; (2) using supplier management systems to set expectations and address non-compliance; (3) building relationships and partnerships with suppliers to build capacity and drive performance; and (4) engaging with downstream customers, clients and consumers, including educational programmes.

5.6.3.1. Mapping value chain actors and ensuring traceability to prioritise and inform action

Traceability means being able to follow a product or material through various value chain stages from production, processing and manufacturing to distribution. It allows product volumes to be linked with the specific operations of suppliers and customers, along with information on their performance. Value chain mapping complements this by identifying the actors within a business's value chain(s) and the relationships between them (Accountability Framework initiative, 2019). Businesses invest in traceability to identify, understand and address social and biodiversity-related impacts and risks in their value chain, to improve transparency and ensure compliance with environmental regulations, human rights standards and global goals for biodiversity conservation, sustainable use and equitable benefit sharing. Businesses with global or complex upstream value chains are more likely to engage in actions to improve traceability (Salmi et al., 2023). The Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) requires traceability systems to demonstrate that palm oil production avoids areas of high conservation value and adheres to no-deforestation commitments (Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO), n.d.). Similarly, seafood traceability systems such as those certified by the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) aim to ensure sustainable fisheries, prevent overfishing and safeguard marine biodiversity (Marine Stewardship Council, n.d.).

Gathering sufficient information for adequate traceability is essential for supply chain management but can be particularly challenging for businesses (see also **Chapter 4**). Both value chain mapping and traceability can be applied at different levels of detail and scope. For example, assessments can be undertaken at the product level to influence a wide range of actors, or they can focus on specific components of a value chain where material impacts and dependencies are most significant, with the aim of influencing key actors in priority geographies. Mapping often begins with direct (first tier) suppliers and can expand to include second and third tier suppliers, to build a progressively more comprehensive picture of the chain. Criteria such as supplier size and span, impact and dependence of a product on biodiversity, and identification of high biodiversity risk sourcing areas can further help prioritise efforts. Products and materials may be traced back to suppliers, such as refiners, traders, cooperatives, groups of farmers, or individual producers, and in some cases to specific locations at the country, province, municipal or site level.

Several approaches and levels of knowledge can be obtained and used to inform and prioritise value chain actions (Accountability Framework Initiative, n.d.-b). These include: 1) full traceability, where materials can be traced back to the production or processing unit of origin, enabling direct assessment of risks, impacts and compliance; 2) the use of supplier control mechanisms that meet relevant criteria and provide reliable, sufficient information; 3) reliance on credible assurance mechanisms, such as third-party verification under voluntary sustainability schemes; and 4) under adequate circumstances, traceability to low-risk landscapes or jurisdictions that can demonstrate acceptable performance. For example, Vietnamese chocolate manufacturer Marou, a small-to-medium size enterprise, ensures full traceability by purchasing beans directly from producers in eight regions local to its factory (Marou, n.d.) (**Annex 5.1**).

Although full traceability is not always necessary, nor made a priority by businesses (Salmi et al., 2023), some have achieved it in one or more of their value chains through dedicated effort. Technological advances, including improved data quality (e.g., remote sensing products) and digital assessment tools (e.g., mobile applications for data recording) have supported this, including the use of blockchain technology (Agrawal et al., 2021). For example, Dutch chocolate manufacturer Tony's Chocolonely works with nine farmer cooperatives and supports 17,740 smallholder farmers in Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire. The company uses a digital tracking system to identify the percentage of cocoa supplied by each farmer in every shipment received, with all farms GPS-mapped and data owned and used by local cooperatives (Hou Jones et al., 2024; Tony's, 2023).

Once value chains have been mapped, including upstream and downstream activities and materials, businesses can use this information to inform actions based on priority procurement categories and their impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Several methods are available to support this process. For example, the Science Based Targets Network materiality tool and ENCORE are often used to identify categories at risk, while life cycle assessment has been used to provide measures of biodiversity impacts (see **Chapter 4**). For some businesses, tools have proven useful, provided uncertainties are recognised and addressed (Bromwich et al., 2025). However, there are many reasons why these approaches often break down when applied to prioritising actions across certain value chains, sectors, businesses and financial institutions. For instance, tools designed to identify priority procurement categories may not comprehensively capture all materials within a business's supply chain, rarely integrate with existing supplier management systems, and include nature-related materiality in ways that do not align with internal risk management systems and processes. Addressing these limitations will require a more comprehensive, regionalised and forward-looking understanding of business activities, which are explicitly linked to procurement categories and their biodiversity impacts and dependencies.

5.6.3.2. Using supplier management systems to set expectations, monitoring performance and addressing non-compliance

To manage impacts and dependencies, businesses use supplier management systems applied company-wide or to specific commodity value chains (Cousins et al., 2019; Vachon & Klassen, 2006). Key features of these systems include clear sourcing and procurement policies to operationalise corporate commitments to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, robust risk assessment strategies, procedures for supplier selection and compliance, protocols for managing non-compliance, and mechanisms for supplier engagement and capacity-building. Equally important are grievance procedures, supplier reporting requirements, and senior management responsibility for implementing the system and ensuring commitments are met (Accountability Framework initiative, 2019). Stricter approaches to supply chain management are often driven by downstream customer demands (Højmosé et al., 2014).

Communicating policy commitments, sourcing requirements and expectations to suppliers across the value chain is essential, ideally with time-bound targets and milestones. For example, some buyers require beef or soy suppliers in Brazil's Amazon and Cerrado to adopt zero-deforestation policies aligned with their corporate commitments and to demonstrate progress by a set date (BNP Paribas, 2021). Requirements for biodiversity protection and respect for Indigenous rights, and other applicable rights of local communities can be embedded in contractual agreements, supplier codes of conduct and engagement plans. Incentives, such as long-term agreements, price premiums or preferential shelf space can further encourage supplier performance (Marshall et al., 2015). Supplier assessment and due diligence support monitoring and verification, through tools such as questionnaires, performance tracking, audits and certification (Marshall et al., 2015; Salmi et al., 2023; Sancha et al., 2019; Vachon & Klassen, 2006). Supplier assessment and due diligence support monitoring and verification, through tools such as questionnaires, performance tracking, audits and certification (Marshall et al., 2015; Salmi et al., 2023; Sancha et al., 2019; Vachon & Klassen, 2006).

Businesses use a variety of risk assessments to identify non-compliance with requirements and commitments. Good practice involves addressing the correct scope and level of disaggregation (relating to commodity, geography and commitment), using appropriate metrics and credible methodologies, qualified risk assessors and independent review (e.g., when sourcing from regions not regarded as low risk). Initial screening through a coarse-grained approach looking across all regions and value chains will highlight where more detailed assessment is necessary, for example, to focus on certain parts of a value chain, certain geographies or suppliers (Accountability Framework initiative, 2019). Transparency is increasingly promoted by publishing supplier lists online,

sometimes with downloadable datasets or maps, or disclosing through platforms such as the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP, n.d.; Salmi et al., 2023).

To address non-compliance, businesses can retain or suspend suppliers, often coupling engagement with corrective support. In some cases, suppliers are excluded altogether, at least until they can demonstrate changes to fulfil requirements. The most suitable course of action depends on the severity of the non-compliance (i.e., its scale, intensity and persistence), the supplier's control over or responsibility for the non-compliance and their commitment and capability (e.g., their commitments, track record). Engagement by the business with its suppliers is essential in all cases to help rectify non-compliance, although it may sometimes be necessary to move away from certain suppliers in preference of those with stronger practices. When sourcing from smallholders or suppliers with limited capacity, alternative and more contextualised approaches to assessing and managing non-compliance are usually needed (see **Section 5.6.3.3**) (Accountability Framework Initiative, 2019).

While businesses can control their own operations and influence the actions of their direct suppliers (Sancha et al., 2019), they face challenges to identify and address risks and impacts related to suppliers that are more than one tier removed from their own operations (Villena & Gioia, 2018). A common approach is to evaluate the adequacy of tier one suppliers' supplier management systems, or their adoption of voluntary sustainability standards (see **Box 5.5**). These may in turn assess performance at the supply chain level or evaluate the systems of their own direct suppliers, creating a cascading oversight process until risks can be properly addressed (Accountability Framework initiative, 2019).

Box 5.5. Voluntary sustainability standards

Voluntary Sustainability Standards are private standards that require products to meet defined economic, social and environmental metrics. These requirements may cover product quality or attributes, production and processing methods, and even transportation. Typically designed and promoted by non-governmental organizations or private businesses, they are adopted by actors across value chains, with labelling used to signal compliance (UNCTAD, 2025).

Businesses can use voluntary sustainability standards to assess and manage biodiversity-related risks in their supply chains, enhance transparency, and demonstrate progress toward sustainability goals to investors and customers. A wide variety of schemes exist. Some are biodiversity-specific and cross-sectoral, such as the French Association for Standardization's Standard NF X32-001 to help organizations structure their approach to biodiversity (AFNOR Editions, 2021) and an ISO standard on Biodiversity Net Gain is currently under development. Others are commodity- and sector-specific, particularly for high-risk commodities such as aluminium, pulp and paper, palm oil, soy, coffee and beef. The scope, quality of requirements, governance and implementation vary considerably. To support credibility and best practice, the International Social & Environmental Accreditation & Labelling Alliance (ISEAL, 2021) provides a widely recognised framework.

Despite rapid growth in recent decades, the scale of voluntary sustainability standards remains limited. Tayleur et al. (2017) found that the certified area across twelve major crop standards increased by 11 per cent annually between 2000 and 2012 but still covered only 1.1 per cent of global cropland (Tayleur et al., 2017). O'Brien et al. (2024) found less than 15 per cent of forests and less than 15 per cent of global marine catch to be certified. Research on effectiveness and efficiency shows mixed results. Documented limitations include weak assurance and enforcement systems, failure to fully prohibit deforestation and forest degradation (despite zero-deforestation goals), limited measurable impact on biodiversity outcomes, governance and credibility issues linked to power imbalances between businesses and smaller non-governmental organizations, high certification costs, conflicts of interest, and risks of greenwashing (BankTrack, 2020; Cosimo et al., 2024; Englund & Berndes, 2015; Moog et al., 2015; O'Brien et al., 2024).

Nonetheless, many sources also highlight the positive role of credible standards in improving business biodiversity performance, particularly when integrated into robust due diligence systems and used as complementary tools (Beck-O'Brien & Bringezu, 2021).

5.6.3.3. Building relationships, partnerships and capacity to drive improved performance

Effective value chain management requires businesses to go beyond procurement requirements, data collection and due diligence, and to work closely with suppliers to transition their activities. These practices have been found to be more effective in driving action on biodiversity loss than actions focused only on setting internal policies and requirements for suppliers (Marshall et al., 2015; Meqdadi et al., 2020; Salmi et al., 2023) and represent important pathways for enabling supply chains to be a lever of transformative change (Wieland, 2021). This is important for businesses with significant influence and resources, and equally critical for smaller businesses, smallholder producers and businesses operated by IPLCs, who may lack the institutional capacity and resources to implement biodiversity actions and improve outcomes (Accountability Framework Initiative, 2019).

Collaboration can foster trust, empower suppliers as change agents and build readiness to address biodiversity impacts. It also strengthens long-term relationships, improves product quality and increases buy-in for corporate action. Common practices include supplier training (Sancha et al., 2019) and capacity-building, for example, improving management practices, adopting simplified due diligence processes (Lumme et al., 2023) or aligning with certification processes. Businesses may also use local workforce as relationship managers or extension services to provide ongoing technical support. Mountain Hazelnuts, for instance, uses this approach in Bhutan to maintain regular contact with smallholder producers (Hou Jones et al., 2024). Other businesses may use direct contact, such as monthly visits and regular phone calls, with suppliers (Mourou et al., 2021).

Such engagement relies on sustained business investment in long-term relationships with suppliers and local communities (Salmi et al., 2023). Integrating communities into value creation activities such as sourcing, production and distribution has been a success factor in sustainable value chain management. Natura, a multinational cosmetics company, sources babassu oil from *quebradeiras de coco do babaçu* (Babassu nut-breaking women) applying traditional knowledge within a biodiversity-based business (**Annex 5.1**). Long-term purchasing agreements, minimum quantity commitments, price premiums, and investments in training, education and infrastructure have strengthened relationships between the company and community suppliers (Puppim de Oliveira et al., 2022).

Businesses can also provide direct support by promoting supplier organizations, for example through cooperatives, offering access to technology or contributing necessary resources, such as seedlings, equipment or financial assistance. For example, Cafédirect partners with 25 cooperatives in Tanzania and Latin America, reaching more than 100,000 farmers, and reinvests half its profits into Producers Direct – an independent, farmer-led charity. Producers Direct provides tailored development programs, financial services, training, producer networks and mobile apps that help farmers analyse crop data, monitor productivity, and even predict yields using artificial intelligence (Hou Jones et al., 2024). Marou, for example, provides interest-free loans and harvest advances, as well as equipment, to support its producer network (Mourou et al., 2021) (**Annex 5.1**).

Processes for joint problem-solving and co-developing solutions are equally important, as they enable knowledge exchange and continuous improvement (S. Lee & Klassen, 2008). Sectoral initiatives can help transfer knowledge from larger to smaller businesses and build supplier capacity. Chain of custody initiatives, for example, provide a network for such engagement and knowledge transfer (**Box 5.6**). In collaborative approaches, businesses often partner with non-governmental organizations or government agencies (Jia et al., 2018). Partnerships between businesses and non-governmental organizations that engage directly with suppliers in sourcing countries can be effective in overcoming barriers to sustainability – by co-developing standards with suppliers and supporting them in meeting these requirements (see **Section 5.7**).

Box 5.6. Chain of custody initiatives to share knowledge and align practices: the case of the Aluminium Stewardship Initiative

The Aluminium Stewardship Initiative's chain of custody approach ensures the responsible production and sourcing of aluminium throughout the value chain by linking sustainability and ethical standards from raw material extraction to the final product. Aluminium Stewardship Initiative's Chain of Custody Standard enables certified entities to demonstrate that their aluminium has been sourced, processed and manufactured in a way that meets rigorous environmental, social and governance criteria, such as biodiversity conservation, reducing carbon emissions, and protecting Indigenous Peoples rights. The chain of custody approach requires transparent documentation and traceability of certified aluminium, ensuring that materials meeting Aluminium Stewardship Initiative standards can be identified and tracked across every stage of production. This system supports industries like construction, packaging, and automotive in delivering responsibly sourced aluminium to customers while promoting sustainability across the value chain (ASI-Aluminium Stewardship Initiative, 2023).

5.6.3.4. Engaging with, educating and incentivising action by customers, clients and consumers

Marketing and other consumer-facing strategies provide businesses with direct opportunities to influence consumer behaviour in support of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. These include educating customers, using clear product labelling, incentivising behaviour change and supporting post-sale engagement. In some cases, businesses are required or incentivised through environmental policy to adopt extended producer responsibility, which makes them financially or physically responsible for the end-of-life management of their products. Extended producer responsibility shifts costs and burdens from governments and taxpayers to producers and brands, with the aim of encouraging the design of more sustainable products that are easier to reuse, repair or recycle. However, such initiatives will remain limited if underlying business models continue to depend on unsustainable patterns of consumption (Purvis et al., 2019; Whiteman et al., 2013) and are often dependent on and driven by institutional pressures (Hoejmose et al., 2014), see also **Section 5.6.1**.

Clear and credible sustainability labels and certifications can indicate that biodiversity considerations have been integrated into sourcing and production processes, enabling consumers to identify products with lower impact (Testa et al., 2015). Dutch organic food company Eosta, for example, uses QR or three-digit codes to provide transparency on growers and environmental footprints (Eosta, 2018, 2025). Certification schemes such as those offered by the Forest Stewardship Council, Marine Stewardship Council and Rainforest Alliance are widely used and signal sustainability to consumers. However, the effectiveness of labels is often limited by information overload, low consumer awareness, scepticism about label credibility, and the financial and administrative burdens of certification (Taufique et al., 2017; Tregidga et al., 2014). Many consumers also misunderstand or mistrust labels, especially when multiple certifications compete in the same market (Thøgersen et al., 2010).

Businesses can shape public understanding of biodiversity and the impact of their products through educational initiatives that aim for long-term shifts in attitudes and behaviours. Such efforts need to ensure coherence between sustainability claims and actual practices to avoid accusations of greenwashing (Delmas & Burbano, 2011) and communication strategies are most effective when there is a transparent and tangible link between the product and its biodiversity impacts (Du et al., 2010). Tools such as the Union for Ethical BioTrade's Biodiversity Barometer help businesses better understand consumer expectations around biodiversity and tailor their corporate strategies and engagement accordingly (Union for Ethical BioTrade (UEBT), 2024).

Some businesses incentivise customers to adopt more sustainable behaviours by offering discounts for returned products, loyalty points for biodiversity-friendly purchases or rewards for recycling

packaging. Post-purchase engagement can help address impacts at the end-of-life stage of products, an area often overlooked in traditional marketing and sustainability frameworks (Peattie & Crane, 2005). Actions include providing guidance and infrastructure for recycling, take-back schemes and repair services to reduce downstream impacts. Several outdoor brands, for example, offer care and repair kits and instructions to extend product life, and provide platforms for second-hand gear (VAUDE, 2025). Patagonia's Worn Wear programme, for instance, rewards customers who return or repair garments, promoting reuse and reducing demand for resource-intensive new production (Armstrong et al., 2015; Patagonia, 2025) (**Annex 5.1**). Similarly, many coffee businesses provide collection and recycling points for used capsules (Nestlé Nespresso S.A., 2024). Incentive-based strategies have been shown to increase consumer engagement, though their effectiveness depends on aligning rewards with meaningful biodiversity outcomes (K. White et al., 2019).

While these consumer-facing strategies can support biodiversity goals, they often sit uneasily within traditional business models. Many businesses depend on volume-based sales growth, which conflicts with encouraging reduced consumption or promoting longer-lasting products (Bocken et al., 2014). Encouraging consumers to buy less, repair more, or extend product life can challenge profitability and cause internal tensions between marketing, sustainability and finance teams (Hahn et al., 2015). Biodiversity's complexity further complicates integration and communication compared to more easily quantified issues like carbon (Addison et al., 2019; IPBES, 2019b). These tensions highlight the need for systemic shifts in how businesses conceptualise value – placing biodiversity, social and ecological wellbeing, at the centre of corporate governance (**Section 5.6.1**).

5.6.4. Additional private actions for financial institutions

Almost \$7.3 trillion (from both public and private sources) is invested annually in activities that have a direct negative impact on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (UNEP, 2026). Addressing biodiversity loss requires not only halting these harmful financial flows but actively redirecting them toward initiatives that enhance biodiversity. Financial institutions are key actors in supporting transformative change. They influence biodiversity outcomes primarily through the businesses they finance or invest in, with the degree of influence varying by institution type. Investors, due to their equity ownership, also hold significant leverage to engage with businesses on biodiversity, with influence generally increasing in proportion to the size of their stake. Lenders, in turn, exert influence mainly through the terms of their financing, which may include exclusion policies targeting certain activities, businesses or sectors, biodiversity mitigation measures tied to financing, and capital allocation decisions.

Nature-related actions by financial institutions fall into two categories: “greening finance” and “financing green” (World Bank, 2022a). *Greening finance* redirects financial flows away from activities that have negative impacts on biodiversity, minimizing harm and addressing drivers of loss. *Financing green* channels capital toward initiatives that conserve, restore and sustainably use biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Both approaches are necessary to catalyse transformative change and involve actions taken by financial institutions (lenders, investors and insurers) at the corporate and portfolio levels of decision-making. This section (**5.6.4**) highlights actions that are additional to and complement the actions listed earlier (**5.6.1-3**) for all businesses, including financial institutions.

5.6.5. Greening finance

5.6.5.1. Setting corporate level requirements for clients to take private action

Financial institutions providing project finance (loans or equity investment meant for a specific project (OECD, 2014) to clients with operations, such as those within extractive, infrastructure,

energy or livestock sectors, often require them to carry out biodiversity impact assessments of the operations and to apply the mitigation hierarchy. Decisions to set client requirements and integrate them in the financial institution's environmental and social safeguard system, are made at the corporate level. Pioneered by development banks, environmental and social safeguards are now also widely applied by private commercial banks. For example, the International Finance Corporation's Performance Standards, including Performance Standard 6: Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources (OECD, 2014) are used by over 130 mostly private financial institutions that have signed up to the Equator Principles (Equator Principles Association, 2024; Narain et al., 2022). Biodiversity requirements embedded within the safeguards involve preliminary risk screening to identify biodiversity affected by a proposed project, followed by a detailed environmental and social impact assessment to identify direct, indirect and cumulative impacts of the operations. The requirements to address these impacts are usually structured around the mitigation hierarchy (see actions in **Section 5.6.2**), applied to avoid and minimise impacts to the greatest extent possible, restore damaged biodiversity and offset residual impacts, often with the explicit goal of achieving at least 'no net loss' of biodiversity (IFC, 2012a).

To detect and address biodiversity impacts within their clients' value chains, financial institutions can require clients to implement traceability measures. Once it is known where in the value chain the impacts lie, clients can be required to engage with high biodiversity-footprint suppliers (to help them avoid or otherwise address any impacts) or to shift away from such suppliers entirely (see actions in **Section 5.6.3**). For example, Barclays' Forestry and Agricultural Commodities Statement, which came into effect on 1 July 2023 prohibits clients from sourcing beef produced or processed on areas in the Amazon cleared or converted after 2008. Clients that source from high-deforestation-risk countries in South America are required to achieve full traceability and deforestation-free status for their value chains by December 2025 (UNEPFI, 2023).

5.6.5.2. Assessing portfolio-level biodiversity impacts and dependencies

To inform a financial institution's actions in redirecting financial flows away from high-biodiversity-impact sectors, the biodiversity 'footprint' (see **Section 4.4.1, Chapter 4**) of its lending and investment activities can be estimated. Tools drawing from environmental-economic models and life-cycle approaches (**Table 4.2, Chapter 4**) have been developed to support these portfolio-level footprinting efforts.

Despite these advances, the availability of tools remains limited, and there are few well-documented examples of their application at the portfolio level. As a result, financial institutions continue to face challenges in reliably quantifying biodiversity impacts and dependencies across their investments, though these tools provide a foundation for identifying high-impact sectors, monitoring changes over time, and aligning portfolios with emerging frameworks such as the Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials (PBAF), Science-Based Targets for Nature (SBTN), and the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). In practice, particularly for large portfolios, footprint estimates are often derived from modelled or self-reported client data rather than direct measurements of on-the-ground change (see **Chapter 4**).

5.6.5.3. Managing biodiversity risk and impacts across portfolio/s through stewardship

Identifying biodiversity-related risk and impact hotspots (sectors, businesses or projects) within a financial institution's portfolio/s then enables the deployment of various mitigation actions. These fall into two broad categories: 1) stewardship and 2) divestment and exclusion. These actions can take different forms for different types of financial institutions, i.e., investors and lenders. For investors, stewardship involves using their influence over current or prospective investee businesses to drive improvements in addressing environmental, social, and governance issues, including biodiversity.

This influence is typically exercised through direct engagement with investees and through participation in shareholder voting processes.

A key stewardship tool available to investors is engagement, which involves establishing a dialogue with investee businesses on biodiversity-related matters. This may include articulating biodiversity policies, urging clients to disclose biodiversity related risks, and pressing for a shift in business practices. Engagement is commonly conducted through meetings, calls, written correspondence or emails. For example, Aviva, a British multinational insurance company, sends an annual letter each January to the chairs of companies in which it invests – and some other companies in which it does not invest – to outline its stewardship priorities. In 2022, Aviva contacted over 1,600 global companies, urging them to develop biodiversity action plans that assess impacts and dependencies, establish interim and comprehensive targets aligned with the Science-Based Targets for Nature (SBTN) and publicly report on their progress (Aviva, 2021).

Investors may undertake such efforts individually or as part of a collaborative initiative – whether through informal alliances or formal investor networks – thereby increasing their influence, legitimacy, and operational efficiency. In some cases, investors may also delegate engagement responsibilities to specialized service providers (Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), 2021). Lenders (banks) can also engage with their clients (borrowers) on biodiversity-related issues. This may involve general awareness initiatives, dialogue on clients' transition plans, and provision of biodiversity-focused financial products. Such engagement also provides banks with a platform to convey their responsible financing policies and to prompt clients to disclose biodiversity-related impacts and risks. Evidence also points to forms of stewardship by bondholders, who can express environmental expectations to issuers (H. S. Lee et al., 2024). However, the influence of lenders is typically more limited than that of investors, given the absence of ownership stakes and the competitive dynamics of lending markets, where some financial institutions may apply less rigorous environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards.

Voting on shareholder resolutions, a mechanism exclusive to listed equity investors, enables shareholders to express positions on corporate decisions, including those related to biodiversity. This process typically involves issue-specific research, the formulation of a voting policy, and engagement with investee businesses before and after votes are cast. Large investors may delegate voting to proxy advisors (Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), 2021). While in theory, voting is a key lever for biodiversity action, recent studies indicate that major asset managers frequently vote against biodiversity-focused resolutions (Baldock et al., 2023). When engagement or voting fails to deliver meaningful progress on biodiversity-related objectives – or where there is a demonstrated lack of effectiveness in similar efforts by other investors – investors may adopt escalation measures. These can include filing shareholder resolutions, opposing the reappointment of unresponsive board members, making public statements, or pursuing shareholder litigation (Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), 2021). Escalation strategies may also encompass divestment or the exclusion of certain businesses or sectors from investment portfolios.

5.6.5.4. Managing biodiversity risk and impacts through divestment and exclusion

Divestment and exclusion represent key strategies through which financial institutions can address biodiversity-related risks and impacts within their investment and lending portfolios. For investors, this may involve selling holdings in (divestment) or refraining from investing in (exclusion) businesses or sectors with significant biodiversity footprints. Lenders similarly apply exclusion policies to avoid extending credit to high-footprint business or industries. For instance, Standard Chartered has committed to withholding financial services from clients whose operations may affect UNESCO World Heritage Sites, involve trade in CITES-listed species, or contribute to the degradation of Ramsar wetlands, high conservation value and high carbon stock forests, or peatlands

(Standard Chartered, 2024). The European bank ABN AMRO, for example, has general and sector-specific activities on its exclusion list, including those that lead to the conversion or degradation of protected areas or critical habitats, or infringe on the rights of Indigenous and/or vulnerable groups without their free, prior and informed consent (ABN AMRO, 2021). Finally, insurers can exclude coverage for certain business activities from insurance products.

The question of whether investors should prioritize engagement or divestment in response to environmental, social and governance-related concerns has been the subject of ongoing debate. However, these approaches are not mutually exclusive. Many investors adopt a stewardship-led strategy, treating divestment as a measure of last resort within a broader escalation framework. For instance, the Norwegian Pension Fund Global combines active environmental, social and governance-related engagement and voting to encourage improved corporate practices, while also operating a Council on Ethics that advises on the exclusion or observation of businesses whose activities contravene the fund’s ethical guidelines (Mestad, 2020). Stewardship is often a tool to promote ‘best practice’ while divestment sets the bottom line of what is acceptable. Given the fiduciary constraints on divestment, it is usually a recourse only when there are obvious, and material biodiversity-related financial risks associated with an investment. This is because once an investor divests, it loses the option of driving change from within the system (Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), 2021).

Equally, there is evidence to show that the financial impact of divestment is often not enough to move a company to change its practices on environmental, social and governance issues; by its very definition divestment means that stock is bought by another investor which likely cares less about the environmental, social and governance-related issue over which the stock was sold. Nevertheless, divestment can be undertaken for purely ethical reasons irrespective of downstream consequences, with investors acknowledging that certain industries should be strictly off the table for investment. This can serve to de-legitimize certain businesses or industries, triggering divestment from other financial institutions as well. Investors therefore, can benefit from carefully considering the advantages and disadvantages of the engagement and divestment options available to them (GEFI, n.d.; PRI, 2022). **Table 5.2** outlines relevant factors identified favouring divestments or engagement with businesses based on responsibility principles.

Table 5.2. Factors favouring engagement with or divestment from a business

Factors favouring divestment	Factors favouring engagement
Investor is seeking value-alignment	Investor is seeking real-world impact
Poor opportunities to transition to a more sustainable business model	Issue is systemic and non-diversifiable
Investors have low leverage, e.g., a controlled company, lack of legal recourse	Investors have or can improve leverage by working collaboratively
Other escalation measures have already been exhausted	Alternative escalation measures remain open to investors
	Fiduciary constraints on use of divestment

While the above-mentioned stewardship and escalation strategies are applicable both to active investors (those that themselves select stocks to invest in) and passive investors (those that do not select stock themselves but instead invest in managed funds that track stock indices), the latter may feel less incentivized to engage with investee businesses. This is because a passive investor usually

has a diverse and diffuse portfolio – its engagement with one company within its portfolio is not likely to result in significant risk management benefits. Likewise, divestment may not be easy for passive investors as it entails exiting from a managed fund in its entirety rather than divesting from a specific company or industry, something that active investors can easily do. These challenges are becoming increasingly significant as a growing share of global assets under management is being allocated to passive investment strategies, driven by leading asset managers such as BlackRock and Vanguard Group (UNPRI, 2019).

5.6.6. Financing green

According to United Nations Environment Programme's 'State of Finance for Nature' (2023), approximately \$200 billion is currently directed annually toward the protection, restoration and sustainable management of biodiversity. However, this figure must rise to \$737 billion by 2050 to meet global needs. The private sector, including both financial institutions and businesses engaging through market-based mechanisms, currently contributes 10 per cent (\$23 billion) of this total (UNEP, 2026). Through their 'financing green' type actions, financial institutions can help fill the global biodiversity finance gap. This includes financing for activities that aim to generate measurable biodiversity outcomes and nature's contributions to people, such as watershed protection, carbon sequestration, pollination and recreation, which can be monetized through mechanisms like biodiversity credits, ecotourism and sustainability certifications, and sold to buyers including project developers with offset obligations or consumers seeking certified sustainable products (Conservation Finance Alliance, 2014; Zu Ermgassen & Löfqvist, 2024). Outlined below are selected 'financing green' approaches that financial institutions decide on at the corporate level to support biodiversity enterprises.

5.6.6.1. Blended finance

Business activities that monetize biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, are often perceived as high-risk and typically fall outside the scope of traditional, market-rate financing due to their limited bankability. Blended finance offers a mechanism to address this constraint by combining capital from public or philanthropic sources, such as governments, development agencies, or foundations, with funding from private financial institutions, including banks and pension funds. This structure enables the reallocation of investment risks to public or philanthropic actors, who are more willing to absorb such risks to mobilize private capital, which continues to earn market-rate returns. The catalytic capital provided by public or philanthropic entities within blended finance structures can take several forms: early-stage risk capital (such as junior or first-loss equity or debt), concessional finance (including grants or below-market-rate loans), or credit enhancement tools (such as guarantees or insurance) (Lankes, 2021; OECD, 2020). Junior equity and subordinated debt instruments allow public or philanthropic investors to absorb greater risk by accepting lower priority in dividend payments or loan repayments, thereby improving the risk-return profile for private investors. In first-loss arrangements, these actors explicitly commit to absorbing initial losses if returns fall short of expectations (Earth Security, 2021; Kwon et al., 2022). Several investment vehicles leveraging this blended finance model have emerged to provide seed and growth capital to biodiversity enterprises, including the EcoEnterprises Fund (EcoEnterprises Fund, 2025) and the Nature+ Accelerator Capital Investment Fund (IUCN, 2020).

5.6.6.2. Green or sustainability-linked bonds

Financial institutions may channel capital into bonds designed to support biodiversity protection or restoration efforts. These instruments typically take the form of either green bonds or sustainability-linked bonds. Green bonds, also referred to as 'use-of-proceeds' bonds, allocate funds to specific environmental projects and offer a fixed coupon rate – the interest paid to investors. In contrast,

sustainability-linked bonds do not earmark proceeds for projects; instead, their coupon rates are contingent on the issuer's performance against predefined biodiversity-related targets (LSE, 2023).

An example of a biodiversity-focused green bond is the Forest Resilience Bond which has mobilized \$4 million to finance wildfire risk mitigation activities, such as vegetation thinning and prescribed burns, across 15,000 hectares of the Tahoe National Forest, with private investors including Calvert Impact Capital and CSAA Insurance Group participating in the offering (Earth Security, 2021). In March 2025, Itaú Unibanco, with support from the International Finance Corporation and IDB Invest, issued a BRL 1.4 billion bond (around \$250 million) divided into two series to fund biodiversity conservation and social initiatives in Brazil. One series will allocate up to \$75 million to biodiversity projects, including Itaú and Syngenta's REVERTE® Program. This supports rural producers recover degraded land (with a target of 1 million hectares by 2030), while aiming to preserve native vegetation, promote sustainable agriculture and contribute to Brazil's bioeconomy efforts (International Finance Corporation (IFC), 2025). A prominent example of a sustainability-linked instrument is the Wildlife Conservation Bond (also known as the 'Rhino Bond') issued by the World Bank in 2022 to support the recovery of the Critically Endangered Black Rhino population in South Africa. Unlike traditional bonds, the Rhino Bond links investor returns to conservation outcomes, with end-of-term payments based on the measured increase in rhino population. Purchasers included private asset managers such as Nuveen, Alliance Bernstein, ASN Impact Investors, Azimut Investments, BlueBay Asset Management, INGKA Investments, and Mackenzie Investments (The World Bank, 2022). Both green and sustainability-linked bonds often operate within blended finance structures, incorporating participation from public or philanthropic entities to enhance creditworthiness or reduce perceived risk.

5.6.6.3. Impact investing

Impact investing refers to the deployment of capital with the explicit intention of generating positive environmental or social outcomes alongside financial returns, often with investors willing to accept returns below market rate. Such investments are made by a range of actors, including wealthy individuals and families – typically through family offices or private foundations – as well as private institutional investors and asset managers. A significant portion of impact investing takes place through pooled investment vehicles, or impact investment funds, which aggregate capital from multiple investors. Some of these funds are conservation-focused and target early-stage investments in businesses seeking positive biodiversity outcomes (Conservation Finance Alliance, 2014). A recent example is the Biodiversity Impact Fund launched by Privium Fund Management in 2025, which aims to raise €500 million to invest in biodiversity conservation and restoration initiatives, with initial commitments secured from Dutch family offices (Higgins, 2024). These funds frequently incorporate blended finance structures, where public or philanthropic entities provide catalytic capital – such as concessional finance or risk-absorbing instruments – to attract commercial investors operating at market rates alongside those engaged in below-market-rate impact investing.

5.7. Actions to change the system and influence others

Transformative change requires businesses to go beyond addressing their own impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (IPBES, 2024a). This section outlines the additional actions that businesses can take to help create an enabling environment for transformative change and to influence other businesses and non-business actors to also take positive action. These include: (1) halting and reversing biodiversity beyond private actions to mitigate impacts caused by their own operations and value chains; (2) engaging in system-level actions to address external barriers; (3) scaling the impact of individual actions through partnerships and collective action; and (4) credibly signalling actions and outcomes to inspire and influence others.

5.7.1. Delivering outcomes beyond impact mitigation goals

Businesses can contribute to global goals by taking additional conservation actions that deliver benefits beyond mitigation of their own impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. These actions can support landscape-scale conservation objectives, such as restoring ecosystem connectivity (Lamont et al., 2023), and may also contribute to broader conservation priorities or global targets (Langhammer et al., 2024), even when outcomes are more difficult to measure or attribute to a single business action. Examples include funding biodiversity research, supporting education and capacity-building and contributing to the management of protected areas or threatened species and ecosystems, such as through invasive species control, sustainable ecosystem management, improved agricultural practices or climate adaptation initiatives (Finance for Nature, n.d.).

Many of these actions can form part of nature-based solutions, particularly when applied through ecosystem-based approaches. Businesses can invest in such solutions to address interconnected challenges like water security, climate adaptation and energy transition (Pörtner et al., 2021). When well-designed, climate-focused initiatives can deliver co-benefits for biodiversity (World Bank, 2022b) – as shown by the IPBES Nexus Assessment through 71 response options identified (IPBES, 2024b) – although trade-offs are also a risk and require careful, strategic planning to optimise outcomes (IPBES, 2024b; Martin et al., 2022). Global standards, such as those developed by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature, support businesses in designing and implementing effective nature-based solutions (IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature, 2020). As another example, The World Bank Climate Facility has released guidance for applying nature-based solutions in the mining sector, covering both operational activities and integrated approaches across climate, water and social objectives (World Bank, 2021).

The scale and location of additional conservation actions needed, and which businesses are most responsible for implementing these, remain key questions. Setting priorities and providing clarity and consensus on business responsibilities should be based on societal expectations and principles of just responsibility-sharing. This may include considerations of a business's dependencies on biodiversity, historic contributions to biodiversity loss, or other factors relevant to distributing responsibility fairly (Bai et al., 2024). Emerging frameworks such as SBTN's landscape engagement targets (Science Based Targets Network (SBTN), n.d.-b) and industry-specific performance requirements are beginning to set clearer expectations for corporate participation in landscape-scale initiatives that aim to deliver proactive, measurable outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

5.7.2. Directly supporting the enabling environment

Businesses have a growing role to play in advocating for ambitious public policy on biodiversity (Business for Nature, 2024). While positive engagement is increasing, it remains relatively new and underdeveloped compared to climate advocacy (Business for Nature et al., 2022). Larger, older, internationally active businesses with strong government relationships are more likely to engage in lobbying (Weymouth, 2012; Yamahaki & Marchewitz, 2024). Recent examples include Patagonia's advocacy for climate action and public lands protection (Patagonia, 2021), Microsoft supporting low-carbon policy development (Microsoft, 2024), Unilever driving efforts on regenerative agriculture and sustainable palm oil sourcing (Unilever, 2024), Google promoting renewable energy adoption through initiatives like RE100 (Google, 2023), and Levi Strauss & Co. advancing sustainable water policies through the Alliance for Water Stewardship (Levi Strauss & Co, 2019). Best practice can draw from the more advanced field of climate lobbying (Global Standard on Corporate Climate Lobbying, 2022; We Mean Business Coalition, 2023) and includes embedding advocacy within core business strategy, allocating sufficient internal resources, and making public commitments through leadership. Effective policy engagement entails extending actions to industry associations and

pushing for alignment with biodiversity goals, especially given that corporate lobbying against strong environment policies remains common (Österblom et al., 2022).

Businesses can influence outcomes through participation in financial associations that shape standards and practices. Organizations such as the International Capital Market Association (ICMA) and the Loan Market Association (LMA) bring together issuers, investors, banks, and intermediaries to establish common rules for directing capital toward environmental goals. Voluntary frameworks like the Green Bond Principles (GBP), Green Loan Principles (GLP), and Sustainability-Linked Bond Principles (SLBP) provide clear guidance on financing activities that deliver biodiversity benefits, from conservation and sustainable land use to ecosystem restoration. By aligning members around shared principles, these associations improve clarity and cohesion, strengthen accountability, and create peer pressure for stronger environmental performance. In doing so, they help ensure that finance plays a catalytic role in driving collective action on biodiversity, complementing company-level strategies with systemic standards and incentives. These initiatives could support necessary reform of global and national financial systems (see **Chapter 6.3.2.2**) where appropriately aligned with global ambitions within the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the efforts of ministries of finance to transform fiscal and economic policies.

Businesses can drive system change by shaping consumer values and promoting sustainable consumption practices. Increasing consumption, driven by population growth and rising per-capita demand, are major drivers of biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019a). For example, food systems alone account for 40 per cent of global biodiversity loss through land-use change and greenhouse gas emissions (Wilting et al., 2017). Businesses can influence societal norms by disclosing product-level impacts, using labels and marketing to guide consumer choices, and investing in education and awareness campaigns. For example, the Satoyama Initiative brings together 328 partners, including businesses, academics, non-governmental organizations, governments, and Indigenous communities, to promote eco-friendly agriculture, reduce waste and strengthen local food systems. By advocating traditional diets and localised consumption patterns, the initiative fosters biodiversity, community resilience and sustainability, while reducing reliance on global value chains (Nishi et al., 2021).

Businesses also have a role in shaping knowledge, skills and capacity. According to the World Economic Forum, up to 395 million jobs could be created through economic transitions (WEF, 2020). By investing in education, research and training, businesses can help build the capacity needed to implement biodiversity strategies. Engaging in social biodiversity leadership by publicly promoting biodiversity values and commitments can shift social norms among customers, suppliers and employees, while also attracting a growing cohort of sustainability-minded consumers and talent (Baggaley et al., 2023). However, as outlined in **Chapter 6 (Section 6.3.6.1)**, if greenwash accusations are to be avoided, leadership ought to be underpinned by credible strategies and measurable action (**Box 5.1**).

Businesses can play a catalytic role in making biodiversity data and tools publicly accessible as shared resources. Pre-competitive collaboration, where businesses collaborate on technology and data outside of direct competition, is key to enabling this. In Brazil, the Soy Moratorium, which is governed by Associação Brasileira das Indústrias de Óleos Vegetais (ABIOVE), Associação Nacional dos Exportadores de Cereais (ANEC) and civil society partners, ensures soy sold by signatories is not sourced from Amazon land deforested after July 2008 (Associação Nacional dos Exportadores de Cereais (ANEC), n.d.; Heilmayr et al., 2020). The initiative relies on satellite monitoring provided by Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries (Associação Brasileira das Indústrias de Óleos Vegetais) in collaboration with Brazil's National Institute for Space Research and Agrosatélite (Agrosatélite Geotecnologia Aplicada Ltda., 2022; Grupo de Trabalho da Soja (GTS) et al., 2023). Another example is Global Forest Watch, a free, open-access platform developed by the World Resources Institute with support from Google, the Jane Goodall Institute, and others, enabling

stakeholders to monitor deforestation globally. Businesses have also partnered with non-governmental organizations in research, such as the collaboration between the World Wildlife Fund for Nature and Johnson & Johnson, to explore links between forests and human health (Beatty et al., 2022; World Wildlife Fund (WWF), n.d.).

5.7.3. Collaboration, partnerships and collective action

The implementation of actions and the outcomes of those actions for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people can be scaled up through engagement, partnerships and collective action involving actors within and beyond the business sector (IPBES, 2024a). Meaningful engagement and partnerships are important for knowledge acquisition, democratic environmental governance and improved corporate legitimacy (Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2017). Partnerships established through trade-associations and commodity roundtables and agreements can supplement formal rules of play across multiple actors, through developing guidance and standards that raise the bar on good practice (Cramb & McCarthy, 2016; Gibbs et al., 2015; Lambin & Thorlakson, 2018; Levy et al., 2023) For example, international leadership organizations have been shown to facilitate dissemination of innovation among mining businesses, in support of better outcomes across battery supply chains (Mendonca Severiano et al., 2025). Public-private partnerships can unlock financing, generate new technologies, improve governance, expand partnerships with civil society organizations, including IPLCs, and lead to lasting and equitable outcomes for biodiversity (Andréasson, 2023; Fitzgerald, 2021; Schroeder et al., 2020). For example, the Sahanala cooperative in Madagascar, created by the non-governmental organization Fanamby, enables local communities to pursue sustainable livelihoods near protected areas while participating in federations that operate in international markets under community-led governance (Sahanala, n.d.).

Partnerships vary in terms of their scale and purpose. Some focus on implementing and coordinating action at the landscape level to address issues within a specific geography (**Box 5.7**) or sector. For example, heavily traded agricultural commodities (e.g., coffee, cocoa, tea and palm oil) have more than 10 per cent of their production area under coordinated voluntary sustainability standards schemes (Tayleur et al., 2017). Cross-border collaboration is crucial for addressing transboundary challenges, such as protecting wildlife migration corridors or managing river basins. Examples include the Great Green Wall in Africa (United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), n.d.) and the Coral Triangle Initiative in Southeast Asia (Coral Triangle Initiative on Coral Reefs, Fisheries and Food Security (CTI-CFF), n.d.). Global partnerships can efficiently direct business resources and investment toward conservation priorities and where barriers to action are largest. Multi-stakeholder platforms, such as the Business for Nature coalition, for example, provide guidance to members on how to align business activities, including measurement and action, with global biodiversity targets. Public-private partnerships, such as the Great Barrier Reef Partnership – a AU\$443 million initiative involving the Australian Government, BHP, Rio Tinto and over 500 other partners – aims to deliver large-scale conservation outcomes, which, as of 2025, has 370 projects aiming to restore and protect the reef (Great Barrier Reef Foundation, n.d.). Public-private partnerships can also support benefit-sharing agreements (**Box 5.8**) and enable businesses to contribute directly to National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) (UNDP BIOFIN, 2023; UNEP Finance Initiative (UNEP FI) & UNDP BIOFIN, 2023).

Partnerships also drive collective action at different decision-making levels. For example, the Fashion Pact is a sector-wide initiative led by chief executive officers (CEO), requiring member businesses to make corporate commitments to zero deforestation and land conversion, development of biodiversity strategies, and sourcing restrictions to reduce biodiversity impacts (The Fashion Pact, n.d.). The Pharmaceutical Supply Chain Initiative (PSCI) convenes businesses in the healthcare sector to improve environmental, safety, and social outcomes across their value chains (PSCI, n.d.). Institutional investor networks, such as the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), provide

Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people
Chapter 5. Businesses as key actors of change: options for action.

platforms for collaborative policy engagement on environmental issues, including biodiversity
(Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2022).

Box 5.7. Place-based initiatives to enable coordinated landscape action on biodiversity

Business can promote, endorse, finance and participate in the coordination of landscape-scale action on biodiversity. One example is the Rimba Collective in Indonesia. It is a collaboration of several consumer goods manufacturers connected to the agricultural commodities industry. The initiative was set up to help corporations deliver on their individual sustainability commitments and invest funds in attributable biodiversity outcomes (Rimba collective, n.d.). The initiative started with the palm oil sector. Each company delivers on its individual sustainability objectives, whilst protecting and restoring landscapes and supporting natural landscapes and supporting people's livelihoods. Rimba projects are run by local civil society organizations, working together with communities and with different levels of government to deliver outcomes intended to benefit biodiversity and people. The engagement with a wide variety of actors is crucial for the long-term success and impact of the projects to ensure actions are aligned with the needs and priorities of the local communities while also promoting biodiversity conservation. Rimba projects like the one in the Pawan Pesaguan landscapes demonstrate the importance of adopting a holistic approach to forest management that considers the ecological, social, and economic aspects of sustainability (Rimba collective, n.d.).

Box 5.8. Partnerships and initiatives support benefit sharing and fair access to biodiversity: the case of South Africa's rooibos tea industry.

Aspalathus linearis (commonly known as rooibos) has long been used by the San and Khoikhoi peoples as a remedy for a wide range of ailments (Department of Environmental Affairs of Republic of South Africa, 2014). The plants' fine, needle-like leaves are naturally caffeine-free, rich in antioxidants, and used to relieve allergic symptoms, provide energy, and promote skin healing. Yet the rooibos tea value chain reflects a complex and often unequal history, transitioning from traditional harvesting by the Khoikhoi to large-scale commercial farming, and mirroring broader patterns of colonialism, economic exploitation, and cultural appropriation that have shaped many industries.

Global governance frameworks have gradually sought to address these inequities. The 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity, for example addresses the terms and conditions for access to genetic resources and benefit sharing, which was later supported by the Bonn Guidelines on Access to Genetic Resources and Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising out of their Utilization, which provided steps and processes for fair access to biological resources and the equitable distribution of benefits from bioprospecting. This principle was reinforced in South Africa through the Biodiversity Act 10 of 2004, the Bioprospecting, Access and Benefit Sharing (BABS) Regulations of 2008, and the adoption of the Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention. Together, these frameworks have raised awareness of benefit-sharing obligations and opened new opportunities for communities to leverage their traditional knowledge (Natural Justice, 2019).

Despite this progress, only around 10 per cent of rooibos is produced by Indigenous farmers, underscoring the continued need for mechanisms that protect community rights and interests. A major milestone came in 2019, when the Khoikhoi and San peoples, as traditional knowledge holders, entered an industry-wide access and benefit sharing agreement with the South African rooibos sector. This was underpinned by the Rooibos Biocultural Community Protocol, which sets out how communities are organized for benefit-sharing purposes and how they expect industry, government, and researchers to engage with them (National Khoisan Council, 2019). The Protocol has created a stronger sense of collective identity, particularly in the Cederberg Mountains, the natural home of rooibos. The South African Rooibos Council (Rooibos Council, n.d.) also plays a key role in promoting rooibos and supporting stakeholders through research and communication (Natural Justice, 2019).

International recognition has further reinforced the value of rooibos. In 2021, the European Commission granted rooibos protected designation of origin (PDO) status, making it the first African product to be entered into the EU's register of protected geographical indications (Law Society of South Africa, 2021). This recognition underscores the cultural and economic significance of rooibos, highlighting its association with superior quality, sustainability, and place-based identity. It also illustrates how geographical indications can serve as a valuable tool to safeguard traditional knowledge, while strengthening trade relationships that provide affordable food and livelihood opportunities across the value chain.

5.7.4. Social signalling actions to inspire action by others

Social signalling actions by business can be understood as deliberate, outward-facing commitments, disclosures or initiatives that aim both to advance biodiversity goals and to influence peers and stakeholders by setting visible norms and expectations (Booth et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025). Such actions can demonstrate leadership, establish credibility and create peer pressure that encourages

others within and beyond the industry to follow suit. In the biodiversity context, this includes public commitments such as adopting ambitious targets, joining high-profile pledges like the Finance for Biodiversity Pledge (Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, n.d.), Business for Nature's *Make it Mandatory* (Business for Nature et al., 2022), *Call to Action* (Business for Nature, n.d.-a) and *Act Now for Nature* campaigns (Now for Nature, n.d.), and publishing disclosures aligned with frameworks such as the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures.

Signalling also encompasses symbolic yet substantive leadership moves, such as establishing biodiversity funds, issuing biodiversity-focused bonds or securing eco-certifications that act as visible proof of commitment (Booth et al., 2024). These actions help shape external conditions in which biodiversity-positive practices become industry norms (Baggaley et al., 2023). By making their actions visible, businesses can advance their own agendas while amplifying influence, diffusing innovation, shaping investor and consumer expectations, and accelerating transformative change.

Divestment is a prominent example of signalling by financial institutions: withdrawing from companies with significant unaddressed biodiversity impacts and adopting exclusion policies for high-footprint industries sends a strong message on responsible practice (**Section 5.6.5.4**). For example, ASN Impact Investors recently announced it would divest from clothing companies and exclude fast fashion businesses that fail to adopt circular business models, noting this decision followed extensive engagement efforts (ASN Bank, 2024).

However, as with advocacy (**Section 5.7.2**), signalling must be backed by credible strategies, commitments, and tangible actions to manage a company's own biodiversity impacts and dependencies and meaningfully contribute towards system level change (Smith et al., 2019). While disclosures can raise awareness and transparency, they rarely lead on their own to systemic shifts in business models or supply chains. They also often lack focus on specific biodiversity elements critical for achieving global goals (Adler et al., 2018; Hassan et al., 2022) and tend to be weakest where biodiversity and risks of loss are highest (Skouloudis et al., 2019). To be effective in driving behaviour change, signalling needs to be combined with regulation, incentives and collaborative frameworks.

5.8. References

- ABN AMRO. (2021). *Exclusion List*. ABN AMRO Bank N.V.
https://www.abnamro.nl/nl/media/Exclusion-List-03-2021_tcm16-120991.pdf
- Accountability Framework Initiative. (n.d.-a). *The Accountability Framework*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://accountability-framework.org/>
- Accountability Framework Initiative. (n.d.-b). *Traceability*. Retrieved 11 September 2025, from <https://accountability-framework.org/fileadmin/uploads/afi/Documents/Traceability-Accountability-Framework.pdf>
- Accountability Framework Initiative. (2019). *Operational Guidance on Smallholder Inclusion in Ethical Supply Chains*. https://accountability-framework.org/fileadmin/uploads/afi/Documents/Operational_Guidance/OG_Supply_Chain_Management-2020-5.pdf
- Accountability Framework initiative. (2019). *Operational Guidance on Supply Chain Management*. https://accountability-framework.org/fileadmin/uploads/afi/Documents/Operational_Guidance/OG_Supply_Chain_Management-2020-5.pdf
- Accountability Framework initiative (AFi). (2019). *Operational Guidance on Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC)* (Minor revision May 2020). Accountability Framework initiative. https://accountability-framework.org/core-principles/?core_principle=88
- Addison, P. F. E., Bull, J. W., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2019). Using conservation science to advance corporate biodiversity accountability. *Conservation Biology*, 33(2), 307–318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13190>
- Addison, P. F. E., Stephenson, P. J., Bull, J. W., Carbone, G., Burgman, M., Burgass, M. J., Gerber, L. R., Howard, P., McCormick, N., McRae, L., Reuter, K. E., Starkey, M., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2020). Bringing sustainability to life: A framework to guide biodiversity indicator development for business performance management. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(8), 3303–3313. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2573>
- Adler, R., Mansi, M., & Pandey, R. (2018). Biodiversity and threatened species reporting by the top Fortune Global companies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 31(3), 787–825. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-03-2016-2490>
- Adler, R., Mansi, M., Pandey, R., & Stringer, C. (2017). United Nations Decade on Biodiversity: A study of the reporting practices of the Australian mining industry. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 30(8), 1711–1745. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-04-2015-2028>
- Afnor Editions. (2021). *Biodiversity—Strategic and operational approach—Requirements and guidelines, NF X32-001*. <https://www.boutique.afnor.org/en-gb/standard/nf-x32001/biodiversity-strategic-and-operational-approach-requirements-and-guidelines/fa199979/261068>
- Agrawal, T. K., Kumar, V., Pal, R., Wang, L., & Chen, Y. (2021). Blockchain-based framework for supply chain traceability: A case example of textile and clothing industry. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 154, 107130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2021.107130>
- Agrosatélite Geotecnologia Aplicada Ltda. (2022). *Monitoring of the Soy Moratorium through Satellite Images: Supplementary Methodological Material*. Grupo de Trabalho da Soja. <https://abiove.org.br/en/publications/>
- Ahen, F. (2019). Globalisation and its Implications for TNCs' Global Responsibility. *Humanistic Management Journal*, 4(1), 33–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41463-019-00057-7>

- Aladağ, Ö. F. (2023). Integrating Biodiversity into Business Strategy: Theoretical Foundations and Exemplary Cases. *İktisadi İdari ve Siyasal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 8(22), 782–794.
<https://doi.org/10.25204/iktisad.1341425>
- Alexander, S. (2012). *The Sufficiency Economy. Envisioning Prosperous Way Down*. Simplicity Institute. <http://simplicityinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/TheSufficiencyEconomy3.pdf>
- Aluminium Stewardship Initiative (ASI). (2023). *ASI Chain of Custody (CoC) Standard, Version 2.1* [Standard]. Aluminium Stewardship Initiative Ltd. <https://aluminium-stewardship.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/ASI-Chain-of-Custody-Standard-V2.1-April-2023.pdf>
- Andréasson, H. (2023). *Business and biodiversity: How businesses understand and work with biodiversity* (Issue E2023:138) [Master's Thesis, Chalmers University of Technology]. <https://research.chalmers.se/en/publication/>
- Armeni, A., Lyon, C., & Menter, J. (2023). *Alternative Ownership Enterprises Report*. Transform Fiance. <https://www.transformfinance.org/alternative-ownership-enterprises-report>
- Armstrong, C. M., Niinimäki, K., Kujala, S., Karell, E., & Lang, C. (2015). Sustainable product-service systems for clothing: Exploring consumer perceptions of consumption alternatives in Finland. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 97, 30–39.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.01.046>
- ASN Bank. (2024). *ASN Impact Investors sells all investments in the clothing industry*. <https://www.asnbank.nl/zo-maakt-geld-gelukkig/asn-impact-investors-sells-all-investments-in-the-clothing-industry.html>
- Associação Nacional dos Exportadores de Cereais (ANEC). (n.d.). *The Soy Moratorium*. Retrieved <https://anec.com.br/article/a-moratoria-da-soja>
- Aviva. (2021). *Aviva Biodiversity Policy*. <https://www.aviva.com/content/dam/aviva-corporate/documents/socialpurpose/pdfs/aviva-biodiversity-policy.pdf>
- B Lab. (n.d.). *What's Behind The B?* Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://usca.bcorporation.net/about-b-corps/>
- Baggaley, S., Johnston, M., Dimitrijevic, J., Le Guen, C., Howard, P., Murphy, L., Booth, H., & Starkey, M. (2023). *Nature positive for business*. IUCN. <https://portals.iucn.org/library/node/51299>
- Bai, X., Hasan, S., Andersen, L. S., Bjørn, A., Kilkiş, Ş., Ospina, D., Liu, J., Cornell, S. E., Sabag Muñoz, O., De Bremond, A., Crona, B., DeClerck, F., Gupta, J., Hoff, H., Nakicenovic, N., Obura, D., Whiteman, G., Broadgate, W., Lade, S. J., ... Zimm, C. (2024). Translating Earth system boundaries for cities and businesses. *Nature Sustainability*, 7(2), 108–119.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01255-w>
- Baldock, C., Willis, J., & Kozlowski, N. (2023). *Voting Against Nature: Are Asset Managers Using Their Proxy Votes for Action on Biodiversity Loss?* Planet Tracker.
- BankTrack. (2020). *Soft Commitments, Hard Lessons: An analysis of the Soft Commodities Compact*. Soft Commitments, Hard Lessons: an analysis of the Soft Commodities Compact
- Bassen, A., Buchholz, D., Lopatta, K., & Rudolf, A. R. (2025). Assessing biodiversity-related disclosure: Drivers, outcomes, and financial impacts. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 29(1), 311–329. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13596>
- Bauer, T. N., & Aiman-Smith, L. (1996). Green career choices: The influence of ecological stance on recruiting. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 10(4), 445–458.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02251780>
- BBOP. (2012). *Standard on biodiversity offsets*. Forest Trends.

- BBOP. (2018). *Working for Biodiversity Net Gain An Overview of the Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP) 2004–2018*. <https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/BBOP-Overview-2018-FINAL-29-10-18.pdf>
- Beatty, C. R., Stevenson, M., Pacheco, P., Terrana, A., Folse, M., & Cody, A. (2022). *The Vitality of Forests: Illustrating the Evidence Connecting Forests and Human Health*. World Wildlife Fund. <https://www.worldwildlife.org/publications/the-vitality-of-forests-illustrating-the-evidence-connecting-forests-and-human-health>
- Beck-O'Brien, M., & Bringezu, S. (2021). Biodiversity Monitoring in Long-Distance Food Supply Chains: Tools, Gaps and Needs to Meet Business Requirements and Sustainability Goals. *Sustainability*, 13(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158536>
- Bell-James, J., & Watson, J. E. M. (2025). Ambitions in national plans do not yet match bold international protection and restoration commitments. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 9(3), 417–424. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-025-02636-4>
- Bennun, L., Fletcher, C., Cook, A., Wilson, D., Jobson, B., Asante-Owusu, R., Dakmejian, A., & Liu, Q. (2024). *Guidance on biodiversity cumulative impact assessment for wind and solar developments and associated infrastructure*. IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature. <https://doi.org/10.2305/EHGE6100>
- Bhattacharya, C., Sen, S., & Korschun, D. (2008). *Using Corporate Social Responsibility to Win the War for Talent*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279905171_Using_Corporate_Social_Responsibility_to_Win_the_War_for_Talent
- Bigard, C., Pioch, S., & Thompson, J. D. (2017). The inclusion of biodiversity in environmental impact assessment: Policy-related progress limited by gaps and semantic confusion. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 200, 35–45.
- Biodiversity Credit Alliance. (2024, May). *Definition of a Biodiversity Credit*. <https://www.biodiversitycreditalliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Definition-of-a-Biodiversity-Credit-Rev-220524.pdf>
- BNP Paribas. (2021, February). *BNP Paribas defines a restrictive policy to fight deforestation in the Amazon and the Cerrado regions*. <https://group.bnpparibas/en/press-release/bnp-paribas-defines-restrictive-policy-fight-deforestation-amazon-cerrado-regions>
- Bocken, N. M. P., Niessen, L., & Short, S. W. (2022). The Sufficiency-Based Circular Economy—An Analysis of 150 Companies. *Frontiers in Sustainability*, 3, 899289. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2022.899289>
- Bocken, N. M. P., & Short, S. W. (2016). Towards a sufficiency-driven business model: Experiences and opportunities. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 18, 41–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2015.07.010>
- Bocken, N. M. P., Short, S. W., Rana, P., & Evans, S. (2014). A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 65, 12–56. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.11.039>
- Boiral, O., & Heras-Saizarbitoria, I. (2017). Managing Biodiversity Through Stakeholder Involvement: Why, Who, and for What Initiatives? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 140(3), 403–421. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2668-3>
- Boiral, O., Heras-Saizarbitoria, I., & Brotherton, M.-C. (2019). Improving corporate biodiversity management through employee involvement. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(5), 688–698. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2273>
- Booth, H., Milner-Gulland, E. J., McCormick, N., & Starkey, M. (2024). Operationalizing transformative change for business in the context of Nature Positive. *One Earth*, S2590332224002951. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.06.003>

- Bromwich, T., White, T. B., Bouchez, A., Hawkins, I., Zu Ermgassen, S., Bull, J., Bartlett, H., Bennun, L., Biggs, E., Booth, H., Clark, M., El Geneidy, S., Prescott, G. W., Sonter, L. J., Starkey, M., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2025). Navigating uncertainty in life cycle assessment-based approaches to biodiversity footprinting. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 2041-210X.70001. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.70001>
- Brown, E., Dudley, N., Lindhe, A., Muhtaman, D. R., Stewart, C., & Synnott, T. (2013). *Common Guidance for the Identification of High Conservation Values: A Good Practice Guide for Identifying HCVs across Different Ecosystems and Production Systems*. HCV Resource Network. <https://www.hcvnetwork.org/library/common-guidance-for-the-identification-of-high-conservation-values>
- Brownlie, S., & Treweek, J. (2018). *Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Impact Assessment*. <https://www.iaia.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/BEST-PRACTICE-Biodiversity-Ecosystem-Services.pdf>
- Buckley, R. C., Liddon, M., Underdahl, S., Zhang, Z. J., Cooper, M.-A., Chauvenet, A. L. M., & Zhong, L. (2025). Nature positive rhetoric, risk and reality: Sector-scale political ecology at CBD COP16. *Npj Biodiversity*, 4(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44185-025-00087-5>
- Bull, J., Baker, J., Griffiths, V. F., Jones, J. P. G., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2018). *Ensuring No Net Loss for people as well as biodiversity: Good practice principles*. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/4ygh7>
- Bull, J. W., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Addison, P. F. E., Arlidge, W. N. S., Baker, J., Brooks, T. M., Burgass, M. J., Hinsley, A., Maron, M., Robinson, J. G., Sekhran, N., Sinclair, S. P., Stuart, S. N., zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., & Watson, J. E. M. (2020). Net positive outcomes for nature. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 4(1), 4–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-1022-z>
- Bull, J. W., Sonter, L. J., Gordon, A., Maron, M., Narain, D., Reside, A. E., Sánchez, L. E., Shumway, N., von Hase, A., & Quétier, F. (2022). Quantifying the “avoided” biodiversity impacts associated with economic development. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 20(6), 370–378. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2496>
- Bull, J. W., & Strange, N. (2018). The global extent of biodiversity offset implementation under no net loss policies. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(12), 790–798. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0176-z>
- Burbano, V. C. (2016). Social Responsibility Messages and Worker Wage Requirements: Field Experimental Evidence from Online Labor Marketplaces. *Organization Science*, 27(4), 1010–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2016.1066>
- Burgess, N. D., Ali, N., Bedford, J., Bhola, N., Brooks, S., Cierna, A., Correa, R., Harris, M., Hargey, A., Hughes, J., McDermott-Long, O., Miles, L., Ravilious, C., Rodrigues, A. R., Van Soesbergen, A., Sihvonen, H., Seager, A., Swindell, L., Vukelic, M., ... Butchart, S. H. M. (2024). Global Metrics for Terrestrial Biodiversity. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 49(1), 673–709. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-121522-045106>
- Business and Biodiversity. (2022, September 12). *Practical guide on biodiversity for SMEs in the agri-foodsector*. One Planet Network. <https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/knowledge-centre/resources/practical-guide-biodiversity-smes-agri-foodsector>
- Business for Nature. (n.d.-a). *More than 1,500 companies with revenues of more than US\$ 7.5 trillion are calling on governments to adopt policies now to reverse nature loss in this decade*. Retrieved 10 September 2025, from <https://www.businessfornature.org/call-to-action>
- Business for Nature. (n.d.-b). *Sector Actions Towards a Nature-Positive Future*. Retrieved 12 July 2024, from <https://www.businessfornature.org/sector-actions>

- Business for Nature. (2024). *Advocating for Nature: A guide for responsible policy engagement*.
https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d777de8109c315fd22faf3a/t/65a01ba49b978562b9977975/1704991660953/Business+Guide+-+Responsible+Policy+Engagement+on+Nature_FINAL.pdf
- Business for Nature, & Accenture. (2023). *Fashion and Apparel: Priority actions towards a nature-positive future*.
https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d777de8109c315fd22faf3a/t/65e6d2b303d0046ded0844fe/1709626044517/Fashion_Full+Report.pdf
- Business for Nature, Capital Coalition, & CDP. (2022). *Make It Mandatory: The case for mandatory corporate assessment and disclosure on nature*. https://capitalscoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/MakeitMandatoryReport_final.pdf
- Campbell, T., Dixon, K. W., Bradshaw, S. D., Gann, G. D., Hartley, W., Lambers, H., & Wardell-Johnson, G. (2024). Standards-based evaluation inform ecological restoration outcomes for a major mining activity in a global biodiversity hotspot. *Restoration Ecology*, 32(8), e14236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.14236>
- Cardenas, I. C., & Halman, J. I. M. (2016). Coping with uncertainty in environmental impact assessments: Open techniques. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 60, 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2016.02.006>
- Carlson, K. M., Curran, L. M., Ratnasari, D., Pittman, A. M., Soares-Filho, B. S., Asner, G. P., Trigg, S. N., Gaveau, D. A., Lawrence, D., & Rodrigues, H. O. (2012). Committed carbon emissions, deforestation, and community land conversion from oil palm plantation expansion in West Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(19), 7559–7564. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1200452109>
- Carvajal, A., & Didier. (2024, September). *Boosting SME Finance for Growth*. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/6de94c67-e8a1-4cf0-871b-3ed4d5a8f046/content>
- Carvalho, S. H. C. D., Cojoianu, T., & Ascui, F. (2023). From impacts to dependencies: A first global assessment of corporate biodiversity risk exposure and responses. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(5), 2600–2614. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3142>
- Cassar, L. (2019). Job Mission as a Substitute for Monetary Incentives: Benefits and Limits. *Management Science*, 65(2), 896–912. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2017.2903>
- Cassar, L., & Meier, S. (2018). Nonmonetary Incentives and the Implications of Work as a Source of Meaning. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 32(3), 215–238. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.32.3.215>
- CBD. (2022). *Decision Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity. 15/4. Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>
- CDP. (n.d.). *Request Data*. Retrieved <https://www.cdp.net/en/request-data>
- Chang, O. H., & Slaubaugh, M. D. (2017). Sustainable Business Practices in the United States: A Survey on Implementation. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 7(3), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jms.v7n3p1>
- Chaudhary, S., & Klug, Arne Philipp. (2023). *Biodiversity and Business: Are Companies Aware of Nature's Risks?* MSCI. <https://www.msci.com/www/blog-posts/biodiversity-and-business-are/04081554185>
- Chen, F., Chen, M., Cong, L., Gao, H., & Ponticelli, J. (2025, July). *PRICING THE PRICELESS: THE FINANCIAL COST OF BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION*. https://www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w32743/w32743.pdf

- Chesbrough, H. (2002). The role of the business model in capturing value from innovation: Evidence from Xerox Corporation's technology spin-off companies. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 11(3), 529–555. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/11.3.529>
- Choi, Y., & Yu, Y. (2014). The Influence of Perceived Corporate Sustainability Practices on Employees and Organizational Performance. *Sustainability*, 6(1), 348–364. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su6010348>
- Clark, G. L., & Hebb, T. (2004). Pension Fund Corporate Engagement: The Fifth Stage of Capitalism. *Relations Industrielles*, 59(1), 142–171. <https://doi.org/10.7202/009130ar>
- Clément, A., & Grenon, G. (2025). Mapping biodiversity risk metrics in finance: A comparative analysis of MSCI and LSEG using the ENCORE framework. *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Accounting*, 7, 100020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.josfa.2025.100020>
- Clift, R., Sim, S., King, H., Chenoweth, J., Christie, I., Clavreul, J., Mueller, C., Posthuma, L., Boulay, A.-M., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Chatterton, J., DeClerck, F., Druckman, A., France, C., Franco, A., Gerten, D., Goedkoop, M., Hauschild, M., Huijbregts, M., ... Murphy, R. (2017). The Challenges of Applying Planetary Boundaries as a Basis for Strategic Decision-Making in Companies with Global Supply Chains. *Sustainability*, 9(2), 279. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9020279>
- Conservation Finance Alliance. (2014). *Supporting Biodiversity Conservation Ventures: Assessing the Impact Investing Sector for an Investment Strategy to Support Environmental Entrepreneurism* (p. 37). Conservation Finance Alliance. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/57e1f17b37c58156a98f1ee4/t/5d13bc499993cf0001faf63c/1561574481958/Impact+Investing+for+Biodiversity+Donlan+2014.pdf>
- Cook, A. S. C. P., Humphreys, E. M., Bennet, F., Masden, E. A., & Burton, N. H. K. (2018). Quantifying avian avoidance of offshore wind turbines: Current evidence and key knowledge gaps. *Marine Environmental Research*, 140, 278–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2018.06.017>
- Coqueret, G., Giroux, T., & Zerbib, O. D. (2025). The biodiversity premium. *Ecological Economics*, 228, 108435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108435>
- Coral Triangle Initiative on Coral Reefs, Fisheries and Food Security (CTI-CFF). (n.d.). *Coral Triangle Initiative (CTI-CFF)*. Retrieved <https://www.coraltriangleinitiative.org/>
- Cosimo, L. H. E., Masiero, M., Mammadova, A., & Pettenella, D. (2024). Voluntary sustainability standards to cope with the new European Union regulation on deforestation-free products: A gap analysis. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 164, 103235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103235>
- Cousins, P. D., Lawson, B., Petersen, K. J., & Fugate, B. (2019). Investigating green supply chain management practices and performance: The moderating roles of supply chain ecocentricity and traceability. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 39(5), 767–786. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-11-2018-0676>
- Cramb, R., & McCarthy, J. F. (Eds). (2016). *The Oil Palm Complex: Smallholders, Agribusiness and the State in Indonesia and Malaysia*. NUS Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1xz0km>
- Crona, B., Wassénus, E., Parlato, G., & Kashyap, S. (2024). *Doing Business Within Planetary Boundaries*. Stockholm Resilience Centre (Stockholm University) and the Beijer Institute of Ecological Economics (Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences). <https://www.stockholmresilience.org/download/18.70974969192bd3915f9a117/1730893682320/Doing%20business%20within%20Planetary%20Boundaries.pdf>
- CSRD. (2024). *Reporting guide*. <https://go.quentic.com/docs/uk/csr-reporting-guide>

- Das, A., & Bocken, N. (2024). Regenerative business strategies: A database and typology to inspire business experimentation towards sustainability. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 49, 529–544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.06.024>
- Dasgupta, P. (2021). *The Economics of Biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review*. HM Treasury. <https://bibliotecadigital.ciren.cl/handle/20.500.13082/32687>
- Dawson, N. M., Coolsaet, B., Sterling, E. J., Loveridge, R., Gross-Camp, N. D., Wongbusarakum, S., Sangha, K. K., Scherl, L. M., Phan, H. P., Zafra-Calvo, N., Lavey, W. G., Byakagaba, P., Idrobo, C. J., Chenet, A., Bennett, N. J., Mansourian, S., & Rosado-May, F. J. (2021). The role of Indigenous peoples and local communities in effective and equitable conservation. *Ecology and Society*, 26(3), art19. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12625-260319>
- Declerck, M., Trifonova, N., Hartley, J., & Scott, B. E. (2023). Cumulative effects of offshore renewables: From pragmatic policies to holistic marine spatial planning tools. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 101, 107153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2023.107153>
- Delmas, M. A., & Burbano, V. C. (2011). The Drivers of Greenwashing. *California Management Review*, 54(1), 64–87. <https://doi.org/10.1525/cmr.2011.54.1.64>
- Dempsey, J. (2013). Biodiversity loss as material risk: Tracking the changing meanings and materialities of biodiversity conservation. *Geoforum, Risky Natures, Natures of Risk*, 45, 41–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2012.04.002>
- Department of Environmental Affairs of Republic of South Africa. (2014). *Traditional Knowledge Associated with Rooibos and honeybush Species in South Africa*. <https://naturaljustice.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/Traditional-Knowledge-Rooibos-Honeybush-Species-SA.pdf>
- Devenish, K., Desbureaux, S., Willcock, S., & Jones, J. P. G. (2022). On track to achieve no net loss of forest at Madagascar's biggest mine. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(6), 498–508. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00850-7>
- Dixon, C., Eis, J., & Gorst, A. (2022). *Nature risk is the next challenge that demands a global solution*. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/sustainability/our-insights/sustainability-blog/nature-risk-is-the-next-challenge-that-demands-a-global-solution>
- Du, S., Bhattacharya, C. B., & Sen, S. (2010). Maximizing Business Returns to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): The Role of CSR Communication. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 12(1), 8–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2009.00276.x>
- Ducros, A., & Steele, P. (2022). *Biocredits to finance nature and people: Emerging lessons*. IIED. <https://iied.org/sites/default/files/pdfs/2022-11/21216IIED.pdf>
- Dudgeon, D., Arthington, A. H., Gessner, M. O., Kawabata, Z., Knowler, D. J., Lévêque, C., Naiman, R. J., Prieur-Richard, A., Soto, D., Stiassny, M. L. J., & Sullivan, C. A. (2006). Freshwater biodiversity: Importance, threats, status and conservation challenges. *Biological Reviews*, 81(2), 163–182. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1464793105006950>
- Durrani, N., Raziq, A., Mahmood, T., & Khan, M. R. (2024). Barriers to adaptation of environmental sustainability in SMEs: A qualitative study. *PLOS ONE*, 19(5), e0298580. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0298580>
- Dzhengiz, T., & Niesten, E. (2020a). Competences for Environmental Sustainability: A Systematic Review on the Impact of Absorptive Capacity and Capabilities. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 162(4), 881–906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04360-z>
- Dzhengiz, T., & Niesten, E. (2020b). Competences for Environmental Sustainability: A Systematic Review on the Impact of Absorptive Capacity and Capabilities. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 162(4), 881–906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04360-z>

- Earth Security. (2021). *The Blended Finance Playbook for Nature-Based Solutions* (p. 26). Earth Security. <https://www.convergence.finance/resource/the-blended-finance-playbook-for-nature-based-solutions/view>
- EcoEnterprises Fund. (2025). *An Investment Fund for Nature*. <https://ecoenterprisesfund.com/>
- EFRAG. (2022). *ESRS E4 Biodiversity and Ecosystems*. https://www.efrag.org/Assets/Download?assetUrl=%2Fsites%2Fwebpublishing%2FSiteAssets%2FED_ESRS_E4.pdf&AspxAutoDetectCookieSupport=1
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (n.d.-a). *Examples of the circular economy in design*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-design/examples>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (n.d.-b). *What is the meaning of a circular economy and what are the main principles?* Circular Economy Introduction. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/topics/circular-economy-introduction/overview>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2021). *The Nature Imperative: How the circular economy tackles biodiversity loss*. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/biodiversity-report>
- Elsayed, R. A. A. (2023). Exploring the financial consequences of biodiversity disclosure: How does biodiversity disclosure affect firms' financial performance? *Future Business Journal*, 9(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00202-7>
- Englund, O., & Berndes, G. (2015). How do sustainability standards consider biodiversity? *WIREs Energy and Environment*, 4(1), 26–50. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.118>
- Eosta. (2018). *True Cost Accounting for Food, Farming and Finance*. Eosta, with SoCiLA (Social Innovation in Latin America). <https://www.socila.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/2018/01/True-Cost-Accounting-for-Food-Farming-and-Finance.pdf>
- Eosta. (2025). *Nature & More Transparency System*. <https://eosta.com/en/nature-more/transparency-system>
- Equator Principles Association. (2024). *Equator Principles Financial Institutions (EPFIs) Reporting*. <https://equator-principles.com/signatories-epfis-reporting/>
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Nature Restoration Law*. European Commission. Retrieved 10 July 2024, from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/nature-restoration-law_en
- European Union. (2024). *DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL ON CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY DUE DILIGENCE AND AMENDING DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1937 AND REGULATION (EU) 2023/2859*. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CONSIL:PE_9_2024_REV_1
- Fairphone. (2024). *Fairphone's Impact 2024*. https://www.fairphone.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Fairphone-Impact_Report-27-May.pdf
- Fauna and Flora International. (2021). *Coordinated and collaborative application of the mitigation hierarchy in complex multi-use landscapes in Africa. Supplementary resource: Applying the mitigation hierarchy at the landscape level*. https://www.fauna-flora.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/FFI_CALM_Supplementary_Resource_Applying-the-MH-at-the-landscape-level_ENG.pdf
- Feger, C. ement, & Mermet, L. (2020). New Business Models for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Management Services: Action Research With a Large Environmental Sector Company. *Organization & Environment*, 35(2), 252–281.
- Fenster, T. L. D., Oikawa, P. Y., & Lundgren, J. G. (2021). Regenerative Almond Production Systems Improve Soil Health, Biodiversity, and Profit. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 664359. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.664359>

- Finance for Biodiversity Foundation. (n.d.). *About the Pledge*. Retrieved <https://www.financeforbiodiversity.org/about-the-pledge/>
- Finance for Biodiversity Foundation. (2022). *Finance for Biodiversity Guide on engagement with companies*. https://www.financeforbiodiversity.org/wp-content/uploads/Finance-for-Biodiversity_Guide-on-engagement-with-companies_Dec2022.pdf
- Finance for Nature. (n.d.). *Finance for Nature – Resources*. Retrieved <https://financefornature.unep.org/resources>
- Fitzgerald, K. H. (2021). *Collaborative Management Partnerships for Protected Areas: A Resource Guide*. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/global-wildlife-program>
- Flammer, C., Giroux, T., & Heal, G. M. (2025). Biodiversity finance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, *164*, 103987. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2024.103987>
- Folke, C., Österblom, H., Jouffray, J.-B., Lambin, E. F., Adger, W. N., Scheffer, M., Crona, B. I., Nyström, M., Levin, S. A., Carpenter, S. R., Anderies, J. M., Chapin, S., Crépin, A.-S., Dauriach, A., Galaz, V., Gordon, L. J., Kautsky, N., Walker, B. H., Watson, J. R., ... de Zeeuw, A. (2019). Transnational corporations and the challenge of biosphere stewardship. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, *3*(10), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0978-z>
- Folke, C., Polasky, S., Rockström, J., Galaz, V., Westley, F., Lamont, M., Scheffer, M., Österblom, H., Carpenter, S. R., Chapin, F. S., Seto, K. C., Weber, E. U., Crona, B. I., Daily, G. C., Dasgupta, P., Gaffney, O., Gordon, L. J., Hoff, H., Levin, S. A., ... Walker, B. H. (2021). Our future in the Anthropocene biosphere. *Ambio*, *50*(4), 834–869. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01544-8>
- Franks, D. M., Segura-Salazar, J., Gallagher, L., Ekubatsion, L. H., Bioantika, Golev, A., Stringer, M., Rogers, P., Soto-Diaz, J., Ardhanari, M., Antonio, C., & Staines, L. (2025). Nose to tail mining: A circular solution for sand supply and tailings reduction at scale. *One Earth*, *8*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101198>
- Freeman, R. E., Martin, K., & Parmar, B. (2007). Stakeholder Capitalism. *Journal of Business Ethics*, *74*(4), 303–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9517-y>
- Gann, G. D., McDonald, T., Walder, B., Aronson, J., Nelson, C. R., Jonson, J., Hallett, J. G., Eisenberg, C., Guariguata, M. R., Liu, J., Hua, F., Echeverría, C., Gonzales, E., Shaw, N., Decler, K., & Dixon, K. W. (2019). International principles and standards for the practice of ecological restoration. Second edition. *Restoration Ecology*, *27*(S1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13035>
- Gardner, T. A., Von Hase, A., Brownlie, S., Ekstrom, J. M. M., Pilgrim, J. D., Savy, C. E., Stephens, R. T. T., Treweek, J., Ussher, G. T., Ward, G., & Ten Kate, K. (2013). Biodiversity Offsets and the Challenge of Achieving No Net Loss. *Conservation Biology*, *27*(6), 1254–1264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12118>
- Gartenberg, C., & Serafeim, G. (2023). Corporate Purpose in Public and Private Firms. *Management Science*, *69*(9), 5087–5111. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2022.4618>
- GEFI. (n.d.). *Investing: Divestment versus Engagement*. Retrieved 8 October 2025, from <https://www.globalethicalfinance.org/2023/07/06/investing-divestment-versus-engagement/>
- Gehman, J., Lefsrud, L. M., & Fast, S. (2017). Social license to operate: Legitimacy by another name? *Canadian Public Administration*, *60*(2), 293–317. <https://doi.org/10.1111/capa.12218>
- Getahun, S., Kefale, H., & Gelaye, Y. (2024). Application of Precision Agriculture Technologies for Sustainable Crop Production and Environmental Sustainability: A Systematic Review. *The Scientific World Journal*, *2024*(1), 2126734. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/2126734>
- Ghijssels, D., Matthysen, E., & Honnay, O. (2026). Beyond compliance: Strengthening mitigation hierarchy implementation in environmental impact assessment practice. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, *116*, 108134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2025.108134>

- Gibbons, P., Evans, M. C., Maron, M., Gordon, A., Le Roux, D., Von Hase, A., Lindenmayer, D. B., & Possingham, H. P. (2016). A Loss-Gain Calculator for Biodiversity Offsets and the Circumstances in Which No Net Loss Is Feasible: When no net loss is feasible. *Conservation Letters*, 9(4), 252–259. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12206>
- Gibbs, H. K., Rausch, L., Munger, J., Schelly, I., Morton, D. C., Noojipady, P., Soares-Filho, B., Barreto, P., Micol, L., & Walker, N. F. (2015). Brazil's Soy Moratorium. *Science*, 347(6220), 377–378. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa0181>
- Global Standard on Corporate Climate Lobbying. (2022). *The global standard*. <https://climate-lobbying.com/apply-global-standard/>
- Gomez-Trujillo, A. M., Velez-Ocampo, J., & Gonzalez-Perez, M. A. (2020). A literature review on the causality between sustainability and corporate reputation: What goes first? *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 31(2), 406–430. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-09-2019-0207>
- Gontier, M., Balfors, B., & Mörtberg, U. (2006). Biodiversity in environmental assessment—Current practice and tools for prediction. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 26(3), 268–286.
- Google. (2023). *Environmental Report*. <https://www.gstatic.com/gumdrop/sustainability/google-2023-environmental-report.pdf>
- Gossen, M., Ziesemer, F., & Schrader, U. (2019). Why and How Commercial Marketing Should Promote Sufficient Consumption: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 39(3), 252–269. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0276146719866238>
- Graafland, J., & Van De Ven, B. (2006). Strategic and Moral Motivation for Corporate Social Responsibility. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 2006(22), 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.9774/GLEAF.4700.2006.su.00012>
- Great Barrier Reef Foundation. (n.d.). *Reef Trust Partnership*. Retrieved 10 September 2025, from <https://www.barrierreef.org/what-we-do/reef-trust-partnership>
- Greening, D. W., & Turban, D. B. (2000). Corporate Social Performance As a Competitive Advantage in Attracting a Quality Workforce. *Business & Society*, 39(3), 254–280. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000765030003900302>
- GRI. (2024). *GRI 101: Biodiversity 2024*. Global Reporting Initiative. <https://www.globalreporting.org/standards/standards-development/topic-standard-project-for-biodiversity/>
- Griffiths, V. F., Bull, J. W., Baker, J., & Milner-Gulland, E. j. (2019). No net loss for people and biodiversity. *Conservation Biology*, 33(1), 76–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13184>
- Grupo de Trabalho da Soja (GTS), ABIOVE, & ANEC. (2023). *Soy Moratorium: Report of the 2022/23 Crop Year*. Grupo de Trabalho da Soja. <https://abiove.org.br/en/publications/>
- Guleria, C., & Gautam, K. (2021). *NTFPs a key Tribal Livelihood Source: A Case of Tendu Leaves*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352904181_NTFPs_a_key_Tribal_Livelihood_Source_a_Case_of_Tendu_Leaves
- Gully, S. M., Phillips, J. M., Castellano, W. G., Han, K., & Kim, A. (2013). A Mediated Moderation Model of Recruiting Socially and Environmentally Responsible Job Applicants. *Personnel Psychology*, 66(4), 935–973. <https://doi.org/10.1111/peps.12033>
- Haffar, M., & Searcy, C. (2018). Target-setting for ecological resilience: Are companies setting environmental sustainability targets in line with planetary thresholds? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(7), 1079–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2053>
- Hahn, T., Pinkse, J., Preuss, L., & Figge, F. (2015). Tensions in Corporate Sustainability: Towards an Integrative Framework. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 127(2), 297–316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2047-5>

- Hahn, T., & Tampe, M. (2021). Strategies for regenerative business. *Strategic Organization*, 19(3), 456–477. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476127020979228>
- Harrell, A. (2025, May). *Material World: Celebrate Biological Diversity Day With Carp Couture*. <https://sourcingjournal.com/sustainability/sustainability-materials/material-world-un-international-biological-diversity-day-1234748865/>
- Hassan, A., Roberts, L., & Rodger, K. (2022). Corporate accountability for biodiversity and species extinction: Evidence from organisations reporting on their impacts on nature. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(1), 326–352. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2890>
- Hawkins, F., Beatty, C. R., Brooks, T. M., Church, R., Elliott, W., Kiss, E., Macfarlane, N. B. W., Pugliesi, J., Schipper, A. M., & Walsh, M. (2023). Bottom-up global biodiversity metrics needed for businesses to assess and manage their impact. *Conservation Biology*, n/a(n/a), e14183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14183>
- Hedblom, D., Hickman, B., & List, J. (2019, September). *Toward an Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility: Theory and Field Experimental Evidence*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3450248
- Heilmayr, R., Rausch, L. L., Munger, J., & Gibbs, H. K. (2020). Brazil's Amazon Soy Moratorium reduced deforestation. *Nature Food*, 1(12), 801–810. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-020-00194-5>
- Heinrich, M., Scotti, F., Andrade-Cetto, A., Berger-Gonzalez, M., Echeverría, J., Friso, F., Garcia-Cardona, F., Hesketh, A., Hitziger, M., Maake, C., Politi, M., Spadafora, C., & Spadafora, R. (2020). Access and Benefit Sharing Under the Nagoya Protocol—Quo Vadis? Six Latin American Case Studies Assessing Opportunities and Risk. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, 765. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.00765>
- Henders, S., Persson, U. M., & Kastner, T. (2015). Trading forests: Land-use change and carbon emissions embodied in production and exports of forest-risk commodities. *Environmental Research Letters*, 10(12), 125012. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/12/125012>
- Higgins, K. (2024). *Privium Fund Management launches new biodiversity impact fund*. Impact Investor. <https://impact-investor.com/privium-fund-management-launches-new-biodiversity-impact-fund/>
- High Conservation Value (HCV) Network. (n.d.). *The HCV Approach*. Retrieved <https://www.hcvnetwork.org/hcv-approach>
- Hoejmose, S. U., Grosvold, J., & Millington, A. (2014). The effect of institutional pressure on cooperative and coercive 'green' supply chain practices. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 20(4), 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2014.07.002>
- Hou Jones, X., Macqueen, D., del Prado Nieto, I. N., Sorsby, N., & Duffy, J. (2024). *Business unusual: How business and investment pioneers are transforming forest and food supply chains*. IIED. <https://www.iied.org/22396iied>
- Hoyle, D., Zrust, M., Aritonang, S., & Crawshaw, J. (2018). *The HCS Approach Toolkit, Module 3. High Carbon Stock Approach (HCSA) Steering Group*. <https://highcarbonstock.org/the-hcs-approach-toolkit/>
- Hulme, P. E. (2009). Trade, transport and trouble: Managing invasive species pathways in an era of globalization. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 46(1), 10–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2008.01600.x>
- Human Rights and Biodiversity Working Group. (2024). *From Agreements to Actions*. <https://swed.bio/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/From-Agreements-to-Actions-A-guide-to-applying-a-human-rights-based-approach-to-the-Kunming-Montreal-Global-Biodiversity-Framework.pdf>

- Hundloe, T. (2021). EIA Laws and Policies: From NEPA to the World. In T. Hundloe, *Environmental Impact Assessment* (pp. 81–98). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80942-3_4
- IAIA IEA. (1999). *Principles of Environmental Impact Assessment Best Practice*.
<https://iaia.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/BEST-PRACTICE-Principles-of-EIA.pdf>
- IAPB. (2024, October). *Framework for high integrity biodiversity credit markets*.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fY8EfmEfAr7zeL2d59vuZhiuiwc8xQaw/view>
- IEA. (2023). *World Energy Outlook 2023*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023>
- IFC. (2007). *Stakeholder Engagement: A Good Practice Handbook for Companies Doing Business in Emerging Markets*. International Finance Corporation.
https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/topics_ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/sustainability-at-ifc/publications/publications_handbook_stakeholderengagement_wci_1319577185063
- IFC. (2012a). *Performance Standard 6 Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources*. <https://www.ifc.org/content/dam/ifc/doc/2010/2012-ifc-performance-standard-6-en.pdf>
- IFC. (2012b). *Performance Standard 7: Indigenous Peoples* (No. 7; Performance Standard, p. 8). International Finance Corporation.
https://www.ifc.org/wps/wcm/connect/topics_ext_content/ifc_external_corporate_site/sustainability-at-ifc/policies-standards/performance-standards/ps7
- IFC. (2019). *International Finance Corporation's Guidance Note 6: Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources*. International Finance Corporation's Guidance Note 6: Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources
- Ingram, J. C., McKenzie, E. J., Bagstad, K. J., Finisdore, J., Van Den Berg, R., Fenichel, E., Vardon, M., Posner, S., Santamaria, M., Mandle, L., Barker, R., & Spurgeon, J. (2024). Leveraging natural capital accounting to support businesses with nature-related risk assessments and disclosures. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 379(1903), 20220328. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2022.0328>
- Innovation Forum. (2025, May). *EUDR's High-risk quartet*.
<https://www.innovationforum.co.uk/articles/eudr-s-high-risk-quartet>
- International Finance Corporation (IFC). (2025). *IFC and IDB Invest Forge Partnership with Itaú Unibanco to First Sustainability and Social Bond*. World Bank Group.
<https://www.ifc.org/en/pressroom/2025/ifc-idb-invest-forge-partnership-with-itaú-to-first-sustainability-and-social-bond>
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (n.d.). *ISO 14000 family Environmental Management*. Retrieved 26 September 2025, from
<https://www.iso.org/standards/popular/iso-14000-family>
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2025). *ISO 17620. Biodiversity—Process for designing and implementing biodiversity net gain in development projects*.
<https://www.iso.org/standard/84992.html>
- Inversa. (n.d.). *Nurturing ecosystems and economies for immediate and measurable impact*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://www.inversaleathers.com/impact>
- IPBES. (2019a). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3831673>
- IPBES (with Díaz, S., Settele, J., Brondízio, E. S., Ngo, H. T., Guèze, M., Agard, J., Arneth, A., Balvanera, P., Brauman, K. A., S. H. M. Butchart, Chan, K. M. A., L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii

- J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, Midgley, G. F., Miloslavich, P., Molnár, Z., Obura, D., Pfaff, A., ... Zayas, C. N.). (2019b). *Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services* (Version summary for policy makers). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3553579>
- IPBES (with Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., & González-Jiménez, D.). (2022). *Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6522522>
- IPBES. (2024a). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Full report* (Version 4.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11382215>
- IPBES (with McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Harmáčková, Z., Hayman, D. T. S., Herrero, M., Kumar, R., Ley, D., Mangalagu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Pengue, W. A., Prist, P. R., Ricketts, T. H., Rounsevell, M. D. A., ... Obura, D.). (2024b). *Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13850290>
- IPIECA. (2015). *A Cross-Sector Guide for Omlplementing the Mitigation Hierarchy*. Koninklijke Brill NV. <https://primarysources.brillonline.com/browse/climate-change-and-law-collection/a-crosssector-guide-for-implementing-the-mitigation-hierarchy;cccc001320150013003>
- Irvine-Broque, A., & Dempsey, J. (2023). Risky business: Protecting nature, protecting wealth? *Conservation Letters*, 16(4), e12969. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12969>
- ISEAL. (2021). *ISEAL Credibility Principles. Version 2*. https://www.isealalliance.org/sites/default/files/resource/2021-06/ISEAL-Credibility-Principles-V2-2021_EN_ISEAL_June-21.pdf
- IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature. (2020). *IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions: A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS: first edition* (1st edn). IUCN, International Union for Conservation of Nature. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.08.en>
- Jain, Y. K., Bhardwaj, P., Joshi, N. K., Lal, P., Singh, R. J., Pandey, A. K., & Kapoor, S. (2024). Estimating the annual production data of bidi sticks in India using the “back-of-the-envelope-method”. *Data in Brief*, 56, 110782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.110782>
- Jay, S., Jones, C., Slinn, P., & Wood, C. (2007). Environmental impact assessment: Retrospect and prospect. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 27(4), 287–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2006.12.001>
- Jia, F., Zuluaga-Cardona, L., Bailey, A., & Rueda, X. (2018). Sustainable supply chain management in developing countries: An analysis of the literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 189, 263–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.248>
- Johnston, A., Thaxter, C. B., Austin, G. E., Cook, A. S. C. P., Humphreys, E. M., Still, D. A., Mackay, A., Irvine, R., Webb, A., & Burton, N. H. K. (2015). Modelling the abundance and distribution of marine birds accounting for uncertain species identification. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52(1), 150–160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12364>
- Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, S., Boelee, E., Cools, J., Van Hoof, L., Hospes, O., Kok, M., Peerlings, J., Van Tatenhove, J., Termeer, C. J. A. M., & Visseren-Hamakers, I. J. (2018). Identifying barriers and levers of biodiversity mainstreaming in four cases of transnational governance of land and water. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 85, 132–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.03.011>

- Kedward, K., Ryan-Collins, J., & Chenet, H. (2020). Managing Nature-Related Financial Risks: A Precautionary Policy Approach for Central Banks and Financial Supervisors. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3726637>
- Kennedy, C. M., Fariss, B., Oakleaf, J. R., Garnett, S. T., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Fa, J. E., Baruch-Mordo, S., & Kiesecker, J. (2023). Indigenous Peoples' lands are threatened by industrial development; conversion risk assessment reveals need to support Indigenous stewardship. *One Earth*, 6(8), 1032–1049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.07.006>
- Kletz, T. A. (2005). Looking Beyond ALARP. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 83(2), 81–84. <https://doi.org/10.1205/psep.04227>
- Kolenova, Z., Boulocher-Passet, V., & Farache, F. (2025). Using Country of Origin (COO) as an Internationalization Branding Strategy. In V. Boulocher-Passet, *International Marketing in Practice* (1st edn, pp. 117–126). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032713007-17>
- Konietzko, J., Bocken, N., & Hultink, E. J. (2020). A Tool to Analyze, Ideate and Develop Circular Innovation Ecosystems. *Sustainability*, 12(1), 417. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12010417>
- Krause, M. S., Droste, N., & Matzdorf, B. (2021). What makes businesses commit to nature conservation? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(2), 741–755. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2650>
- Krueger, P., Metzger, D., & Wu, J. (2020, November 9). *The Sustainability Wage Gap*. Swiss Finance Institute. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3672492
- Kvam, R. (2019). *Meaningful Stakeholder Engagement: A Joint Publication of the MFI Working Group on Environmental and Social Standards*. Inter-American Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0001990>
- Kwon, T., Panulo, B., McCallum, S., Ivankovik, K., & Essa, Z. (2022). *Blended Finance: When to Use Which Instrument?* (p. 72). Initiative for Blended Finance, University of Zurich. https://ibf-uzh.ch/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Blended-Finance_When-To-Use-Each-Instrument_Phase-1-final.pdf
- Lambin, E. F., & Thorlakson, T. (2018). Sustainability Standards: Interactions Between Private Actors, Civil Society, and Governments. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 43(1), 369–393. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-102017-025931>
- Lambooy, T., & Levashova, Y. (2011). Opportunities and challenges for private sector entrepreneurship and investment in biodiversity, ecosystem services and nature conservation. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management*, 7(4), 301–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2011.629632>
- Lamont, T. A. C., Barlow, J., Bebbington, J., Cuckston, T., Djohani, R., Garrett, R., Jones, H. P., Razak, T. B., & Graham, N. A. J. (2023). Hold big business to task on ecosystem restoration. *Science*, 381(6662), 1053–1055. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adh2610>
- Langhammer, P. F., Bull, J. W., Bicknell, J. E., Oakley, J. L., Brown, M. H., Bruford, M. W., Butchart, S. H. M., Carr, J. A., Church, D., Cooney, R., Cutajar, S., Foden, W., Foster, M. N., Gascon, C., Geldmann, J., Genovesi, P., Hoffmann, M., Howard-McCombe, J., Lewis, T., ... Brooks, T. M. (2024). The positive impact of conservation action. *Science*, 384(6694), 453–458. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adj6598>
- Lankes, H. P. (2021). *Blended Finance for Scaling up Climate and Nature Investments: Report of the One Planet Lab* (p. 50). Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment, London School of Economics and Political Science. <https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Blended-Finance-for-Scaling-Up-Climate-and-Nature-Investments-1.pdf>

- Law Society of South Africa. (2021). *Rooibos: Revealing the road to traditional knowledge protection*.
<https://www.derebus.org.za/rooibos-revealing-the-road-to-traditional-knowledge-protection/>
- Lawrence, P. (2023). Transnational Corporations and Globalisation: The Development of Development? In M. Tribe & G. Kararach (Eds), *The Political Economy of Global Manufacturing, Business and Finance* (pp. 173–195). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25832-9_8
- Leclère, D., Obersteiner, M., Barrett, M., Butchart, S. H. M., Chaudhary, A., De Palma, A., DeClerck, F. A. J., Di Marco, M., Doelman, J. C., Dürauer, M., Freeman, R., Harfoot, M., Hasegawa, T., Hellweg, S., Hilbers, J. P., Hill, S. L. L., Humpenöder, F., Jennings, N., Krisztin, T., ... Young, L. (2020). Bending the curve of terrestrial biodiversity needs an integrated strategy. *Nature*, 585(7826), 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2705-y>
- Lee, H. S., Salas, J. M., Shen, K., & Yang, K. (2024). The effect of bond ownership structure on ESG performance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 89, 102678.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2024.102678>
- Lee, L., & Chen, L. (2018). Boosting employee retention through CSR: A configurational analysis. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 25(5), 948–960.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1511>
- Lee, S., & Klassen, R. D. (2008). Drivers and Enablers That Foster Environmental Management Capabilities in Small- and Medium-Sized Suppliers in Supply Chains. *Production and Operations Management*, 17(6), 573–586. <https://doi.org/10.3401/poms.1080.0063>
- Lele, S., Ramanujam, V., & Rai. (2015). Co-operative procurement and marketing of tendu leaves in Madhya Pradesh: Image and reality. *Environment and Development Discussion Paper No. 3*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235356241_Co-operative_procurement_and_marketing_of_tendu_leaves_in_Madhya_Pradesh_Image_and_reality
- Levi Strauss & Co. (2019). *2025 Water Action Strategy*.
- Levy, S. A., Cammelli, F., Munger, J., Gibbs, H. K., & Garrett, R. D. (2023). Deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon could be halved by scaling up the implementation of zero-deforestation cattle commitments. *Global Environmental Change*, 80, 102671.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102671>
- Li, J., & Wu, D. (Andrew). (2020). Do Corporate Social Responsibility Engagements Lead to Real Environmental, Social, and Governance Impact? *Management Science*, 66(6), 2564–2588.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2019.3324>
- Liu, Q., Süring, C. M., Thorsen, B. J., Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Strange, N., Wunder, S., Bull, J. W., Lagerkvist, C., & Lundhede, T. (2025). A Scoping Review of Determinants of Business Engagement With Biodiversity. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 32(4), 5540–5556. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.3249>
- Locke, H., Rockström, J., Bakker, P., Bapna, M., Gough, M., Lambertini, M., Morris, J., Polman, P., Samper, C., Sanjayan, M., Zabey, E., & Zurita, P. (2021). *A Nature-Positive World: The Global Goal for Nature*. 21.
- Lozano, R. (2015). A Holistic Perspective on Corporate Sustainability Drivers. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 22(1), 32–44.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1325>
- LSE. (2023). *What are sustainability-linked bonds and how can they help developing countries?*
<https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/explainers/what-are-sustainability-linked-bonds-and-how-can-they-help-developing-countries/>

- Ludwig, P., & Sassen, R. (2022). Which internal corporate governance mechanisms drive corporate sustainability? *Journal of Environmental Management*, 301, 113780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113780>
- Lumme, M., Nahi, T., & Gouw, B. (2023). *People and Planet in Business: A Simple Guide to How Small and Micro Companies Can Start or Strengthen Their Due Diligence* (p. 24). Fairtrade Centre of Excellence on HREDD and B Lab. <https://www.fairtrade.net/content/dam/fairtrade/global/why-we-do-it/hredd/hredd-pdfs/People-and-planet-HREDD-guide-final.pdf>
- Lyon, T. P., & Montgomery, A. W. (2015). The Means and End of Greenwash. *Organization & Environment*, 28(2), 223–249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086026615575332>
- Ma, D., Rhodes, J., Klein, C. J., & Maron, M. (2023). Redistribution of fishery benefits among commercial and recreational fishers caused by offsetting. *Marine Policy*, 158, 105881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105881>
- Macellari, M., Gusmerotti, N. M., Frey, M., & Testa, F. (2018). Embedding biodiversity and ecosystem services in corporate sustainability: A strategy to enable Sustainable Development Goals. *Business Strategy & Development*, 1(4), 244–255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.34>
- Mair, L., Elnahass, M., Xiang, E., Hawkins, F., Siikamaki, J., Hillis, L., Barrie, S., & McGowan, P. J. K. (2024). Corporate disclosures need a biodiversity outcome focus and regulatory backing to deliver global conservation goals. *Conservation Letters*, 17(4), e13024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.13024>
- Makepa, D. C., & Chihobo, C. H. (2024). Barriers to commercial deployment of biorefineries: A multi-faceted review of obstacles across the innovation chain. *Heliyon*, 10(12), e32649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e32649>
- Mammen, M. (2024). *Integrating biodiversity considerations into corporate strategic decision-making—Incentives and barriers in applying Science-Based Targets for Land in agri-food corporations in European context* [Lund University]. lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/search/publication/9171266
- Marine Stewardship Council. (n.d.). *Certified Sustainable Seafood*. Retrieved 11 September 2025, from <https://www.msc.org/en-us>
- Maron, M., Brownlie, S., Bull, J. W., Evans, M. C., von Hase, A., Quétier, F., Watson, J. E. M., & Gordon, A. (2018). The many meanings of no net loss in environmental policy. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-017-0007-7>
- Maron, M., Quétier, F., Sarmiento, M., ten Kate, K., Evans, M. C., Bull, J. W., Jones, J. P. G., zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Brownlie, S., Treweek, J., & von Hase, A. (2023). ‘Nature positive’ must incorporate, not undermine, the mitigation hierarchy. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02199-2>
- Maron, M., Von Hase, A., Quétier, F., Sonter, L. J., Theis, S., & Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E. (2025). Biodiversity offsets, their effectiveness and their role in a nature positive future. *Nature Reviews Biodiversity*, 1(3), 183–196. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-025-00023-2>
- Marou. (n.d.). *Marou. Our Philosophy*. Retrieved 21 March 2025, from <https://www.marouchocolate.com/pages/our-philosophy>
- Marques, A. T., Batalha, H., Rodrigues, S., Costa, H., Pereira, M. J. R., Fonseca, C., Mascarenhas, M., & Bernardino, J. (2014). Understanding bird collisions at wind farms: An updated review on the causes and possible mitigation strategies. *Biological Conservation*, 179, 40–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.08.017>

- Márquez-García, M., Jacobson, S. K., & Barbosa, O. (2018). Evaluating biodiversity workshops in Chile: Are farmers responding with conservation action? *Environmental Education Research, 24*(12), 1669–1683. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2018.1519065>
- Marquis, C., Toffel, M. W., & Zhou, Y. (2016). Scrutiny, Norms, and Selective Disclosure: A Global Study of Greenwashing. *Organization Science, 27*(2), 483–504. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2015.1039>
- Marshall, D., McCarthy, L., Heavey, C., & McGrath, P. (2015). Environmental and social supply chain management sustainability practices: Construct development and measurement. *Production Planning & Control, 26*(8), 673–690. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2014.963726>
- Martin, A. E., Neave, E., Kirby, P., Drever, C. R., & Johnson, C. A. (2022). Multi-objective optimization can balance trade-offs among boreal caribou, biodiversity, and climate change objectives when conservation hotspots do not overlap. *Scientific Reports, 12*(1), 11895. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-15274-8>
- Marttinen, K., & Kähkönen, A.-K. (2022). Fostering firms' ability to cascade sustainability through multi-tier supply chains: An investigation of power sources. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management, 42*(8), 1146–1172. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-11-2021-0739>
- Mayer, F., & Gereffi, G. (2010). Regulation and Economic Globalization: Prospects and Limits of Private Governance. *Business and Politics, 12*(3), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.2202/1469-3569.1325>
- Mayfield, H. J., Bird, J., Cox, M., Dutson, G., Eyre, T., Raiter, K., Ringma, J., & Maron, M. (2022). Guidelines for selecting an appropriate currency in biodiversity offset transactions. *Journal of Environmental Management, 322*, 116060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116060>
- McElwee, P., Turnout, E., Chiroleu-Assouline, M., Clapp, J., Isenhour, C., Jackson, T., Kelemen, E., Miller, D. C., Rusch, G., Spangenberg, J. H., Waldron, A., Baumgartner, R. J., Bleys, B., Howard, M. W., Mungatana, E., Ngo, H., Ring, I., & Santos, R. (2020). Ensuring a Post-COVID Economic Agenda Tackles Global Biodiversity Loss. *One Earth, 3*(4), 448–461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.09.011>
- McKenzie, E. J., Jones, M., Seega, N., Siikamäki, J., & Vijay, V. (2025). Science and technical priorities for private sector action to address biodiversity loss. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, 380*(1917), 20230208. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0208>
- McQuaid, S., Kooijman, E. D., Rhodes, M.-L., & Cannon, S. M. (2021). Innovating with nature: Factors influencing the success of nature-based enterprises. *Sustainability, 13*(22), 12488.
- Mendonca Severiano, B., Northey, S. A., & Giurco, D. (2025). Mining industry networks influence the diffusion of innovations in the battery minerals sector. *Environmental Research: Infrastructure and Sustainability, 5*(3), 035014. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2634-4505/adf5e1>
- Meqdadi, O., Johnsen, T. E., Johnsen, R. E., & Salmi, A. (2020). Monitoring and mentoring strategies for diffusing sustainability in supply networks. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal, 25*(6), 729–746. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-08-2019-0288>
- Merriman, K. K., Sen, S., Felo, A. J., & Litzky, B. E. (2016). Employees and sustainability: The role of incentives. *Journal of Managerial Psychology, 31*(4), 820–836. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-09-2014-0285>
- Mestad, O. (2020). *Values and Responsibility: The Ethical Framework for the Government Pension Fund Global*. Norwegian Ministry of Finance. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/nou-2020-7/id2701232/>

- Microsoft. (2024). *2024 Environmental Sustainability Report*. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/corporate-responsibility/sustainability/report?msockid=3932a453741c66da0525b02075fc6734>
- Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2022). Don't dilute the term Nature Positive. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 6(9), 1243–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01845-5>
- Milner-Gulland, E. J., Addison, P., Arlidge, W. N. S., Baker, J., Booth, H., Brooks, T., Bull, J. W., Burgass, M. J., Ekstrom, J., Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Fleming, L. V., Grub, H. M. J., Von Hase, A., Hoffmann, M., Hutton, J., Juffe-Bignoli, D., Ten Kate, K., Kiesecker, J., Kumpel, N. F., ... Watson, J. E. M. (2021). Four steps for the Earth: Mainstreaming the post-2020 global biodiversity framework. *One Earth*, 4(1), 75–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.12.011>
- Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment. (2016). *National Policy on Biological Diversity 2016-2025 of Malasia*. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/my/my-nbsap-v2-en.pdf>
- Moog, S., Spicer, A., & Böhm, S. (2015). The Politics of Multi-Stakeholder Initiatives: The Crisis of the Forest Stewardship Council. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 128(3), 469–493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-2033-3>
- Morgan, R. K. (2012). Environmental impact assessment: The state of the art. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 30(1), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2012.661557>
- Morrison-Saunders, A., Arts, J., Nykiel, A., Muir, B., Morgan, R., Fitzpatrick, P., O'Faircheallaigh, C., Fonseca, A., Faith-Ell, C., González, A., Wessels, J.-A., Geißler, G., Sánchez, L., Jha-Thakur, U., Ross, W., & Glasson, J. (2024). Developing international guidance to make impact assessment follow-up happen – reflections on an interactive design process. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 42(5), 470–481. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2024.2421031>
- Morrison-Saunders, A., & Pope, J. (2013). Conceptualising and managing trade-offs in sustainability assessment. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 38, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2012.06.003>
- Mourou, V., Gia, V. D., Thi Huyen, T. D., Le Hong, P., & Gregor, S. (2021). *Marou Cacao Report 2021*. https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0812/6064/2599/files/Marou_cacao_report_2021_120122.pdf?v=1704342842
- Mukherjee, A., Owen, R., Scott, J. M., & Lyon, F. (2024). Financing green innovation startups: A systematic literature review on early-stage SME funding. *Venture Capital*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691066.2024.2410730>
- Mutua, K., Powell-Turner, J., Spiers, M., & Callaghan, J. (2025). An In-Depth Analysis of Barriers to Corporate Sustainability. *Administrative Sciences*, 15(5), 161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci15050161>
- Myers, N. (n.d.). *Perverse Subsidies*. Retrieved 4 September 2025, from <https://www.cbd.int/doc/case-studies/inc/cs-inc-iucn-05-en.pdf>
- Naito, R., Zhao, J., & Chan, K. M. A. (2022). An integrative framework for transformative social change: A case in global wildlife trade. *Sustainability Science*, 17(1), 171–189. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01081-z>
- Narain, D., Teo, H. C., Lechner, A. M., Watson, J. E. M., & Maron, M. (2022). Biodiversity risks and safeguards of China's hydropower financing in Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) countries. *One Earth*, 5(9), 1019–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2022.08.012>
- National Khoisan Council. (2019). *The Khoikhoi Peoples' rooiboos biocultural community protocol*. <https://naturaljustice.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/NJ-Rooibos-BCP-Web.pdf>

- Natural Justice. (2019). *The Rooibos Access and Benefit-sharing Agreement*.
<https://naturaljustice.org/the-rooibos-access-and-benefit-sharing-agreement/>
- Nature Positive Initiative. (2025, January). *Draft State of Nature Metrics for Piloting*.
https://www.naturepositive.org/app/uploads/2025/01/Draft-State-of-Nature-Metrics-for-Piloting_170125.pdf
- Nature Squared. (2024). *Changing the rules of the game Reforming targets, regulations and incentives to promote Nature Positive outcomes*. <https://www.nature-squared.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Changing-the-rules-of-the-game-SUSTAIN.pdf>
- Nestle. (2023). *Creating Shared Value and Sustainability Report 2023*.
<https://www.nestle.com/sites/default/files/2024-02/creating-shared-value-sustainability-report-2023-en.pdf>
- Nestlé Nespresso S.A. (2024). *The Positive Cup: ESG 2024 Progress Document* (p. 36). Nestlé Nespresso S.A. <https://nestle-nespresso.com/sites/site.prod.nestle-nespresso.com/files/Nespresso-ESG-The-Positive-Cup-2024-Progress-Document.pdf>
- Nguyen, H. L., & Kanbach, D. K. (2024). Toward a view of integrating corporate sustainability into strategy: A systematic literature review. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 31(2), 962–976. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2611>
- Niessen, L., & Bocken, N. M. P. (2021). How can businesses drive sufficiency? The business for sufficiency framework. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 1090–1103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.030>
- Nishi, M., Subramanian, S. M., Gupta, H., Yoshino, M., Takahashi, Y., Miwa, K., & Takeda, T. (Eds). (2021). *Fostering Transformative Change for Sustainability in the Context of Socio-Ecological Production Landscapes and Seascapes (SEPLS)*. Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-6761-6>
- Non, A., Rohde, I., De Grip, A., & Dohmen, T. (2022). Mission of the company, prosocial attitudes and job preferences: A discrete choice experiment. *Labour Economics*, 74, 102087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2021.102087>
- Now for Nature. (n.d.). *First nature strategies featured as part of 'It's Now for Nature'*. Retrieved 17 July 2024, from <https://nowfornature.org/>
- Nyborg, K., & Zhang, T. (2013). Is Corporate Social Responsibility Associated with Lower Wages? *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 55(1), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-012-9617-8>
- O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., Agrawal, A., Bennett, E., Biggs, O., Calderón Contreras, R., Carr, E. R., Frantzeskaki, N., Gosnell, H., Gurung, J., Lambertucci, S. A., Leventon, J., Chuan, L., Reyes García, V., Shannon, L., Villasante, S., Wickson, F., Zinngrebe, Y., Périanin, L., ... Zaccagnini, M. E. (2024). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Summary for Policymakers* (Version v10.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11382230>
- OECD. (2014). *Private Financing and Government Support to Promote Long-Term Investments in Infrastructure*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://www.oecd.org/finance/private-financing-and-government-support-to-promote-long-term-investments-in-infrastructure.htm>
- OECD. (2015). *The Private Sector: The Missing Piece of the SDG Puzzle*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://web.archive.oecd.org/2017-04-07/433666-Infographic%20-%20The%20Private%20Sector%20-%20Missing%20Piece%20of%20the%20SDG%20puzzle.pdf>
- OECD. (2020). *OECD DAC Blended Finance Principle 4: Focus on Effective Partnering for Blended Finance*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/blended-finance-principles/documents/Principle_4_Guidance_Note_and_Background.pdf

OECD. (2023). *How Green is Household Behaviour?: Sustainable Choices in a Time of Interlocking Crises*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/2b4bb663-en>

OECD. (2024). *Global Corporate Sustainability Report 2024*. https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2024/03/global-corporate-sustainability-report-2024_d8e1e8b4/8416b635-en.pdf

Österblom, H., Bebbington, J., Blasiak, R., Sobkowiak, M., & Folke, C. (2022). Transnational Corporations, Biosphere Stewardship, and Sustainable Futures. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 609–635. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-120120-052845>

Owen, J. R., Kemp, D., Lechner, A. M., Harris, J., Zhang, R., & Lèbre, É. (2022). Energy transition minerals and their intersection with land-connected peoples. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(2), 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-00994-6>

Pagell, M., & Wu, Z. (2009). BUILDING A MORE COMPLETE THEORY OF SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT USING CASE STUDIES OF 10 EXEMPLARS. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 45(2), 37–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-493X.2009.03162.x>

Pandora Group. (n.d.). *Recycled silver and gold*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://pandoragroup.com/sustainability/circular-innovation/recycled-silver-and-gold>

Panwar, R. (2023). Business and biodiversity: Achieving the 2050 vision for biodiversity conservation through transformative business practices. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 32(11), 3607–3613. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-023-02575-1>

Parkhurst, T., Commander, L., & Standish, R. J. (2025). Global ecosystem accounting standard: A solution to monitor, mitigate, and transparently report global mining impacts in support of biodiversity goals. *One Earth*, 8(9), 101430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101430>

Pascual, U., McElwee, P. D., Diamond, S. E., Ngo, H. T., Bai, X., Cheung, W. W. L., Lim, M., Steiner, N., Agard, J., Donatti, C. I., Duarte, C. M., Leemans, R., Managi, S., Pires, A. P. F., Reyes-García, V., Trisos, C., Scholes, R. J., & Pörtner, H.-O. (2022). Governing for Transformative Change across the Biodiversity–Climate–Society Nexus. *BioScience*, 72(7), 684–704. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biac031>

Patagonia. (2021). *Annual Benefit Corporation Report*. <https://www.patagonia.com/on/demandware.static/-/Library-Sites-PatagoniaShared/default/dw18ad9c7c/PDF-US/Patagonia-2021-BCorp-Report-Updated-2-15-22.pdf>

Patagonia. (2025). *Worn Wear*. <https://eu.patagonia.com/es/en/worn-wear/?srsltid=AfmBOopc8tDpjmqwEpx1m8htgEq4PvZ6gDUTTzLUQ5JLRDSI1EgisNBB>

Peattie, K., & Crane, A. (2005). Green marketing: Legend, myth, farce or prophesy? *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 8(4), 357–370. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13522750510619733>

Phalan, B., Hayes, G., Brooks, S., Marsh, D., Howard, P., Costelloe, B., Vira, B., Kowalska, A., & Whitaker, S. (2018). Avoiding impacts on biodiversity through strengthening the first stage of the mitigation hierarchy. *Oryx*, 52(2), 316–324. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605316001034>

Piet, G. J., Tamis, J. E., Volwater, J., De Vries, P., Van Der Wal, J. T., & Jongbloed, R. H. (2021). A roadmap towards quantitative cumulative impact assessments: Every step of the way. *Science of The Total Environment*, 784, 146847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146847>

- Pollination, & Tsakforce on Nature Markets. (2023). *Biodiversity Credit Markets. The role of law, regulation and policy*. https://cdn.prod.website-files.com/623a362e6b1a3e2eb749839c/6452340b9bcbb3ef3f82e6b6_BiodiversityCreditMarkets.pdf
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneth, A., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L. (William), Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., ... Ngo, H. (2021). *Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change* (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4659158>
- Poulton, D. W., & Maron, M. (2025). Distinguishing among remediation, reclamation, and offsetting in the pursuit of no net loss. *Journal of Environmental Management*, *391*, 126569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126569>
- PRI. (2022). *Discussing divestment: Developing an approach when pursuing sustainability outcomes in listed equities*. <https://www.unpri.org/stewardship/discussing-divestment-developing-an-approach-when-pursuing-sustainability-outcomes-in-listed-equities/9594.article>
- Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI). (2021). *An Introduction to Responsible Investment: Stewardship* [Guidance]. UN PRI. <https://www.unpri.org>
- PSCI. (n.d.). *Pharmaceutical's pharmaceutical supply chain initiative*. Retrieved 19 July 2024, from <https://pscinitiative.org/supplierPartnership>
- Puppim de Oliveira, J. A., Mukhi, U., Quental, C., & de Oliveira Cerqueira Fortes, P. J. (2022). Connecting businesses and biodiversity conservation through community organizing: The case of babassu breaker women in Brazil. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *31*(5), 2618–2634. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3134>
- Purvis, B., Mao, Y., & Robinson, D. (2019). Three pillars of sustainability: In search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science*, *14*(3), 681–695. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-018-0627-5>
- Purwandani, J. A., & Michaud, G. (2021). What are the drivers and barriers for green business practice adoption for SMEs? *Environment Systems and Decisions*, *41*(4), 577–593. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-021-09821-3>
- Quarshie, A. M., Salmi, A., & Leuschner, R. (2016). Sustainability and corporate social responsibility in supply chains: The state of research in supply chain management and business ethics journals. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, *22*(2), 82–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2015.11.001>
- Rainey, H. J., Pollard, E. H. B., Dutson, G., Ekstrom, J. M. M., Livingstone, S. R., Temple, H. J., & Pilgrim, J. D. (2015). A review of corporate goals of No Net Loss and Net Positive Impact on biodiversity. *Oryx*, *49*(2), 232–238. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605313001476>
- Reid, A. J., Carlson, A. K., Creed, I. F., Eliason, E. J., Gell, P. A., Johnson, P. T. J., Kidd, K. A., MacCormack, T. J., Olden, J. D., Ormerod, S. J., Smol, J. P., Taylor, W. W., Tockner, K., Vermaire, J. C., Dudgeon, D., & Cooke, S. J. (2019). Emerging threats and persistent conservation challenges for freshwater biodiversity. *Biological Reviews*, *94*(3), 849–873. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12480>
- Reside, A. E., Cosgrove, A. J., Pointon, R., Trezise, J., Watson, J. E. M., & Maron, M. (2019). How to send a finch extinct. *Environmental Science & Policy*, *94*, 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.01.005>
- Retief, F., Bond, A., Pope, J., Morrison-Saunders, A., & King, N. (2016). Global megatrends and their implications for environmental assessment practice. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, *61*, 52–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2016.07.002>

- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., Drüke, M., Fetzer, I., Bala, G., von Bloh, W., Feulner, G., Fiedler, S., Gerten, D., Gleeson, T., Hofmann, M., Huiskamp, W., Kummu, M., Mohan, C., Nogués-Bravo, D., ... Rockström, J. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh2458>
- Rimba collective. (n.d.). *Collective action to deliver individual corporate sustainability commitments*. Retrieved 20 July 2024, from <https://rimbacollective.com/>
- Rooibos Council. (n.d.). Retrieved 10 September 2025, from <https://sarooibos.co.za/>
- Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO). (n.d.). *Biodiversity and High Conservation Value (HCV) Working Group*. Working Groups. Retrieved <https://rspo.org/who-we-are/governance/working-groups/biodiversity-hcv-working-group/>
- Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO). (2022). *RSPO Free, Prior and Informed Consent, Guide (2022)* (Guidance RSPO-GUI-T08-002 V2 ENG; p. 65). Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO). https://rspo.org/library/lib_files/preview/1571
- RSPO. (2024). *Impact Report 2024*. https://rspo.org/wp-content/uploads/RSPO_ImpactReport_2024.pdf
- Rueda, X., Garrett, R. D., & Lambin, E. F. (2017). Corporate investments in supply chain sustainability: Selecting instruments in the agri-food industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 2480–2492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.026>
- Sahanala. (n.d.). *Sahanala Madagascar*. Retrieved <https://sahanala.net/about-us/>
- Salmi, A., Quarshie, A. M., Scott-Kennel, J., & Kähkönen, A.-K. (2023). Biodiversity management: A supply chain practice view. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 29(4), 100865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2023.100865>
- Sancha, C., Wong, C. W. Y., & Gimenez, C. (2019). Do dependent suppliers benefit from buying firms' sustainability practices? *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 25(4), 100542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2019.100542>
- SBTi. (2024). *SBTi Corporate Net-Zero Standard* (Version 1.2). <https://files.sciencebasedtargets.org/production/files/Net-Zero-Standard.pdf>
- SBTi. (2025). *Financial Institutions Net-Zero Standard* (Version 1.0). <https://files.sciencebasedtargets.org/production/files/Financial-Institutions-Net-Zero-Standard.pdf>
- SBTN. (2020). *Science-Based Targets for Nature. Initial Guidance for Business*. <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/SBTN-initial-guidance-for-business.pdf>
- Schaltegger, S., Christ, K. L., Wenzig, J., & Burritt, R. L. (2022). Corporate sustainability management accounting and multi-level links for sustainability – A systematic review. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 24(4), 480–500. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12288>
- Schaltegger, S., Gibassier, D., & Maas, K. (2023). Managing and accounting for corporate biodiversity contributions. Mapping the field. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(5), 2544–2553. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3166>
- Scheidel, A., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Bara, A. H., Del Bene, D., David-Chavez, D. M., Fanari, E., Garba, I., Hanaček, K., Liu, J., Martínez-Alier, J., Navas, G., Reyes-García, V., Roy, B., Temper, L., Thiri, M. A., Tran, D., Walter, M., & Whyte, K. P. (2023). Global impacts of extractive and industrial development projects on Indigenous Peoples' lifeways, lands, and rights. *Science Advances*, 9(23), eade9557. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.ade9557>
- Schroeder, D., Chennells, R., Louw, C., Snyders, L., & Hodges, T. (2020). The Rooibos Benefit Sharing Agreement—Breaking New Ground with Respect, Honesty, Fairness, and Care.

- Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics*, 29(2), 285–301.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0963180119001075>
- Science Based Targets Network (SBTN). (n.d.-a). *About the Science Based Targets Network*. Retrieved <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/about/>
- Science Based Targets Network (SBTN). (n.d.-b). *Landscape Engagement Target*. Retrieved <https://sciencebasedtargetsnetwork.org/companies/take-action/set-targets/land-targets/address-landscape-pressures/>
- Science Based Targets Network (SBTN). (2024). *SBTN's Materiality Screening Tool*. https://amandahyman.shinyapps.io/MST_shiny/
- SEEA. (n.d.). *SEEA Central Framework*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://seea.un.org/content/seea-central-framework>
- Sharma, U. (2003). *Tendu Leaves. Trade and management practices in India*. INDIRA GANDHI NATIONAL FOREST ACADEMY, DEHRADUN.
<https://www.ignfa.gov.in/document/biodiversity-cell-ntfp-related-issues15.pdf>
- Shrikanth, S., Zu Ermgassen, S., & Bull, J. W. (2025). Nature markets are nothing new—They are widespread, regulated and instructive. *Nature*, 638(8050), 321–321.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-025-00432-5>
- Simmonds, J. S., Sonter, L. J., Watson, J. E. M., Bennun, L., Costa, H. M., Dutson, G., Edwards, S., Grantham, H., Griffiths, V. F., Jones, J. P. G., Kiesecker, J., Possingham, H. P., Puydarrieux, P., Quétier, F., Rainer, H., Rainey, H., Roe, D., Savy, C. E., Souquet, M., ... Maron, M. (2020). Moving from biodiversity offsets to a target-based approach for ecological compensation. *Conservation Letters*, 13(2), e12695. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12695>
- Simmonds, J. S., Von Hase, A., Quétier, F., Brownlie, S., Maron, M., Possingham, H. P., Souquet, M., Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Ten Kate, K., Costa, H. M., & Sonter, L. J. (2022). Aligning ecological compensation policies with the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework to achieve real net gain in biodiversity. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(3), e12634. <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12634>
- Simmonds, J. S., & Watson, J. E. M. (2019). All threatened species habitat is important. *Animal Conservation*, 22(4), 324–325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12518>
- Singh, S. K., Chen, J., Del Giudice, M., & El-Kassar, A.-N. (2019). Environmental ethics, environmental performance, and competitive advantage: Role of environmental training. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 146, 203–211.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.05.032>
- Skouloudis, A., Malesios, C., & Dimitrakopoulos, P. G. (2019). Corporate biodiversity accounting and reporting in mega-diverse countries: An examination of indicators disclosed in sustainability reports. *Ecological Indicators*, 98, 888–901.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.11.060>
- Smith, G. S., Ascui, F., O'Grady, A. P., & Pinkard, E. (2021). Materiality Assessment of Natural Capital Risks in Australian Forestry. *Current Forestry Reports*, 7(4), 282–304.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-021-00147-6>
- Smith, T., Beagley, L., Bull, J., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Smith, M., Vorhies, F., & Addison, P. F. E. (2020). Biodiversity means business: Reframing global biodiversity goals for the private sector. *Conservation Letters*, 13(1), e12690. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12690>
- Smith, T., Paavola, J., & Holmes, G. (2019). Corporate reporting and conservation realities: Understanding differences in what businesses say and do regarding biodiversity. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 29(1), 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1839>

- Sonter, L. J., Dade, M. C., Watson, J. E. M., & Valenta, R. K. (2020). Renewable energy production will exacerbate mining threats to biodiversity. *Nature Communications*, *11*(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17928-5>
- Sousa, P., Gomes, D., & Formigo, N. (2020). Ecosystem services in environmental impact assessment. *Energy Reports*, *6*, 466–471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2019.09.009>
- SpencerStuart. (2023). *Sustainability Stocktake: How CEOs Can Turn Vision into Value*. <https://www.spencerstuart.com/-/media/2023/november/sustainabilityvision/sustainability-stocktake-how-ceos-can-turn-vision-into-value.pdf>
- Srivastava, R. (2024, September). 'Jungle is our life': Indian villages collectivise, harness decades-old laws to protect forests. Azim Premji University. <https://azimpremjiuniversity.edu.in/best-practices-in-local-democracy/jungle-is-our-life-indian-villages-collectivise-harness-decades-old-laws-to-protect-forests>
- Standard Chartered. (2024). *Nature Position Statement* (p. 4). Standard Chartered. <https://av.sc.com/corp-en/nr/content/docs/nature-position-statement.pdf>
- Statista. (2025, June). *Secondhand apparel market value worldwide from 2021 to 2029*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/826162/apparel-resale-market-value-worldwide/>
- Swinfield, T., Shrikanth, S., Bull, J. W., Madhavapeddy, A., & Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E. (2024). Nature-based credit markets at a crossroads. *Nature Sustainability*, *7*(10), 1217–1220. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01403-w>
- Tallis, H., Kennedy, C. M., Ruckelshaus, M., Goldstein, J., & Kiesecker, J. M. (2015). Mitigation for one & all: An integrated framework for mitigation of development impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, *55*, 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2015.06.005>
- Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). (n.d.). *Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD)*. Retrieved <https://tnfd.global>
- Taufique, K. M. R., Vocino, A., & Polonsky, M. J. (2017). The influence of eco-label knowledge and trust on pro-environmental consumer behaviour in an emerging market. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, *25*(7), 511–529. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2016.1240219>
- Tayleur, C., Balmford, A., Buchanan, G. M., Butchart, S. H. M., Ducharme, H., Green, R. E., Milder, J. C., Sanderson, F. J., Thomas, D. H. L., Vickery, J., & Phalan, B. (2017). Global Coverage of Agricultural Sustainability Standards, and Their Role in Conserving Biodiversity. *Conservation Letters*, *10*(5), 610–618. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12314>
- Testa, F., Iraldo, F., Vaccari, A., & Ferrari, E. (2015). Why Eco-labels can be Effective Marketing Tools: Evidence from a Study on Italian Consumers. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *24*(4), 252–265. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1821>
- The Confederation of Swedes Enterprises. (2023). *The Business Sector's Role in Strengthening Biodiversity*. https://www.svensktnaringsliv.se/bilder_och_dokument/rapporter/oqgoai_the_business_sectors_role_in_strengthening_biodiversity_digitalpd_1203614.html/The_Business_Sectors_Role_in_Strengthening_Biodiversity_DIGITAL.pdf
- The Fashion Pact. (n.d.). *Our work*. Retrieved 19 July 2024, from <https://www.thefashionpact.org/our-work/#How-we-work>
- The Responsible Jewellery Council. (2024, December). *Chain of Custody*. <https://www.responsiblejewellery.com/wp-content/uploads/RJC-2024-COC-Standard-24-12-10.pdf>
- The World Bank. (2022, March). *Wildlife Conservation Bond Boosts South Africa's Efforts to Protect Black Rhinos and Support Local Communities* [Press release]. PRESS RELEASE NO: 2022/059/AFE. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2022/03/23/wildlife->

conservation-bond-boosts-south-africa-s-efforts-to-protect-black-rhinos-and-support-local-communities

- Thøgersen, J., Haugaard, P., & Olesen, A. (2010). Consumer responses to ecolabels. *European Journal of Marketing*, 44(11/12), 1787–1810. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561011079882>
- Thomas, H., Ward, M. S., Simmonds, J. S., Taylor, M. F. J., & Maron, M. (2025). Poor compliance and exemptions facilitate ongoing deforestation. *Conservation Biology*, 39(1), e14354. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14354>
- Tilba, A., & McNulty, T. (2013). Engaged versus Disengaged Ownership: The Case of Pension Funds in the UK. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 21(2), 165–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2012.00933.x>
- TNFD. (2023a). *Guidance on engagement with Indigenous Peoples, Local Communities and affected stakeholders* (p. 56). https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Guidance_on_engagement_with_Indigenous_Peoples_Local_Communities_and_affected_stakeholders_v1.pdf?v=1695138220
- TNFD. (2023b). *Guidance on the identification and assessment of nature related issues: The LEAP approach* (p. 282). Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD). https://tnfd.global/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Guidance_on_the_identification_and_assessment_of_nature-related-issues_The_TNFD_LEAP_approach_v1.pdf?v=1695138163
- Tony's. (2023). *Tony's Chocology Annual Report*. <https://online.flippingbook.com/view/287207390/7/>
- Torelli, R., & Balluchi, F. (2023). Biodiversity management approaches in small and innovative businesses: Insights from a *systems thinking* perspective. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 19(7), 1297–1319. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-03-2022-0113>
- Treepongkaruna, S. (2024). Corporate sustainability and biodiversity reporting: A proactive business strategy to mitigate litigation and reputational risks. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 33(7), 6640–6651. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3840>
- Tregidga, H., Milne, M., & Kearins, K. (2014). (Re)presenting 'sustainable organizations'. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 39(6), 477–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aos.2013.10.006>
- Turconi, S., Singh, P., & Wang, R. (2021, August). *Natura & Co: Sustainability at Scale*. <https://publishing.london.edu/cases/natura-co-sustainability-at-scale/>
- UK Government. (2023). *Biodiversity net gain*. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/biodiversity-net-gain>
- Ullah, A., Ullah Baber, M., & Arshad, N. (2024). Assessing the Transformative Influence of ChatGPT on Research Practices among Scholars in Pakistan. *Mesopotamian Journal of Big Data*, 2024, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.58496/MJBD/2024/001>
- UN Environment Programme. (2022). *Sand and Sustainability: 10 Strategic Recommendations to Avert a Crisis*. GRID-Geneva, United Nations Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/sand-and-sustainability-10-strategic-recommendations-avert-crisis>
- UN Global Compact and IUCN. (2012). *A Framework for Corporate Action on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. <https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/2012-036.pdf>
- UNDP BIOFIN. (2023). *How Can Biodiversity Finance Plans Support NBSAPs?* United Nations Development Programme, Biodiversity Finance Initiative (BIOFIN). <https://www.biofin.org/knowledge-product/how-can-bfps-support-nbsaps>

- UNEP. (n.d.). *UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration 2021-2030*. Retrieved 2 September 2025, from <https://www.decadeonrestoration.org/>
- UNEP. (2023). *State of Finance for Nature 2023: The Big Nature Turnaround - Repurposing \$7 Trillion to Combat Nature Loss*. United Nations Environment Programme. <https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/44278>
- UNEP. (2024). *Global Resources Outlook. Bend the Trend – Pathways to a liveable planet as resource use spikes*. https://www.resourcepanel.org/sites/default/files/documents/document/media/gro24_full_report_29feb_final_for_web.pdf
- UNEP. (2026). *State of Finance for Nature 2026: Nature in the Red—Powering the Trillion Dollar Nature Transition Economy*. <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/49119>
- UNEP Finance Initiative. (2023). *PRB Nature Target Setting Guidance*. <https://www.unepfi.org/industries/banking/nature-target-setting-guidance/>
- UNEP Finance Initiative (UNEP FI) & UNDP BIOFIN. (2023). *Engaging Private Finance in the NBSAP Review and Implementation: Sign-posts for Policymakers*. UNEP FI and UNDP BIOFIN. <https://www.unepfi.org/publications/engaging-private-finance-in-the-nbsap-review-and-implementation/>
- UNEP-WCMC & UNEP FI. (2024). *Accountability for Nature: Comparison of Nature-Related Assessment and Disclosure Frameworks and Standards* (p. 88). <https://www.unepfi.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Accountability-for-Nature.pdf>
- Unilever. (2024). *Climate Transition Action Plan*. <https://www.unilever.com/files/92ui5egz/production/2a44a1a76f4899f09a2d745ccdd86d0b65185eb5.pdf>
- Union for Ethical BioTrade (UEBT). (2024). *Biodiversity Barometer 2024: Report Summary* (p. 34). Union for Ethical BioTrade. <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/577e0feae4fcb502316dc547/t/67bf1aafb8b1c467400f2b38/1740577461089/UEBT+Biodiversity+Barometer+2024+Report+Summary.pdf>
- United Nations. (2008). *United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples*. https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/unpfii/documents/DRIPS_en.pdf
- United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). (2025). *Voluntary Sustainability Standards*. <https://unctad.org/topic/trade-analysis/voluntary-sustainability-standards>
- United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD). (n.d.). *Great Green Wall Initiative*. Retrieved <https://www.unccd.int/our-work/ggwi>
- Vachon, S., & Klassen, R. D. (2006). Extending green practices across the supply chain: The impact of upstream and downstream integration. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 26(7), 795–821. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443570610672248>
- Van Tulder, R., & Da Rosa, A. (2014). Multinationals and Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs): A linkages perspective on inclusive development strategies. In *Progress in International Business Research* (pp. 203–227). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1745-8862\(2013\)0000008014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1745-8862(2013)0000008014)
- Vanclay, F. (2017). Principles to gain a social licence to operate for green initiatives and biodiversity projects. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 29, 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2017.11.003>
- Vanclay, F., & Esteves, A. M. (Eds). (2024). *Handbook of Social Impact Assessment and Management*. Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781802208870>

Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people
Chapter 5. Businesses as key actors of change: options for action.

- Vaude. (n.d.). *VAUDE Rent—Dein Mietservice für umweltfreundliche und fair produzierte Outdoor-Ausrüstung*. Retrieved 9 September 2025, from <https://rent-secondhand.vaude.com/pages/mieten>
- Vijay, V., Pimm, S. L., Jenkins, C. N., & Smith, S. J. (2016). The Impacts of Oil Palm on Recent Deforestation and Biodiversity Loss. *PLOS ONE*, *11*(7), e0159668. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0159668>
- Villarroya, A., Barros, A. C., & Kiesecker, J. (2014). Policy Development for Environmental Licensing and Biodiversity Offsets in Latin America. *PLOS ONE*, *9*(9), e107144. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0107144>
- Villena, V. H., & Gioia, D. A. (2018). On the riskiness of lower-tier suppliers: Managing sustainability in supply networks. *Journal of Operations Management*, *64*(1), 65–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2018.09.004>
- WBA. (2024). *Nature Benchmark 2022-2024*. Nature Benchmark. <https://www.worldbenchmarkingalliance.org/publication/nature/>
- WBCSD. (2023a). *Roadmap to Nature Positive: Foundations for the agri-food system Row crop commodities subsector. Deep dive: Soy production in the Cerrado, Brazil*. <https://www.wbcd.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Deep-dive-Soy.pdf>
- WBCSD. (2023b). *Roadmaps to Nature Positive: Foundations for all businesses* (Roadmaps to Nature Positive). World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). <https://www.wbcd.org/resources/roadmaps-to-nature-positive-foundations-for-all-businesses/>
- WBCSD. (2025, May). *Implementing outcome-based metrics to scale regenerative agriculture*. <https://www.wbcd.org/resources/implementing-outcome-based-metrics-to-scale-regenerative-agriculture/>
- We Mean Business Coalition. (2023). *CLIMATE AMBITION TO ADVOCACY: A framework for responsible policy engagement*. <https://www.wemeanbusinesscoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/A-Framework-for-Responsible-Policy-Engagement-%E2%80%93RPE.pdf>
- WEF. (2020). *New Nature Economy Report II: The Future Of Nature And Business*. New Nature Economy series. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/new-nature-economy-report-ii-the-future-of-nature-and-business/>
- WEF. (2023). *Nature Positive: Role of the Cement and Concrete Sector*. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Nature_Positive_Role_of_the_Cement_and_Concrete_Sector_2023.pdf
- WEF. (2025). *The Global Risks Report 2025*. https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Risks_Report_2025.pdf
- Weymouth, S. (2012). Firm lobbying and influence in developing countries: A multilevel approach. *Business and Politics*, *14*(4), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1515/bap-2012-0030>
- Whelan, T. (2024, February). *Boards Better Prepared in 2024 for Tackling Financial Material Sustainability Issues but Major Weaknesses Persist*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/18P3JiGRMxjT6Dc01ouMUECC9eD5A4ftP/view>
- White, K., Habib, R., & Hardisty, D. J. (2019). How to SHIFT Consumer Behaviors to be More Sustainable: A Literature Review and Guiding Framework. *Journal of Marketing*, *83*(3), 22–49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022242919825649>
- White, T. B., Petrovan, S. O., Bennun, L. A., Butterworth, T., Christie, A. P., Downey, H., Hunter, S. B., Jobson, B. R., zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., & Sutherland, W. J. (2023). Principles for using evidence to improve biodiversity impact mitigation by business. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, *n/a*(n/a). <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3389>

- White, T., Bromwich, T., Bang, A., Bennun, L., Bull, J., Clark, M., Milner-Gulland, E. J., Prescott, G. W., Starkey, M., Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., & Booth, H. (2024). The “nature-positive” journey for business: A conceptual research agenda to guide contributions to societal biodiversity goals. *One Earth*, 7(8), 1373–1386.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.07.003>
- Whiteman, G., Walker, B., & Perego, P. (2013). Planetary Boundaries: Ecological Foundations for Corporate Sustainability. *Journal of Management Studies*, 50(2), 307–336.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2012.01073.x>
- Wicki, S., & Hansen, E. G. (2019). Green technology innovation: Anatomy of exploration processes from a learning perspective. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(6), 970–988.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2295>
- Wieland, A. (2021). Dancing the Supply Chain: Toward Transformative Supply Chain Management. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 57(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jscm.12248>
- Wilcove, D. S., & Koh, L. P. (2010). Addressing the threats to biodiversity from oil-palm agriculture. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 19(4), 999–1007.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-009-9760-x>
- Williams, A., Perego, P., & Whiteman, G. (2025). Boundary Conditions for Organizations in the Anthropocene: A Review of the Planetary Boundaries Framework 10 Years On. *Journal of Management Studies*, 62(4), 1811–1846. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.13150>
- Wilting, H. C., Schipper, A. M., Bakkenes, M., Meijer, J. R., & Huijbregts, M. A. J. (2017). Quantifying Biodiversity Losses Due to Human Consumption: A Global-Scale Footprint Analysis. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 51(6), 3298–3306.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b05296>
- World Bank. (2017). *The World Bank Environmental and Social Framework*. World Bank.
<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/383011492423734099/pdf/The-World-Bank-Environmental-and-Social-Framework.pdf>
- World Bank. (2019, October 16). *World Bank SME Finance* [Text/HTML]. World Bank.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/sme/finance>
- World Bank. (2021). *Forest-Smart Mining: Guidance to Applying Nature-Based Solutions in the Large-Scale Mining Sector*. World Bank.
https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099120005072233028/pdf/P1722450216bf0fe0a1940eb4798287bc1.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- World Bank. (2022a). *Business Enabling Environment*.
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/2250b12dfe798507f7b42064378cc616-0540012022/original/BEE-Concept-Note-December-2022.pdf>
- World Bank. (2022b). *NATURE AND DEVELOPMENT Integrating Climate and Nature Action* (p. 132). World Bank.
<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/0054ddab7bfac0338f255a2ea5d9c32e-0320012022/original/2-Nature-Climate.pdf>
- World Benchmarking Alliance. (2023). *2023 Nature Benchmark*.
<https://www.worldbenchmarkingalliance.org/publication/nature/#:~:text=The%202023%20iteration%20of%20the,world's%20food%20and%20agriculture%20revenue>
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). (n.d.). *World Business Council for Sustainable Development*. Retrieved <https://www.wbcsd.org/>
- World Wildlife Fund (WWF). (n.d.). *Forests and Human Health*. Retrieved <https://www.worldwildlife.org/initiatives/forests-and-human-health>
- Wunder, S., Fraccaroli, C., Bull, J. W., Dutta, T., Eyres, A., Evans, M. C., Thorsen, B. J., Jones, J. P. G., Maron, M., Muys, B., Pacheco, A., Olesen, A. S., Swinfield, T., Tegegne, Y. T., White, T.

- B., Zhang, H., & Zu Ermgassen, S. (2024). *Biodiversity credits: Learning lessons from other approaches to incentivize conservation*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qgwfc>
- Yadav, S., & Prajapati, S. (2023, July). *Korchi's Forest Communities and the Mahagrame Sabha*. <https://wri-india.org/perspectives/korchis-forest-communities-and-mahagrame-sabha>
- Yamahaki, C., & Marchewitz, C. (2024). Collaborative investor engagement with policymakers: Changing the rules of the game? *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*.
- Yeung, H. W.-C. (2009). Transnational Corporations, Global Production Networks, and Urban and Regional Development: A Geographer's Perspective on Multinational Enterprises and the Global Economy. *Growth and Change*, 40(2), 197–226. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2257.2009.00473.x>
- Young, R. E., Gann, G. D., Walder, B., Liu, J., Cui, W., Newton, V., Nelson, C. R., Tashe, N., Jasper, D., Silveira, F. A. O., Carrick, P. J., Hägglund, T., Carlsén, S., & Dixon, K. (2022). International principles and standards for the ecological restoration and recovery of mine sites. *Restoration Ecology*, 30(S2), e13771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13771>
- Zadek, S. (2007). The Path to Corporate Responsibility. In W. C. Zimmerli, M. Holzinger, & K. Richter (Eds), *Corporate Ethics and Corporate Governance* (pp. 159–172). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-70818-6_13
- Zhu, Y., Prescott, G. W., Chu, P., & Carrasco, L. R. (2024). Glaring gaps in tools to estimate businesses' biodiversity impacts hinder alignment with the Kunming-Montreal global biodiversity framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142079>
- zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Drewniok, M. P., Bull, J. W., Corlet Walker, C. M., Mancini, M., Ryan-Collins, J., & Cabrera Serrenho, A. (2022). A home for all within planetary boundaries: Pathways for meeting England's housing needs without transgressing national climate and biodiversity goals. *Ecological Economics*, 201, 107562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107562>
- zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Howard, M., Bennun, L., Addison, P. F. E., Bull, J. W., Loveridge, R., Pollard, E., & Starkey, M. (2022). Are corporate biodiversity commitments consistent with delivering 'nature-positive' outcomes? A review of 'nature-positive' definitions, company progress and challenges. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134798>
- Zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., & Löfqvist, S. (2024). Financing ecosystem restoration. *Current Biology*, 34(9), R412–R417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2024.02.031>
- zu Ermgassen, S. O. S. E., Utamiputri, P., Bennun, L., Edwards, S., & Bull, J. W. (2019). The Role of "No Net Loss" Policies in Conserving Biodiversity Threatened by the Global Infrastructure Boom. *One Earth*, 1(3), 305–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2019.10.019>
-